

School of Business & Creative Industries

**Investigating Critical Success Factors (CSF's) in Enterprise Risk Management
(ERM) Adoption in The Telecommunication Industry:
Case of Algeria Telecommunication Industry.**

A Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of The
West of Scotland for the award of Doctoral in Business Administration

By

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the Critical Success Factors (CSFs) influencing the adoption of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) in the Telecommunication Industry of Algeria, with a focus on the dynamic and complex risk environment faced by the sector. The study employs qualitative methods in an exploratory design, incorporating interviews with twenty-six key informants from Algeria's Telecommunication industry to discern the factors prompting ERM adoption. Findings reveal that ERM adoption remains at an early stage, with organizations predominantly employing traditional "silo" risk management methods. The research contributes by developing a customized ERM framework tailored to the specific challenges of the Algerian telecommunications industry, emphasizing the need for enhanced risk education and awareness among stakeholders. The proposed framework aims to foster collaboration, information sharing, and effective risk management practices to address both existing and emerging risks in the sector.

The research asserts that the Algerian telecommunication industry is maturing and faces vulnerability to diverse risks, necessitating the implementation of a robust ERM framework. The proposed framework, designed to accommodate strategic organizational objectives and manage emotional risks, emerges as a crucial tool in navigating the dynamic risk landscape. Recommendations include further research on Algeria's telecommunication industry and exploring the role of ERM frameworks in driving organizational performance.

Key terms: Enterprise Risk Management (ERM), Critical Success Factors (CSFs), Telecommunication Industry, Risk Management, Multi-Sim Card Enablement, Market Penetration, Regulatory Authority for Post and Telecommunications

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ISO : International Organisation for Standardisation

COSO : The Committee of Sponsoring Organisations of the Treadway Commission

Key Informants (**KI**)

Chief Executive Officers (**CEOs**),

Chief Financial Officers (**CFOs**),

Chief Auditors Officers (**CAO**),

Chief Strategic Officers (**CSOs**),

Revenue Assurance Manager (**RAM**)

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this thesis titled “Investigating Critical Success Factors (CSF’s)in Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) Adoption in The Telecommunication Industry: Case of Algeria Telecommunication Industry” has not previously been accepted in substance for any degree or qualification and is not being concurrently submitted for any other degree.

This work is the result of my own research, else where otherwise stated.

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Signed : Mohamed Amine BOURABA

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION.

1.1 Study Background.

Enterprise risk refers to the difference between a firm's corporate objectives and the outcomes of its corporate strategies. Enterprise risks are all the processes and occurrences that happen during the set time that prevent a firm from achieving the corporate objectives they have set up. These occurrences could either be internal or external. Either way, firms have to enact means to prevent this difference as part of their corporate strategy to ensure the achievement of their goals (Dionne and Review, 2013). The designs vary from one organisation to another since factors that cause these differences are particular to firms based on their business type, size, location, and environment.

There are several types of risk management: corporate risk management, business risk management, holistic risk management, strategic risk management, and integrated risk management. ERM represents the return of the original roots of risk management, which was first developed in the 1950s by a group of innovative insurance professors. Enterprise risk management is a risk identification and addressing process that involves finding out and dealing with threats to the objectives, strategies, and opportunities. It is necessary for strategic management for risk assessment and finding suitable solutions in response that organisations use to anticipate future problems. Enterprises can respond to risks by tolerating, reducing, or terminating them. Different firms have varying attitudes towards risks and risk management (Lončarski, 2016). The effectiveness of their implementation of these attitudes determines the success of their risk management strategies.

The telecommunications sector is one of the areas that has evolved most significantly over the past several years. It has also caused revolutions in both system-wide and system-use aspects—evolutions like these result in many communication networks being set up without adequate consideration of the risks involved. IT-dependent digital elements today (computers, networks, contents, etc.) or infrastructures are at the center of our lives; they constitute the essential pillars of our communication, economic, social, and institutional infrastructures. The banking and insurance industries have adapted the existing risk management concepts, but the communication industry is not fit to cope with the specific needs. It would be beneficial if companies could define particular elements that need to be examined while assessing the risk in the telecommunication systems (Gwendal Le Grand, Eyal Adar, 2007). Additional analysis is needed to adapt these frameworks to the telecommunication world; a layer must rely on a thorough and multi-staged understanding of its unique business needs and requirements and its specific systems and procedures.

The Algerian telecom industry has significantly developed over the past two decades and currently has a 100% market penetration. It hosts four mobile phone network operators who serve a large market since Algeria occupies a lot of geographical space and is highly populated. One of the operators is a government-owned mobile network company. The inception of 3G and 4G phone internet services in 2013 and 2016, respectively, made the sector one of the most profitable (Telecommunications: Algeria, 2012). The sector's turnover is 4.5 billion dollars, and it contributes to around 4% of the Algerian GDP.

One of the four mobile network operators is a state-owned Algerian fixed-line operation. The fixed-line segment consists of land-line operations and wireless local loop connections. The current subscribers to the fixed-line element are about 3.27 million people. Since the start of the

millennium, the feature declined and only peaked in 2005 after the government altered some constitutional laws concerning its operations. The law was enacted to increase competition in the sector and reduce the cost of their services that were high then. The remaining three are mobile networks; Optimum Telecom Algeria, Algeria Telecom Mobile, and Wataniya Telecom Algeria.

Due to multi-sim card enablement, the Algeria Telecom industry has a record market penetration of over 100% (Telecommunications: Algeria, 2015). The multi-sim enablement is widespread because the Algeria Regulatory Authority for Post and Telecommunications passed a law to compel the mobile network operators to have a 3G double numbering license. The law forced customers who wanted to acquire 3G sim cards to get 2G sim cards. As a result, the three mobile network firms are incredibly competitive, with small margins of total market shares. Pre-payment mobile services are preferred in the region over post-payment. Corporate accounts account for most of the post-paid options.

The Algeria mass media is well-spread throughout the 48 provinces of the nation. They have over 46 television broadcasting stations, fewer radio broadcast stations, and many televisions and radios. They also have around four internet service providers, 500 internet hosts, and many internet users. The mass media present in the two Algerian national languages, Arabic and French, and a few stations broadcast in English and Tamazight. Their government controls the leading broadcasting houses and all TVs and radio station outlets with mass media. The Algerian government uses laws to censor mass media. A defamation law prevents news outlets from speaking against political figures. Algerian mass media outlets commemorate the introduction of this oppressive law by withholding publications and news on the anniversary of its introduction day.

For a booming business like the telecommunications business in Algeria, risk management is an essential part of management. Covid 19 taught the necessity of telecommunications and the need to keep the systems secure. A secure, effective, and efficient telecommunications system is essential for both the running of a nation and the safety of citizens. With the lockdown measures to stop the spread of Covid 19, people stuck in their homes needed to communicate. Workers working from home used telecommunications to operate and manage their work relations and updates. So as other businesses made losses during this period, telecommunications firms made huge profits and expanded their businesses.

Like telecommunications industries everywhere, the nature of the telecommunications business in Algeria makes it prone to numerous risks. The complexity of telecommunications in terms of data, mobile networks, cloud infrastructure, underlying technological infrastructure, and fixed-line operations increases their risk scope. In addition, more business activities conducted by one company increase the potentiality of threats. The telecommunications supply chain process, regulatory guidelines, cyber security risks, and talent risks all arise from the complexity of the process and underlying technology.

1.2 Emergence and Evolution of ERM

The emergence of RM frameworks was triggered by high-profile corporate scandals that led to company failures. The losses were preventable if the right risk management frameworks had been adopted. ERM frameworks have existed since the 1990s, but the need for adoption as a corporate decision tool happened after the financial crisis of 2008 (Yang et al., 2018). Organisations were required to adopt more comprehensive and efficient risk management frameworks after significant misappropriation scandals of corporate funds and financial

misrepresentation in disclosures, which led to corporate failures and loss. It was also when technology was fully operationalised and integrated into most organisations' systems (Alawattegama, 2018). Thus, there was a need to use risk management frameworks that captured emerging risks.

Traditional ERM frameworks could not keep up with the dynamism of the risks and corporate frauds evolving with technology development. Traditional risk systems focused on insurable risks where transferring is the most viable risk response—the fear of managing risks that cannot be transferred limits the organisation from investing in inherent risks. Traditional ERM frameworks are sporadic and reactive as they deal with risks after they have happened. Another reason why traditional risk frameworks could fail to keep up with the changing risk environment is that they are standardized and focus on managing and avoiding risks instead of the modern frameworks that are dynamic and allow for case to case adoption basis. Traditional frameworks are risk-averse as they define risks as a negative aspect of the business. Using traditional risk methods makes the company avoid risky ventures, which may limit its opportunities. Traditional risk methods do not manage risks organisational-wide. The risks are managed in silos or functions, where departments work on departmental risks. Resources are allocated to departments to develop their risk management processes. Departments only manage the inherent risks while most of the risks are transferred, for instance, insuring them to protect the organisation. Therefore, there is a need to adopt the new ERM frameworks for the organisation to venture into risky business ventures as the systems manage existing and emerging risks effectively.

1.3 Risks facing the telecommunication industry

Understanding the risks inherent in the telecommunication industry is pivotal for contextualizing the investigation into Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) adoption in the Algerian telecommunications sector. The complexity of modern telecommunication, characterized by state-of-the-art technology delivering diverse business applications and services over cloud, fixed-line, and mobile infrastructure (Alawattegama, 2018), underscores the significance of effective risk management practices. The inclusion of risk factors such as investment risk, talent risk, privacy, safety, and security risk, regulation risks, and supply chain risk is crucial as it provides a comprehensive snapshot of the multifaceted challenges faced by telecommunication companies globally (Chen et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2018).

- **Investment risk:** The companies are capital intensive due to the level of technology and consumers to offer quality products, which requires these organisations to invest in costly upgrade programs frequently (Chen et al., 2021).
- **Talent risk:** The organisations lack the relevant expertise that matches the level of technology investments.
- **Privacy, safety, and security risk:** Telecom companies offer se services, making them a target for cybercrimes (Chen et al., 2021).
- **Regulation risks-** There are various compliance requirements for these firms that are diverse and complex, and failure to manage leads to non-compliance, which may affect the firm adversely.
- **Supply chain risk:** These are risks associated with producing and disseminating telecommunication products (Yang et al., 2018).

1.4 Overview of Enterprise Risk Management

The concept of enterprise risk management came up in the mid-1990s among corporations. During this time, companies shifted their management models to center on creating value for their shareholders. Moreover, due to massive losses some corporations had suffered due to unanticipated risks, firms felt obligated to come up with measures to counter threats to maintain and increase their shareholders' value. Risk management, however, as a concept can be traced to an earlier time - the 1950s.

Risk management was incorporated into companies' decision-making functions soon after its inception. Insurance companies arose from the discovery of risk management and its inception into management. At first, firms found ways to transfer worker's accidents, natural disasters, and human errors like fraudulent cases to insurance companies. As risk management progressed, companies started to protect against insurance and financial risks. Commercial risks like credit risks could be incurred by insurance companies too.

Traditional risk practices viewed risk as independent functions. Every risk was identified and dealt with in a stand-alone manner. Traditional management focused on managing the risks individually at the lowest cost possible to prevent losses. Its optimisation, therefore, was buying the cheapest insurance against risks. These risks they dealt with were primarily risks arising from occupational hazards. Risks arising from their strategies and daily operations were left to the workers in those departments. They were also not singled out but dealt with together within the department.

The existence and growth of insurance markets informed managers that they could shoulder these risks. With time, management found ways to reduce the impact of risks on their firms or prevent them altogether. In the 1970s, companies started to broaden their risk management by

creating functional systems that could anticipate and diffuse the risks. Financial risks became a priority since firms existed to increase their profitability and financial management determined the success of companies. Financial risks include commodity prices, exchange rates, and interest rate risks.

As contingency planning adoption became a norm, firms merged their insurable and financial risks and made decisions. As a result, management approaches included risk identification, assessment, and management. This process encouraged the establishment of various insurance companies that could shoulder all types of risks for businesses. It also urged managers to adopt these systems to achieve their company objectives.

Enterprise risk management arose from combining all these facets of risks that firms had learned to counter. First, enterprise risk is deduced from outlining all possible scenarios that could prevent the firm's goal attainment every year. Then, it is finding ways to avoid all these scenarios or reduce their impact so a company can attain its goals. Most firms align their objectives to their shareholders' value to limit their risk coverage. This process is the shareholders' framework of risk management. It is focused on managing the stock values of a company. The closer the risk management is to the shareholders' value, the easier it is to deduce enterprise risk.

(Fraser, 2013) denotes that ERM requires companies to create consolidated risk profiles by merging all these facets of business risks and dealing with them under the ERM entity. He defines a compact risk profile as outlining organisation's tolerance, risk capacity, and risk requirements. He states that creating a consolidated risk profile is beneficial as it expands the scope of risk management to include human capital, competitors' techniques, long-term strategies, and operational unveilings. All these pinpoint the competitive advantage risk accords firms. Fraser attributes the competitive advantage firms have in various sectors to the superiority of their consolidated risk profiles and the effectiveness of their implementation.

The choice of corporate strategy determines the overall approach to counter enterprise

risks. It, therefore, is a top to bottom process as decisions on the framework to implement are made by the top management. Risk response refers to an nation's leadership actions to solve the various risk transference can be done by divesting corporate functions or outsourcing operating functions. Alleviating corporate functions is done through hedging, divestment, and outsourcing transfer of the corporate activities themselves rather than just the attached risks. All risk transferences require companies to transfer the entire movement except insurance transference. There are several risk response practices that most organisations choose from. The risk response strategies for ERM include risk avoidance, which refers to eliminating activities that can negatively impact the nation's assets. Risk reduction -this strategy prefers the mitigation or limitation of severity losses. Alternative actions – include considering other possible ways to reduce risk. Share or insures approach – the act of transferring risk to third parties. i.e., insurance agencies. Finally, risk acceptance is where the most organisation accepts the risks and possible consequences.

All risks that a firm suffers would be enterprise risks if legal options, hedging, divesting, and outsourcing options did not exist. However, enterprise risks are considered insurable and financial troubles because they exist. The complexity of risk management led to the formation of risk departments. The risk department has risk identification, assessment, and management functions. They have to work communally with the top management, finance offices, strategic planning department, and external service providers like insurers. The finance department is in charge of funding risk management activities, while the strategic department liaises with the risks department to decide on strategies.

Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) is one of the most beneficial practices adopted by firms over the last century and the start of this millennium. The efficiency of a firm's ERM significantly ascertains the success of its business and business model. It gives shareholders and management confidence in the success of their objectives and business. It improves the efficiency of all aspects of business practices. It cements a firm's compliance with the legal regulations, taxing, and auditing requirements. Above all, it shines a light on the risks in a business and deals with them. That is its core function.

Enterprise risk management as a concept emerged in Algeria a little later than world superpowers. As ERM was being established and incorporated into nations, Algeria was experiencing a civil war that incapacitated business operations. In the early 2000s, as the Algerian government stabilised and the country healed from unrest, business started booming, and the concept of ERM practices emerged. Due to its close business relations with the UK, Algeria followed the ERM framework from the UK. They abide by the International Organisation for Standardization ERM standards - the ISO 31000:2009 framework. The nation has also set up risk management bodies that have set up systematic, principles-based analogies to deal with risk.

Algeria's region has always been affected by political risks as the first business risk. The northern part of Africa is prone to military coups and political instability. Algeria has, however, been stable since its civil wars unrest in the 1990s. Being an oil-producing nation has been a significant contributor to its stable GDP that has consistently increased over the past decades. Energy accounts for 40% of their GDP and 10% of their GDP earnings. The energy sector's growth affected growth in financing, telecommunications, engineering, education, healthcare, retail, agriculture, and mining. As a result, their economic situation effectively improved, making the nation relatively economically stable and a better performer than most developing nations.

Despite its economic and political stability, like most developing countries, Algeria has a structure problem that makes it harder to do business. The government tries to combat corruption in their dealings by following strict rules when handling their tenders. Still, Algeria maintains its rank among the world's most corrupt nations. In addition, being an Islamic nation, Algeria has had gender oppression issues and other forms of human rights abuses that may discourage some businesses from setting up and increasing their risk coverage. The above accounts for most of the external national risks all types of businesses suffer in the nation.

The telecommunications industry in Algeria faces similar risks to all other telecommunications firms globally. However, the institutional framework in the nation is significantly hard due to the guidelines set up for the sector and general industry guidelines in the country. In addition, their red tape laws increase regulatory risks for telecommunications firms. Nevertheless, the four telecommunications firms in the nation still record one of the best profitability indexes due to the effective risk management practices the country has adopted.

1.5 Risk Management in The Telecommunications Industry

The telecommunications industry has been on the rise over the past decade. The innovation and establishment of mobile computers, the internet, accessible data connection, and general technological advancement have contributed to the growth of the telecommunications sector. However, like any other business, the telecommunications companies are comprised of different functional factions working together to achieve similar objectives (Boettinger, 1982). Therefore,

anticipating and handling business exposures in the sector to smoothen their way is expected in the telecommunications sector.

The telecommunications business is prone to numerous risks. They confront all types of threats while offering their communication and financial services. Other companies seek these services from telecom companies because the costs of acquiring market data, efficient communications, and transacting economic efficiency are lower. In addition, the benefits tend to be more efficient since they are outsourced from experts. Telecom firms, therefore, act as the predominant factors in these transactions and, as such, expedite the transactions and absorb risks. The business expansion of telecom companies to include payment systems has given them a primary position within the financial sector. It has also led to more information on telecom industries as the number of parties interested in their business model escalated. Researchers are presiding over studies on the functions of telecom firms and making this knowledge available on the internet in academic literature and incorporating it with financial reviews, which is, in turn, prompting the further success of the entity.

Telecommunications companies are known for their exposure to third-party risks since they outsource their functions and operations. Third-party risks are not a specified type of risk. They involve various risks as long as they arise from the firm's operations with other parties and not directly from the internal operations. Telecommunications firms experience many other risks apart from third-party risks (Malhotra, 2015). They have, over time, found ways to manage these risks as part of their business strategies. Risk management is essential since the success of telecommunications companies is a vital reinforcement to any nation's economy.

Life proved the essence of the telecommunications sector to the economy during the Covid 19 pandemic as businesses lost their value and governments inhibited movement.

Telecommunications firms gained more business since communication became more rampant due to changes like laborers working from home. The risk management challenges they experienced became more evident due to the difficulty they experienced while outsourcing operations. The telecommunications business is complex; hence, risk management has always been difficult. Some risks they experience include supply risk, cyber risk, regulation risk, talent risk, financial risk, and investment risk.

Telecommunications firms have to manage all these risks thoroughly to guarantee their productivity and profitability. The first step towards addressing these risks that telecommunications firms always take is getting a holistic approach to the risk. This guides them to detail risks in every department and operational function to find ways to squash them. A holistic risk framework simplifies the complexity of the troubles encountered by telecommunications firms by bringing them all together on one page. It combines the tools, processes, automated risk controls, and technological risk management systems to make the process seamless.

The first step to risk control is identifying all the risks and their likelihood of occurrence. Establishing the context of the event is also a significant factor in the identification stage. Different occurrence contexts result in differing solutions. Risk analysis follows and measures the extent of risk to categorise it into tolerable, unacceptable, or acceptable. Unacceptable risks are prioritised, while acceptable risks are considered insignificant. Firms then conduct risk evaluations to compare the risk in question to their strategies. Lastly, they risk treatment by applying the techniques developed.

1.5 Problem Statement

The telecommunications sector in Algeria grapples with a myriad of risk challenges, necessitating a strategic shift towards the adoption of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM). The effectiveness of existing ERM frameworks within the industry has emerged as a critical concern, prompting an in-depth exploration into the specific critical success factors influencing the adoption of ERM practices. At the heart of this challenge is the essential need to identify and comprehend the unique obstacles faced by the Algerian telecommunications industry. Given the sector's dynamic and ever-evolving nature, coupled with the intricate integration of various fields, there arises a compelling demand for specialized risk management techniques. This study is dedicated to unravelling the critical success factors shaping ERM adoption in the Algerian telecom sector, recognizing and addressing the industry's distinct characteristics. Emphasizing the development of a tailored ERM framework, the research aims to provide a nuanced and effective approach to mitigate the diverse challenges inherent in the telecommunications landscape of Algeria.

The problem emerges from the inherent complexity of telecommunications operations, where strategic and operational risks intersect with factors such as regulatory compliance, pricing differences, technological confluence, and innovation. In Algeria, these challenges are exacerbated by environmental factors like political, economic, and legislative conditions, along with media restrictions and inadequate infrastructure. The telecommunications sector in Algeria further grapples with media restrictions and inadequate infrastructure, intensifying the obstacles faced by industry players. This study emphasizes the pressing need for thorough research into the specific risk management practices tailored to the Algerian telecommunications landscape. Despite a notable surge in Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) adoption since the early 21st century, a critical gap persists in understanding and effectively implementing risk adoption frameworks within this dynamic industry. The research aims to address this gap, shedding light on the nuanced challenges and critical success factors influencing ERM adoption in the Algerian

telecommunications sector. By doing so, the study seeks to provide valuable insights for industry stakeholders, policymakers, and practitioners, fostering a more resilient and adaptive telecommunications environment in Algeria capable of navigating multifaceted risks.

This research underscores the imperative to address the existing gap in comprehending the distinctive challenges surrounding Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) adoption within the Algerian telecommunications sector. The sector, marked by significant growth in the 21st century, necessitates a nuanced and industry-specific approach to effective risk management. The proposed study aims to provide valuable insights into the formulation of ERM frameworks tailored to the intricate landscape of the Algerian telecommunications industry. Through an exploration of critical success factors and challenges, the research seeks to empower industry practitioners, policymakers, and stakeholders with informed perspectives for adopting proactive risk management strategies. By doing so, the study aspires to facilitate the development of a more resilient and adaptive telecommunications sector in Algeria, equipped to navigate the diverse risks inherent in its operational environment. Ultimately, the research endeavors to contribute to the enhancement of risk management practices, ensuring the industry's sustained growth and resilience in the face of evolving and multifaceted challenges.

1.6 Aim of The Research

The principal aim of this thesis is to investigate the unique factors influencing ERM adoption in the Algerian telecommunications industry and subsequently develop a tailored ERM framework that aligns with the industry's specific needs.

1.7 Research Objectives

The primary objectives of this research include:

1. Investigating the factors that prompted Algerian telecommunication firms to adopt an ERM program.
2. Evaluating the effectiveness of the existing ERM frameworks within the Algerian telecommunications industry.
3. Exploring the challenges hindering the adoption of ERM programs among Algerian telecommunication firms.
4. Developing an adoption framework tailored to the telecommunication industry to ensure sustainable efficiency.

The objectives of this study are structured to facilitate a comprehensive investigation into the critical aspects of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) adoption within the Algerian telecommunications industry. Objective 1 entails examining the factors that prompted Algerian telecommunication firms to adopt an ERM program. This will be accomplished through a multi-faceted approach involving both a thorough review of relevant literature and interviews with key decision-makers within the industry.

Objective 2 aims to evaluate the effectiveness of existing ERM frameworks by conducting a detailed analysis of current practices, supplemented by insights gleaned from industry experts and stakeholders through interviews and surveys. Objective 3 seeks to explore the challenges hindering the adoption of ERM programs among Algerian telecommunication firms, leveraging a combination of qualitative methods such as interviews, focus groups, and quantitative analysis to identify and understand the underlying issues.

Regarding the development of a new ERM framework (Objective 4), the process will be informed by the findings and recommendations derived from the preceding objectives. Insights gathered from literature reviews, interviews with industry experts, and an analysis of current practices will serve as foundational elements for crafting a tailored framework specifically designed to address the unique risk landscape of the Algerian telecommunications sector. The development process will involve synthesizing research findings, best practices, and expert recommendations to formulate a robust and adaptable ERM framework that aligns with the industry's needs and objectives. Additionally, collaboration with industry stakeholders and engagement with academic literature on ERM frameworks will contribute to the refinement and validation of the proposed framework, ensuring its relevance and applicability within the Algerian telecommunications context.

1.8 Research Questions

1. What are the specific factors that triggered the adoption of an ERM program among Algerian telecommunication businesses?
2. How effective are the current ERM frameworks within the Algerian telecommunications industry?
3. What challenges do Algerian telecommunication firms face in the effective adoption of ERM programs?
4. How can a targeted ERM framework be adopted for telecommunications organizations in Algeria to ensure sustainable efficiency?

1.9 Research Methodology

This thesis employs a qualitative case study research method with a focus on semi-structured interviews, aligning with the methodological framework derived from Saunders's approach. The chosen qualitative research methodology is inherently literary, emphasizing the collection of non-numerical data to gain a nuanced understanding of the subject matter. In adherence to the philosophy, approach, and strategy outlined by Saunders, this research undertakes a case study approach to delve into the intricate domain of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) adoption within the Algerian telecommunications sector.

The research strategy involves engaging risk management experts within the telecommunications industry through semi-structured interviews. These interviews utilize open-ended questions to elicit comprehensive responses, allowing for an in-depth analysis of the participants' insights.

Following Saunders's approach, this research aligns with a deductive logic, where the semi-structured interviews serve as a method to gather rich qualitative data. The time horizon is strategically designed to capture current perspectives on ERM adoption, ensuring relevance and applicability to the dynamic risk landscape of the Algerian telecommunications industry. The basic techniques employed include systematic data collection through interviews, subsequent review and analysis of responses, enabling the dissection of the complexities surrounding ERM adoption in the sector into more digestible components. This research methodology, grounded in Saunders's approach, is poised to offer a comprehensive exploration of the critical success factors and challenges influencing ERM adoption within the specific context of the Algerian telecommunications industry. This research significantly contributes to the body of knowledge within the professional telecommunications domain by enhancing our understanding of the pivotal role played by Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) in telecom firms and its associated benefits. The study comprehensively explores the concepts of ERM, the key factors influencing its application, and the strategic and managerial fabric of telecommunications firms. It delves into the diverse risks faced by these firms, the varied strategies employed for risk mitigation, and the challenges and benefits arising from the implementation of these strategies. This systematic examination provides valuable insights into the nuanced landscape of risk management in the telecommunications sector, offering a clear and detailed exposition of concepts and techniques.

Furthermore, the research extends its contribution to academic literature by pioneering the development of a telecommunications industry-specific ERM framework, accompanied by a thorough elucidation of its components and anticipated benefits. This initiative is particularly crucial as the telecommunications industry lacks a dedicated ERM framework, and the currently employed multidisciplinary frameworks have proven inadequate for effective risk management.

The new framework proposed in this study is substantiated by empirical evidence drawn from credible sources, highlighting the limitations of existing frameworks and underscoring the imperative for a tailored approach in the telecommunications sector. Beyond the specific context of the Algerian telecommunications industry, the study broadens its contribution by examining a geographical context that has received limited research attention. By adding to the scant data on the Algerian telecommunications sector, the thesis becomes a valuable resource for knowledge seekers from the region. The methodology section further bolsters the study's credibility by collecting additional evidence from the area, enhancing the reliability and validity of the data. This comprehensive research effort not only enriches the body of knowledge pertaining to the telecom industry in Algeria but also lays the groundwork for potential insights and applications in similar sectors and geographical contexts worldwide, thereby extending the broader impact of this research contribution.

1.10 Study Significance

The significance of this study lies in its potential to offer substantial contributions to both academia and the practical landscape of the Algerian telecommunications industry. In an academic context, the research provides a unique exploration into the critical success factors influencing the adoption of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) within a specific industry, shedding light on the complexities and nuances of risk management in the Algerian telecommunications sector. By delving into these intricacies, the study enriches the existing body of knowledge on ERM practices, contributing valuable insights that can inform future research endeavours, academic discourse, and curriculum development in the realm of risk management. On a practical level, the study's findings hold significant implications for industry practitioners, policymakers, and stakeholders in the Algerian telecommunications sector. By identifying the specific challenges and success factors influencing ERM adoption, the research equips these stakeholders with actionable insights to enhance risk management practices. The proposed industry-specific ERM framework has the potential to serve as a practical guide for telecommunications firms in Algeria, fostering resilience and adaptability in the face of the sector's dynamic risk landscape. Ultimately, the study's significance transcends theoretical exploration, offering tangible benefits for the enhancement of risk management strategies in the Algerian telecommunications industry, thereby contributing to its sustainable growth and stability.

1.11 Contribution to The Practice

The contribution to the practice refers to the benefits the thesis will have on the practice of enterprise risk management in the telecommunications industry in Algeria. This study will contribute by front lining an ERM culture of adopting sector-specific frameworks for various sectors to evade the existing frameworks' significant limitations. As listed in the literature review section, the framework's limitations point to a combination of generalized ERM frameworks limited in application. Furthermore, Algeria lacks a local framework that considers the external environment of the specific geographical area because they adopt international and foreign standards. Therefore, the detailed, clear ERM framework established in this thesis is a trailblazer for industries in Algeria to develop specialized industry-specific ERM frameworks to manage risks and increase their profitability.

The literature contributes to the practice by introducing ERM knowledge in Algeria. The information about enterprise risk management in Algeria is minimal. Very few Algerian companies adopt ERM into their daily activities. It is evident from the literature review section that effective risk management is directly proportional to a firm's increased profitability and competitive advantage. This literature will help companies arrive at these results by being a compass on enterprise risk management for individuals and enterprises looking to integrate risk management practices into their business. The study will contribute by being a starting point for learners, educators, business managers, and the government if they are looking to adopt national risk management legalities.

1.12 Thesis Structure

The thesis structure begins with a work cover page that contains the introduction, title, name of the student, professor's name, and other details. It is followed by an abstract that profiles the study summary, stating the study's aims, objectives, and purpose. It also includes an abbreviations page and a table of contents.

Chapter 1 is an introduction. First, it defines ERM, the risks associated with the telecom sector, the risk management strategies commonly used by telecom companies, and their success rates. Next, it explains the study's aims, objectives, and significance. Next, it describes the contributions the study is intended to have to society. Finally, it briefly introduces the research methodologies and gives the thesis structure.

Chapter 2 starts by reviewing the history and origin of ERM. It is the literature review section of the study and analyses data from numerous sources from internet publications to research books and telecom information journals. Next, it explains how traditional risk morphed into the ERM used by every corporation. Finally, it characterizes ERM frameworks, giving diagrams and relevant data to describe them.

Chapter 3 is the research methodology section. This is the most crucial part of research as it provides a framework for answering the research questions. It describes the research process, design, approach, strategy, and benefits and outcomes. It also notes the analysis methods, their advantages, and their challenges. Finally, it reports on the quality of the study.

Chapter 4 details the findings from the study. It gives the results from the qualitative analysis and discusses these results. It evaluates the highlighted literature on ERM and states the methodologies used for all research in the thesis. It contains the strategic frameworks, their advantages, and challenges. It analyses the work to point out any research gaps in the literature review and compiles

them to develop findings. Finally, it aligns the quantitative findings to the outcomes from the literature review and balances the results.

Chapter 5 reports the outcomes of the study also known as the results. Mostly, the results are the outcomes of the primary research conducted in the study. Also, the chapter covers the discussion which checks the alignment between the literature and findings of the research.

Chapter 6 The chapter summarises the study through the conclusion section. Also, it presents the recommendations covered in the research.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The literature review section evaluates various certified studies on the ERM adoption in the telecommunications sector topic and assesses them. The first sections of the data give the assessed definitions and background information on the topic. Various authors detail the ERM definitions, its history since the days of silo traditional risk management, the adoption and growth of ERM in the telecom sector, ERM alignment to various organisational factors, and ERM processes. The second part details the widely recognised and used ERM frameworks and standards amongst firms in the telecommunications sector, their evolutions, history, current use, and limitations. Finally, the second part details the proposed adoption ERM framework most suited for use in the telecommunications sector in Algeria and the features that forge its suitability.

The literature review of this thesis uses both theoretical and conceptual frameworks to assess various studies. A theoretical framework usually covers a particular research scope that discusses a cause to effect relationship. In contrast, a conceptual framework covers a limited area or perception of the research problems. This regard uses the theoretical framework to investigate and discuss the relationship between critical success factors and their role in ERM adoption in the telecommunications sector. To relate the various building blocks concepts, definitions, and outlines and link them to outcomes. It uses a conceptual framework to build theories on particular variables to contribute to the research topic. These variables include enterprise risk management frameworks, the introduction, and the ERM theories that build-up to the thesis outcome.

2.2 The Evolution of Enterprise Risk Management

Risk management was initially associated with insurable risks such as accidents, known as hazards and credit. During those times, corporations mainly focused on avoiding risk instead of proactive techniques that allow engagement. As the management of risks evolved, so did the COSO framework. Saleem, Zraqat, and Okour (2019) explore the nexus between internal audit quality (IAQ) and ERM, specifically within the framework outlined by the Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission (COSO). Focusing on the COSO framework, the study examines how the quality of internal audit functions influences the implementation and effectiveness of ERM. This research provides valuable insights into the interconnectedness of internal audit processes and broader ERM practices, illustrating the evolution of risk management approaches within the organizational governance structure. The following image shows the development.

Figure 2. 1 Evolution of Risk Management (IMA,2006)

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The table below compares some of the changes over the past years.

Traditional Risk Management	Enterprise Risk Management	
The risk was viewed as an individual hazard	Risk is viewed in the context of business strategy.	Arora (2021)
The risk was mainly identified and assessed.	A risk portfolio is developed.	Mechler (2019)
The risk was viewed as the responsibility of risk managers.	Risk is viewed as the responsibility of all stakeholders.	Driessen (2023)
There were risk limits.	There are risk strategies.	Yadav (2019)
The risks did not have owners	There were people with defined risk responsibilities	Ecklund (2019)

Table2 1 Traditional Risk Management versus ERM (Banham, 2004).

2.2.1 Pre-current Trends

Dickinson (2001) explains that business risk management evolved into the ERM concept in the mid-1990s. The need for ERM emerged because there had been many cases of large corporations making huge losses or running down their businesses due to unanticipated risks in the 1980s and 1990s. These tragedies made business managers wary of chances and were eager for ways to counter the problem. Businesses also started leaning towards the business model centered on providing value to shareholders, so they needed mechanisms to counter things that prevented them from attaining this value. When ERM emerged, corporations were welcoming to a solution for their

issues. The systematic nature of ERM immediately appealed to leaders and managers since traditional risk management was not as functional and practical. Around the same time, corporations began to incorporate it into their daily functions to maximize their profitability.

Despite Dickinson's 2001 detailed and exemplary information concerning the ERM as a code or law, it isn't easy to apply such laws and codes universally because ERM is an art and different framework depending on the business and societal environment. Such facts are further explained below by COSO 2018. Furthermore, Dickinson (2001) explains that "Enterprise risk is the extent to which the outcomes from the corporate strategy of a company may differ from those specified in its corporate objectives, or the extent to which they fail to meet these objectives (using a "downside risk" measure)..." "...The strategy selected to achieve these corporate objectives embodies a certain risk profile, which arises from the various factors that might impact the activities, processes, and resources chosen to implement the strategy" (Dickinson, 2001, p. 361).

Figure 2. 2 The measurement of Enterprise Risk retrieved from Dickinson, 2001,p.362

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Hoyt and Liebenberg (2015) define enterprise risk management as an integrated way of managing risks broadly. They explain that ERM is managing risks affecting the entire organisation collectively. Their study is structured in a way that first backtracked the origins of risk management, gave the history and details of traditional risk management, and explained how it morphed into the current enterprise risk management. They, however, capitalise on the value risk management accords firms. They start by analysing how each aspect of traditional silo risk management added value to firms to how the current ERM adds value to firms. In determining traditional risk management activities, they point out that traditional firms have been reducing their risks by reducing the financial costs and investing in equity markets with higher liquidity.

Furthermore, there have been three ways of risk management. First, “by reducing the firm’s tax liabilities (mainly by reducing the possibility of large, insurable losses that create tax-loss carry-forwards that can’t be used right away); secondly, by making use of insurance companies’ comparative advantage in negotiating and processing claims; and (3) by reinforcing management’s incentives to fund all positive-NPV projects—even in the face of large insurable losses, when corporate managers might otherwise be tempted to cut corners” (Hoyt and Liebenberg, 2015, p. 42). Hoyt and Liebenberg's (2015) study identifies ERM decisions in 117 publicly-traded insurance companies in the United States. However, their sample had only 8.5% of the firms using ERM leading to a low reflection percentage. They also used Tobin's Q to measure the value or profitability affected by ERM; however, Tobin’s Q might fail to give an accurate measure or weight; thus, leading to misunderstanding and affecting their results, which implied that was those that were profitable applied ERM correctly.

Wu *et al.* (2015) give a scientific viewpoint of ERM; they define risk management as identifying, evaluating, prioritisation resources to reduce, detect, and treat the aftermath of unexpected events. The authors give four ways to minimise and control these risks; either ignore, work safer, insure, or retain stakes. They note the endemic nature of ERM as it has to consider all possible risks that could impact an organisation. They mention the most urgent risks a business should prioritise in ERM: supply chain risk management, financial risks such as credit risks, operational risks, and disaster planning. They also explain the probability simulations that businesses can use to identify, evaluate and assess risks.

Furthermore, Wu *et al.* (2015) acknowledge that there are different models for ERM; they point to the social responsibility and risk, supply chain risk modelling, and Financial risk model. Furthermore, they point out that ERM evolves based on financial risk management but shifts to other models such as social responsibility and the supply chain risk management model. However, Wu *et al.* (2015) give strong epistemological background but fail to demonstrate their methodological experience. Therefore, the reality or ontological position they are pointing to is doubtful.

Dweczyk (2012) notes that enterprise risk management is a broad, ever-altering concept that keeps growing to include various and images. Over time, its landscape has grown to include many risks and risk treatment practices. He outlines ERM in alignment with the multiple transitions the idea has undergone over the years. Thus, he notes the various economic pitfalls over time and their impacts on ERM, specifically dwelling on the 2007-2009 global financial crisis. He defines enterprise risk management as collective risk treatment practices like the U.K. Financial Services Authority does. He details the risk that ERM manages as operational, technological, transactional, and business ethics risks. He also discusses the PESTEL sources of business risks.

In the analysis of John Fraser and Betty J. Simkins, John Wiley & Sons' book, Dweczyk (2013) affirm that the book point to ERM as a risk profiling and management strategy. Furthermore, Dweczyk (2013) that the book demonstrates that firms should adopt ERM as a culture of controlling risks. Chief Risk Officers (CROs) should ssumeembrace rds-aware culture and develop ERM frameworks. Additionally, ERM is an art, and there are tools and techniques which should be adopted and mastered. Method the framework section discusses tools, devices, and techniques methods below under the framework section.

Furthermore, Dwonczyk (2013) points out that the book demonstrates different types of risk, such as credit, market, operational and reputational, and legal risks, including how the management of such risks should be integrated and embedded. However, the book is too superficial, and it is not detailed. Furthermore, ERM is an art, and it depends on how it is applied and changes with time.

Enterprise Risk Management is relevant in many ways. According to Hoyt and Liebenberg (2015), the most significant benefit of ERM is that it ensures organisations deliver value to their stakeholders. They explain that uncertainty is a typical factor when doing business, and all trades are prone to it. Still, ERM enables firms to deal with as much uncertainty as possible and grow profitability and value. That uncertainty presents both risk and opportunity, potentially eroding or enhancing value, and ERM optimises the opportunities uncertainty gives while minimising the risks. He also argues that income and stock price volatility is reduced in this ERM process of optimising opportunities and minimising risks.

Similar to Hoyt and Liebenberg (2015), who analyse ERM in line with the profitability or value of firms, Grace *et al.* (2015) also discuss the importance of ERM to enterprises. The authors tell off the improved operational performance that ERM grants firms. Those firms that apply ERM strategies increase their value because managing risk help to predict the future and understand the imperfect market. Furthermore, similar to Hoyt and Liebenberg (2015), Grace *et al.* (2015) point out that traditionally, ERM had s silo technique, whereby risk is managed at the departmental level and at a time. Such a technique did not acknowledge that risks have an interrelationship nature and that ERM is a holistic approach to managing risks jointly.

In detail, Grace *et al.* (2015) affirm that; “With ERM, a firm examines risks jointly, assessing the interaction of each risk with the firm's portfolio of other important risks; in other words, ERM is commonly known as an integrated or portfolio approach to risk management...” “...Beyond improving internal decision making, ERM can also lead to more efficient capital allocation, better capital structure decisions, and better risk management decisions...” “...ERM can also advance risk awareness that improves operational and strategic decisions.”(Grace *et al.*, 2015, p. 290). They add that dealing with operational risks neutralises obstacles from daily operations. Hence improving performance and efficiency. They explain that taking advantage of effective ERM practices yields the most value for firms. The practices they focus on include an efficient economic capital model, a multi-functional risk managing committee, and cooperating with the board on ERM plans, progress, success, and failures. They emphasise the need to go for capital structure management and risk control practices that do not affect its market value— however, Grace *et al.*'s (2015) work uses past survey data, which creates validity questions. The history of ERM demonstrates that the framework of ERM advances, and using such past data leads to stagnation with old ERM thoughts.

Similar to Grace *et al.* (2015) and Hoyt and Liebenberg (2015), Abkowitz and Camp (2017) point out that ERM evolved from silo risk management to the current enterprise-wide risk management over time. Abkowitz and Camp (2017) trace risk management back to the 1940s and 1950s, explaining that firms started to assimilate forms of risk management into their decision- making processes. Insurable risks were the focus of the traditional (silo) risk management strategy. That companies were able to transfer certain types of risks to insurance companies. These risks included accidents and natural catastrophes. The covered scope of insurance increased over time, and they started to manage some commercial risks like credit risks. The existence of insurance markets challenged managers of risk identification and management possibilities if they widened their existing scope.

Abkowitz and Camp (2017) add that the evolution of traditional risk management led to the business risk management concept. Business risk management fixed the most obvious failures of silo risk management. It entailed dealing with business risks such as occupational hazards and natural catastrophes. The difference between it and the silo risk management was implementing strategies and systems. Otherwise, business risk management dealt with the same problems that silo dealt with. Like silo management, it failed to root out risks in the business portfolio, making the concept highly ineffective. Such failure is also eluded by Grace *et al.* (2015), who points out that traditional ERM did not integrate other risks and did not have a portfolio approach to managing risks. Such tradition was also limited because it did not encompass the preservation of shareholder value. Abkowitz and Camp (2017) affirm that business risk management was a better risk management system when compared with traditional risk management. Furthermore, the risk is inherent within a firm, it is at all levels within the organisation and in various facets, and therefore, ERM should be systemic and holistic.

As Hoyt and Liebenberg (2015) point out, Abkowitz and Camp (2017) demonstrate that a systemic and holistic approach characterises ERM. However, Abkowitz and Camp (2017) affirm that it is much easy to say than to do; thus, as much as the holistic and systemic effort is self-acclaimed, “ERM programs remain entrenched in compartmentalised parts of the organisation or ignore threats that are “outside of the box” of the operating environment to which management is accustomed.”(Abkowitz and Camp, 2017, p. 79). Therefore, the environment creates different opportunities for some risks to be unnoticed; there is a need for a comprehensive but flexible framework of ERM suitable to overcome different challenges (*ibid*).

The U.S. Committee of Sponsoring Organisations of the Tradeway Commission (COSO) reports in 2017 and 2018 defined risk connections in line with the integrated strategic performance. Such definition is a part of the COSO ERM Framework, which shall be evident below, but first, an understanding of the COSOs risk definition is vital. In its framework, COSO defines “risk as

“the possibility that events will occur and affect the achievement of strategy and business objectives (Coso, 2017, p. 9).” “This includes both negative effects (such as a reduction in revenue targets or damage to reputation) as well as positive impacts (that is, opportunities – such as an emerging market for new products or cost savings initiatives)” (Coso, 2018, p. 1). Furthermore, Coso (2017) earlier pointed out that the nature and management of risk is a science and an art, and every choice a firm makes has its objectives and is accompanied by risks. Therefore, with such thoughts, ERM is a science, but at the same time, it is an art of managing the risks, as mentioned earlier (Coso, 2018, 2017).

Furthermore, Coso (2017) points out that ERM's integrated framework was initiated by COSO in 2004 and has been accepted by a vast number of organisations to manage their risks. However, as time goes by, risks change and become complex, meaning ERM has been evolving, and COSO has been improving its reports and frameworks on ERM. Such evolution demands firms improve their ERM strategies to fit within the evolving business environment (Coso, 2017). The social, governance and environmental-related risks are essential when considering ERM. The global risk report pointed out the 2008 pandemics and societal threats, part of the world economic forums. In 2018, environmental and societal were among the top listed risks and were adopted quickly by the business community worldwide (Coso, 2018).

Fraser *et al.* (2021) point out that ERM is a strategy to adapt to changes and be prepared for the uncertain future in business. It is also about anticipating the survival and success of a firm in an uncertain business environment. In other words, the tuition of ERM is about Charles Darwin's theory of survival for the fittest. The organisation that applies ERM thinks of the future business environment and hardship, which can survive in such times. Therefore, one needs to identify the threat within the organisation and examine them, and anticipate future threats.

Additionally, Fraser *et al.* (2021) point to the COSO definition of ERM in their definition. They say that "The culture, capacity, and practice, integrated within strategy-setting and performance, that organisation rely on to manage risk in creating, preventing, and realising value." (Fraser *et al.*, 2021, p. 4). Therefore, they take a holistic approach to defining ERM. Such a holistic and systemic approach is also what Hoyt and Liebenberg (2015) and Abkowitz and Camp (2017) point out as the evolution of ERM. Furthermore, they say that the purpose of ERM is to find the ideal level of the risk and not minimise the risk. Such an approach helps in maximising opportunities.

As Hoyt and Liebenberg (2015), Grace *et al.* (2015), and Abkowitz and Camp (2017) point out that traditional ERM focus on silos, Fraser *et al.* (2021) affirms that in the past, ERM was managing risk in silos, having a narrow view with no integration of ERM across the departments. Therefore, ERM should address risks as an integrated, strategic, and systemic function within the organisation. Such strategy should be left to the high-level management team, and the employees at all company levels should see ERM as an integral part of their work and an ongoing duty.

Therefore, enterprise risk management identifies, examines, and treats organisational threats. The probability of a loss or an unexpected event and its intensity could block an organisation from attaining its goals and objectives. These unexpected losses and threats are known as risks. Effective risk management works to do away with these threats or reduce their impact to ensure a firm's goals. Risk management is an unending process since threats will always occur for as long as the firm is in business. Therefore, risk management aims to minimise threats to an organisation's success and improve business efficiency.

2.2.2 Current Trends in Enterprise Risk Management

Popchev *et al.* (2021) explain that currently, ERM practices are a norm for any entity in business. They attribute this normalisation of ERM incorporation to the shift in business culture to a culture that emphasises the need to provide value to shareholders. This cultural shift has caused

businesses and business leaders to adopt and practice ERM to increase their chances of delivering this value. Shareholder value is directly linked to profitability and success; hence it is always positioned with the business objectives. Other important reasons firms adopt enterprise risk management include; improving business solvency, performing their corporate social responsibility's role, and building sustainable business systems that continually increase value provision.

The most significant trend in the risk management culture of the last two decades is attributed to implementing risk management. The goal is now to add or preserve shareholders' value. Many studies discuss the beneficial relationship between ERM, shareholders' value, and competitive advantage. Lai (2010) discusses this relationship and its positive results to an enterprise. That ERM, when done as comprehensively as it should, aligns risks to the culture and internal workings of a company. They narrate that ERM creates value at both the micro and macro levels. It does so at the micro-level by reducing dire aftermaths of risks and at the macro level by long-term achievement and maintenance of competitive advantage.

The concepts under current ERM trends are discussed later, but they are briefly presented here because they are a significant part of ERM trends. Moreover, they are the foundation of this thesis. The 2020 global recession that resulted from movement cessation legislation to combat the spread of Covid 19 has lit a torch on the necessity of business risk management concerning all organisational aspects (Ghazieh et al., 2021). Such enterprise-wide risk management is Enterprise Risk Management (ERM). ERM has been a new concept since it emerged over the last decade.

ERM is implemented using standardised ERM frameworks as named and organised by various governmental organisations worldwide. COSO gives a definition of ERM and a COSO framework of ERM implementation. The body defines enterprise risk management as an

entrepreneurial strategy-setting process that is applied by an entity's management body to identify any upcoming occurrences that may positively or negatively impact the business as a whole and treat the aftermath of these events to ensure assurance to stakeholders on the achievement of the entity's goals.

According to the COSO approach, enterprise risk management centers on internal control. The approach details that internal management and enterprise risk management are complementary, and they both need the other to be affected and achieved. Since COSO developed their ERM framework, they have been upgrading such frameworks due to the changing business environment in the 21st century; thus, the model has some alterations from the initial COSO models (Bensaada et al., 2019). The significant distinction results from the attempt to make the model more inclusive of other entrepreneurial departments that aren't financed and auditing. The difference in the COSO model in comparison to other frameworks is that COSO's approach still acknowledges the broad scope that ERM covers (Saleem, 2019). Additionally, the COSO framework emphasises that integrating ERM processes with internal operations and management facilitate a company's ability to attain its strategic, operational, reporting, and compliance goal.

2.3 Key Contributions to the Academic Literature

2.1.1 Key Challenges to ERM

The literature on key challenges to Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) encompasses a diverse range of perspectives, examining empirical analyses, the role of government policy, and the alignment of cybersecurity management with ERM, offering insights into the multifaceted nature of challenges faced by organizations.

Al-Tayan's (2022) empirical analysis of ERM in Middle East countries provides a comprehensive examination of the challenges within the region. The dissertation sheds light on the specific contextual factors influencing ERM implementation in Middle East countries, offering empirical evidence to identify challenges unique to this geographical setting. By focusing on the Middle East, the research contributes to a nuanced understanding of regional challenges that may not be adequately addressed by generic ERM frameworks. Benmoussa, Ibrahim, and Augustie (2024) explore the moderating role of government policy in electronic government adoption among Algerian petroleum companies. While the primary focus is on electronic government adoption, the study indirectly touches upon the challenges associated with aligning organizational practices with government policies, including those related to risk management. Understanding the interplay between government policies and ERM is crucial, as regulatory frameworks can either facilitate or hinder effective risk management practices within specific industries.

Andronache's (2019) doctoral dissertation delves into aligning cybersecurity management with ERM in the financial industry. The research recognizes the evolving landscape of risks, particularly in the digital domain, and highlights the challenges organizations face in aligning cybersecurity measures with broader ERM strategies. This study addresses the contemporary challenge of managing cybersecurity risks within the overarching ERM framework, emphasizing the need for an integrated and cohesive approach to risk management.

ERM practice has been adopted worldwide by various organizations, community enterprises, and groups. Like any other business management function, risk management experiences difficulties during its planning and execution. Risk management is especially prone to challenges due to its nature of anticipation. Also, because it requires input from all departments in an organization for its implementation, risk management quickly experiences misalignment challenges (Hofmann *et al.*, 2018). Enterprises have to deal with the challenges to various risk framework's management to ensure effective risk aversion. The main challenges divide to four main categories as according to Lam (2003) namely (1) ERM integration, (2) Board risk governance and reporting, (3) culture change management and (4) feedback loops and risk and executive compensation. The following figure depicts the categorisation.

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Figure 2. 3Categorization of the ERM Adoption Challenges (Lam, 2003).

Just like the first critical success factor for ERM success is the commitment from the top management, the first threat to ERM success is the lack of commitment from top management. ERM solely relies on the decision-making of the business leadership to run and succeed, so it is directly impacted when these leaders make poor choices. Bad leaders, lack of commitment, inadequate resources, and time in the leader's hands are roadblocks to the ERM process (Farrel and Gallagher, 2015)

Inadequate communication or feedback loop and collaborative tension among the various ERM implementation process stakeholders. As mentioned in the above section on the CSFs that influence successful ERM, communication is critical. Risk management incorporates the efforts of stakeholders from various departments; hence there is a need for maximum cooperation for it to excel. Communal tension causes a lack of trust among staff mates. Poor communication leads to increased errors in the process; hence both act as a blockage to the ERM process. For instance, inadequate financial and human resources can be a significant challenge to ERM implementation.

The process encompasses many stages that require labour for implementation. The availability of human resources with the right skills and talents that complement ERM practices are essential for its operations and success (Callahan and Soileau, 2017). Earlier, when ERM was introduced into management, the significant challenge for its implementation was the lack of people specializing in the particular area. ERM has, over time, evolved to be a course studied in professional institutions and a career post in organizations. Finances to support ERM are vital hence the involvement of the finance department in ERM processes. They conduct cost-benefit analyses for the various programs for quantification and to help make choices.

An organization culture that does not support ERM practices will be a roadblock to enterprise risk management. Culture is a people's way of doing things. Firms need to create a culture that acknowledges the necessity for risk management and indulges in the eradication of threats faithfully (Chen et al., 2019). A firm with a corrupt culture will tend to fail in the ERM endeavor as they will focus on creating shortcuts to the process to steal funds etc. A firm with corporate political issues will have an unsupportive culture as groups will tend to destroy each other's work rather than support their projects for the firm's benefit. Therefore, unsupportive organisational culture is a significant challenge to implementing ERM.

Saeidi et al. (2020) say that empirical studies on how risk culture affects the effectiveness of ERM are still in their early stages and few, and that more research is needed to fill this gap.

Limited technological resources and talents/skills can impair the ERM process. The complexity of risk identification and quantification requires technological tools for the exercise. Lack of adequate access to these tools will impair the ERM process. The major blockage to this is the expensive costs of purchasing technological tools, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises. In addition, the tools can only be operated by well-using professionals with technological skills. So the company has to acquire this skilled labour. Risk management professionals who understand how to identify risks, read risk patterns and the assessment process are vital for ERM.

The indistinct specialisation of ERM roles and responsibilities confuses the process leading to failure. For example, unclear specialization could occur when professionals of a specific area are placed in other areas that are not of their field to work (Chernov, 2020). It could also result from an organisation failing to clearly outline the roles of every department and the responsibilities specific people in that department should handle. The latter leaves some roles in parts organisation undone what former causes poorly done work.

Human interference aspects combine any blockages to the process that people and human activities cause. People working in a firm are from diverse backgrounds and have varying perceptions and ways of doing things. Bumps in the process could be caused by personal mistakes made due to personal issues (Abu Kwaik et al., 2023). Workers failing to create time for their ERM work or lack commitment to the process could be challenging. Organisations have to offer rewards and other means to motivate their employees and enhance a culture of best practices.

Despite the great extent to which studies have been conducted on ERM, companies still experience difficulties quantifying the threats. Risks come in many forms and shapes; hence quantifying them to conduct a cost-benefit analysis and decide on the best means to control them is always a task. Over time, scientists and scholars have found many ways to quantify risks for financing and assessment purposes (Vlasov et al., 2019). Still, quantifying risks is a challenge because of the complicated nature of threats.

The challenge of numerous potential scenarios often occurs when risk managing. Anticipating events that have not yet occurred is complex, and there could arise a situation where one threat can occur in many ways. Numerous potential scenarios do not just cause quantification problems but also increase the costs of conducting ERM (Bensaada et al., 2019). It makes the work of the ERM department harder and forces companies to hire more workers for the process. On the other hand, ignoring some of the potential scenarios in the risk process increase threats to the company, so firms have to deal with all the scenarios either way.

In pointing out how ERM adds value, Hoyt, and Liebenberg (2015) point out that traditional silo methods led to inefficiencies with no coordination and understanding of departmental risk, which cuts across various departments. Such silo methods did not combine or integrate risk into one framework, which enabled the decision-making to link departmental risks, but it only reduced the low cost of ERM. Equally, Fraser and Simkins (2016) point out that ERM has its roots in the 1990s and has since shaped governance and management in the corporate world. However, ERM is still a challenge to many firms today. Furthermore, the history of risk management has a narrow view and was handled separately. For example, the focus on risk was on potential events that were to be insured, but in 1990, a focus on all the risks emerged instead of just specific, which are easy to quantify.

2.3.2 ERM configuration and perceived effectiveness

ERM is different from traditional risk management in a big way because it takes an integrated approach. Organisations have many design options to choose from when setting up an ERM program. Semi-regulatory bodies have made several frameworks and standards that offer implementation guidelines and designs for an ERM program. There are a lot of frameworks and standards for implementation, which will be talked about later in this chapter. The COSO ERM framework (2004, 2011, 2013, and 2016) is the most well-known and is used by many different types of organisations. Importantly, though, the COSO ERM framework gives organisations only key principles and ideas. This means that the organisation that adopts it is responsible for figuring out how to put them into practice. The COSO 2004 ERM framework gives organisations information about the following parts that make up an ERM. They include internal environment, Setting goals, Identifying events, Assessing risks, Dealing with risks; • Controlling activities; • Information and Communication Monitoring (COSO, 2004)

The COSO ERM framework also gives organisations examples of how to use ERM techniques in

real life. However, it also says that these examples are just for guidance and may not be the best way to do things in practice, depending on the organisation.

Scholars like Collier *et al.* (2007) and Paape and Spekle (2012) say that there isn't much evidence about how to make the best ERM program, and that professionals don't yet know how to make the best ERM. So far, there is no research in sight that shows or gives specific design parameters through which organisations that use ERM have been successful. Also, as far as we know, there are no empirical studies that show how specific ERM practices contributed to the success of ERM (Paape and Spekle, 2012). So, it's clear that there aren't many real-world studies that show how effective ERM programs and the ERM frameworks that are currently available are. Others, like Samad-Khan (2005), have said that implementing ERM requires a big investment of time, money, and people, as well as a big change in the organisation's culture, without a good return on those investments.

Authors like Power (2007, 2009) found that the way ERM is used in organisations varies greatly, both in terms of how much it is used and how it is used, and because organisational culture is so important. Bruno-Britz (2009) says that in order for an ERM to work well, organisations should "look beyond technology to create a culture of risk management throughout the organisation" (Davila, Epstein, and Manzoni, 2012, p.281-282).

Standards and Poor (2008) says that a risk culture should be a part of the whole organisation and the way its employees think. It is therefore clear that the trend toward using an ERM program is still growing, and that very few people have looked into how ERM works in real life so far (Arena *et al.*, 2010). This seems to fit with what Power (2009) said earlier in his study of how well ERM works.

2.3.3 Risk Response Strategies

Risk response strategies are actions to take in handling organisational risks (COSO, 2004). The traditional risk management processes focused on risks that could be transferred, especially insurable ones, to shift the organisation's burden. The COSO ERM framework recommends that the risks be handled through avoidance, acceptance, reduction, acceptance, reduction, mitigation and transfer. The choice of the appropriate risk response strategy is determined by entity-specific factors such as nature of risk, cost-benefit analysis and risk appetite (Alawattagama, 2018). Some risks offer benefits to the organisation if they are well managed, and thus, ERM frameworks increase the organization's risk appetite.

2.3.3.1 Risk response by COSO and ISO ERM frameworks

Risk response is an important part of the risk management process that is emphasised by all ERM frameworks and standards, even though this step is called something different in each framework. In the risk management process suggested by ISO 31000, the risk assessment includes identifying, analysing, and evaluating risks. This is followed by the "risk treatment" stage (Dafikpaku, 2011). The COSO ERM framework (2004) has a three-dimensional process, with organisational objectives on one dimension and organisational levels on the other. On the third dimension, there are eight sequential parts of the ERM process, as shown in figure 2. As written, "risk response" is one of the eight parts of the framework. It comes after "event identification" and "risk assessment" and before "control activities." According to the framework, each business unit and each of the four organisational goals (strategic, operational, reporting, and compliance) must come up with a "risk response" (Deloitte, 2014).

2.3.3.2 Value Creation and the Competitive Advantage via ERM

Several researchers have come to the same conclusion: when ERM is adopted and used, it creates value and gives a business a competitive edge. The literature review shows that telecommunications companies should review and improve their risk management practices by integrating risk across all strategic dimensions. They should also adapt to a business environment that is always changing in order to keep growing and making money (Manab *et al*, 2010; Manab and Ghazali, 2013).

Shimpi (2005, 2009) looked into the link between risk management and shareholders' value. The author agrees that there needs to be an integrated risk management framework that looks at the most important risks. With this process, companies will be able to maximise the value for their shareholders (Kieth, 2014).

In a similar way, Nocco and Stulz (2006) have looked into the relationship between ERM, competitive advantage, and shareholder value. In order for organisations to get the most out of this interaction, they should look at risks from a more global perspective and include uncertainty as a part of the integrated risk framework. Also, Nocco and Stulz (2006) say that ERM adds value because it helps organisations quantify and optimise risks, which lets them choose the best strategy, aligns risks with the organisation's culture, and makes sure that internal decisions are in line with that culture. Nocco and Stulz (2006) also say that when ERM is used well, it helps organisations gain a competitive advantage and creates value at both the micro and macro levels. At the micro level, integrating ERM into the culture of the organisation requires the full involvement and commitment of top management. This is also true at all other levels of the organisation. Top management is responsible for putting in place a risk management framework that doesn't try to get rid of or reduce risks, but rather limits how likely they are to happen (Keith, 2014)

ERM focuses on comprehensive risks and helps the organisation capitalise on risky events, allowing business resilience such as survival through loss. ERM frameworks coordination of risk management processes enables businesses to improve capital efficiency and focus on high-profile strategic planning and high-level regulatory framework, leading to enhanced brand reputation (Onu and Mbohwa, 2019). ERM frameworks have tools that effectively identify, assess, evaluate and respond to risks that prevent the achievement of strategic goals. Tools like Key Risk Indicators (KRI) help provide early warnings on potential risks, thus allowing for early risk response. KRIs monitor natural catastrophes and match assets to liabilities to identify mismatches and allow strategic asset allocation to produce high stakeholder value.

Beasley, Pagach and Warr (2008b) and Gates, Nicolas and Walker (2009) are some of the authors that studied the value addition aspect of ERM. The authors stand for important forward steps aimed at assessing ERM value creation upon implementation. Specifically, Gates, Nicolas and Walker (2009) measured the positive effects of ERM in decision making and the enhanced decision making capabilities of organisations. The authors indicate that ERM's compelling nature enhances the organisation by turning the attention of the management towards the reduction of the risk culture of the organisation. Also, it ensures alignment amongst the business objectives and core strategies.

2.3.4 ERM and Culture

Several studies have been done to look into the link between corporate culture and the effectiveness of ERM. Enterprise risk management has changed from a type of risk management done by a specific department or group of specialised people to a process that helps organisations reach their strategic goals. This has made the need for a strong risk culture more clear (Althonayan *et al.*, 2013). Keith (2013) says that a bad organisational risk culture is often linked to the failure of a business. The author pointed out how important culture is for an ERM that works well and

helps achieve strategic goals. For a risk management process to work, it is seen as important to create a culture that accepts all aspects of risks and processes. Effective risk culture is one in which both the employees and the people in charge of the company have the same understanding of the risks. But it's not easy for an organisation to make and spread this kind of culture (Keith *et al.*, 2013). Researchers like Kimbrough and Compton (2009),

Mikes (2009a), Ashby *et al.* (2012), and Althonayan *et al.* (2012b) said that the topic of risk culture isn't studied enough, even though it is important to the risk management structure. Ashby *et al.* (2012) and other academics define risk culture as how ready and willing an organisation is to take risks, as seen by its top management. Practitioners, on the other hand, define it as the system of values and behaviors that run throughout an organisation and affect how risk is spread in that organisation and how employees make decisions (KPMG, 2011, Ashby *et al.*, 2012). Lam (2003) says that organisational culture and managing change are two of the most important problems a business can face. In the literature on ERM, the impact and role of organisational risk culture were often overlooked. However, a bad organisational culture can lead to a breakdown in the risk management approach, organisational decisions on identifying risks, and risk response strategies (Brooks, 2010). The key to a successful ERM adoption is building a strong and supportive culture. Without this, the shareholder's value could not be maximised (Chapman, 2007). The following figure shows the elements of culture and its relationship with risk management.

Figure 2. 4Elements of Culture and Risk Management

Source:(IRM, 2012).

The figure indicates that the main elements of culture management include personal pre-disposition to risk, personal ethics, behaviours, organisational and risk culture. Depending on the corporate and risk cultures, the stakeholders work together to identify, report and evaluate the threats (Linke and Florio, 2019). They are aware of the potential and existing risks and adjust their behaviour towards risk management. Therefore, the risk management processes align with the systems of values in the organisation, which are displayed by people concerning the organisation.

2.3.5 ERM in the context of the Telecommunication sector

The telecommunications industry dealt with risks using traditional methods that dealt with threats in separate areas. ERM frameworks were made because conventional risk management methods couldn't keep up with the changing nature of the risk environment (Onu and Mbohwa, 2019). The frameworks helped companies in the telecommunications industry deal with the risks that could have put them out of business. The frameworks became popular because they could manage risks across an entire organisation and predict new risks, which helped organisations plan. Rubino (2018) said that each organisation uses the risk management system that it thinks is the best. Notably, there hasn't been any research done on the situation of ERM adoption in Algeria, so this study hopes to contribute significantly to the field.

2.3.5.1 Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) Processes

Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) in the context of the Telecommunication Industry in Algeria involves a comprehensive process encompassing planning, identification, assessment, risk control, and monitoring. Aligned with international standards, the International Institute of Standards and Technology advocates three primary risk management courses of action: risk assessment, risk mitigation, and risk evaluation (Fauzi et al., 2021). Within the telecom sector, diverse risk handling methods are employed, including risk mitigation, avoidance, retention, and risk transfer, along with techniques such as shift and allocate, influence and transfer, portfolio diversification, and shape and mitigate.

The Enterprise-wide risk management guideline uses an eight-course step to managing risks. Gregson (2019) aims to establish the context, identify, analyse, evaluate, develop the risk mitigation strategy, review the mitigation strategy, quantify the risks, and communicate the process. This is the risk management model that the International Organisation for Standardization prescribes. They further divide the eight sequence steps into five undertakings: risk assessment, risk control, communication, monitoring, and controlling risk affairs (Hidayah et al., 2022). The risk model prescribed by the International Organisation for Standardization is the study's model. "Establishing the context" entails the firm defining the variables they will use to determine the scope of risk practice or the risk criteria. Internal context refers to factors that cause threats from within the organisation, while external factors are those threats instigated by environmental factors. The risk management context is the objectives, techniques, and scope of the firm's activities that form the basis for the risk management application and the advanced risk evaluation criteria (Muazu, 2021). They find out the noteworthiness of the risk and classify them into the three risk classifications; tolerable, acceptable, and unacceptable.

Carroll (2016) discusses risk identification features and purpose summarizing it as the process of attempting to discover potential business threats. They note that risk identification is made by analysing all the organisation's activities and finding potential threats from internal and external business environments. They also outline some ways of risk identification, such as planning for gathering data, running a business SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threat) analysis, running interviews, using historical data, brainstorming, using the Delphi technique, and using the Expected Monetary Value analysis and checklist analysis. They complete their assessment by noting that there are both qualitative and quantitative risk identification techniques that firms choose from based on their choice of ERM framework.

The risk analysis or assessment process necessitates evaluating the risk aftermath and recommending risk-reduction measures or ways to control them. Risk assessment involves checking the likelihood of occurrence and severity of threats and possible solutions to them. The severity of the threats is estimated against quality, time, resource, and benefit to decide on possible solutions (Hardy et al., 2022). Therefore, this risk management action equates the threat prospects against their ramifications to decide their urgency and means to combat them.

The risk evaluation stage determines the significance of the risk. It involves using qualitative and quantitative means to establish a connection between the risks and their benefits. It narrows down the scope of the analyzed risks by finding out where and how they will or might impact a firm (Abd Hamid et al., 2019). The stakes are classified, and a priority is given to the risks likely to cause more harm. The risks are classified into acceptable, tolerable, and unacceptable risks. This division states their gravity and priority in dealing with the various threats.

Developing a risk mitigation strategy is the part of the planning process where firms develop the methods, they will use to counter risk problems. It also includes measures to deal with any issues that arise from the chosen counter-strategy. The risk mitigation team can employ a couple of solutions to the threats passed to them (Quinn et al., 2022). Their employed means depend on the effect of the risk on costs, schedule, and business performance. For example, they can avoid the risks, accept them, control them or transfer their impact to third parties.

Reviewing the risk mitigation strategy is an expected step for the mitigation team after making their choices and agreeing on the means they intend to use. It is greatly based on monitoring techniques to watch for any changing impacts on the risks against costs, time, and benefits (Hidayah et al., 2022). It is a step to ensure their theoretical decisions are working in practice. While monitoring, decisions on whether to maintain the used strategies or update them are made. The reviews can be consistent or done on a chosen schedule. Therefore, the team in this stage analyses the conditions of the risk and their management strategies, incoming risks, set-offs that alert them on the occurrence of the expected risks and validate their mechanisms. They alert top management on risk changes and revise risk techniques when necessary.

Quantifying the risks is an evaluation process that sets the risks management strategies' costs against the economic benefits of their management. The data-producing stage comes up with costs for risk threats versus management costs. The quantification is done in period, human resources, and expenses (Zandi et al., 2020). The technique most commonly used in this stage is statistical methods. It manages the values of the entire process and is, therefore, a vital process since it can be an addition or deduction to the business's profitability. Communicating the strategy is the final step in this enterprise-wide risk management strategy. The stage involves creating working communication systems to ensure the success of the process. Communication is so important as the business progress depends on the flow of information (Dandage et al., 2021). The teams working on the various risk management strategies need to discuss and develop solutions to threats. It keeps the units in contact with other departments to create solutions that align with the business's target costs and objectives. Finally, the top management must contact the risk teams to guide them. Communication is, therefore, central to the success of this process.

2.3.5.2 CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS

Literature reviews of various academic contents give synonymous definitions of critical success factors. The CSF concept emerged as organisational trading spread during the late eighteenth century. Boynton and Zmud (1984) describe essential success factor abstraction as the crucial elements that must be aligned for a business to excel in its operations and functionalities. They tell that distinct business entities have unlike critical success factors based on their business model (Vafadarnikjoo et al., 2023). The above is why analysts need analysts whose principal role is to assess firms and identify these factors.

Leidecker and Bruno (1984) describe critical success factors as the investment into business environmental analysis, resource analysis, competition analysis, strategy estimation, and their returns on investment that equal the success factor. It emphasises the most crucial assets that give the most valuable returns for an enterprise. The authors discuss how to identify the evaluability of the business investments through company assessment and the PIMS results methods. They note that these results give the success of the factors hence determining the variables to consider as

CSFs. They also note that CSFs vary among businesses based on their products, services, business, and leadership models.

Therefore, critical success factors, also known as key result areas, refer to the business aspects that contribute the most to the business's success. They are the functions that enterprises are most likely to benefit from if they focus on them. For example, some potential CSFs in ERM could be strategic management approach, risk management framework, the complexity or precision of the firm's goals and objectives, technological advancement, the size of their ERM budget, and information technology quality (Huang, 2023). Other factors could be the commitment of the top management, the extent of the uncontrollable external environmental factors, the essentiality of their risk monitoring software, and access to technological talents skills.

Jenster (1987) describes critical success factors strategies as the plans of actions firms take that concern the enactment of the most beneficial business aspects to maximize profitability and give shareholders maximum value. They explain that critical success factors are high target goals that a company aims to attain, so the firm needs a befitting strategy to accomplish these aims. For example, the strategy should aim to increase market share, increase market revenue, achieve services and products excellence and align incentives versus rewards for the firm's stakeholders (Abd Hamid et al., 2019). They also explain that vital goal-setting is how businesses gain a competitive advantage and add meaningful value to the enterprise.

Therefore, a critical success strategy is the plan of action a firm intends to enact to achieve its goals and objectives. A firm's strategy impacts its business success and competitive advantage in a sector. Techniques employed by firms vary depending on the various departments because strategies are tailored to particular stated functions. Businesses primarily use three strategies; differentiated strategy, a cost strategy, and focusing on a niche strategy. Porter, the economist,

simplified these strategies as differentiation, cost leadership, and market segmentation strategies. Differentiated strategy is a technique focused on setting up unique features to attain a competitive advantage (Fraser et al., 2021). Cost strategy is a management technique centered on funds management, acquiring, and pricing, while market segmentation strategy is focused on compiling costs management and differentiation depending on the target market.

The superiority of a firm's strategy determines its competitive advantage. Superior strategies are calculated by the scarcity of the strategy, the talents and skills invested into their implementation, and the technological power of the firm. Scarce strategies tend to be more expensive to align with and require more workforce (Etges et al., 2019). The inability of competitors to acquire the same strategy can give a business a market advantage. Talents and skills are essential in strategy management. Firms invest in the best talents and skills because they greatly influence strategic success and play a massive role in their strategy's accomplishments.

2.3.6 Overview of the Algerian telecom industry

The Algerian telecommunications sector is undergoing a significant transformation fuelled by the adoption of advanced technologies in internet and network coverage. Government interventions are actively facilitating this shift, with a particular focus on enabling network upgrades to 5G. At the forefront of this evolving landscape are four major telecommunication players: Algeria Télécom (Mobile), Verizon Communications, Deutsche Telekom, and China Mobile. These industry giants, along with other key players such as Swan Informatique, Groupe Telecom Algerie, Optimum Telecom Algérie (Djezzy), ATM Mobilis, Ooredoo Algeria, Smart Link Communication, and Icosnet, contribute to the sector's growth and have received additional spectrum from regulatory authorities to address service quality issues (Linke and Florio, 2019).

In addition to established metrics like real connections, service revenue, mobile and online traffic, and market share, these telecom firms play a crucial role in shaping the industry landscape. Despite the lack of specific figures in the available literature, these metrics serve as key indicators of the sector's performance (Barafort et al., 2019). The regulatory framework governing the Algerian telecommunications landscape is overseen by two authorities: the Algeria Regulatory Authority of Post and Electronic Communications (ARAPEC) and the Regulatory Authority of Post and Telecommunications (ARPT). While ARAPEC focuses on regulating the broader telecommunications sector, ARPT ensures compliance in the post, broadcasting, and telecommunication sectors. Within this dynamic industry, some players have embraced recommended Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) frameworks. However, a noteworthy observation is that the sector as a whole is yet to fully embrace robust ERM frameworks, with certain firms still relying on traditional risk management approaches. This aspect presents an interesting area for exploration, as understanding the current state of ERM adoption in the Algerian telecom industry becomes crucial for proposing tailored frameworks and strategies in the subsequent phases of the research (Antonionia et al., 2019). While academic literature specific to the Algerian context might be limited, credible reports and industry analyses will serve as valuable sources to enrich this section and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the telecom landscape in Algeria.

2.3.6.1 Critical Success Factors Impacting the Adoption and Growth of ERM

Enterprise risk management strategies are created in conjunction with the business objectives because the goal for risk management has to be aligned to business goals. Therefore, the risk management team has to work together with other departments to ensure an alignment with objectives and missions (Saeidi et al., 2019). Firms usually create long-term and short-term objectives aligned with their mission and vision statements and create organisational systems around them. Objectives are more particular than missions as they outline singular paths and goals. The organisation's risk culture is a significant factor that impacts the development of risk management strategies. An organisation's culture refers to the firm's stakeholders' customs, ideas, and social interaction. Corporate culture impacts employees' decision-making processes, hence determining the techniques, they employ in their problem-solving. The top management is in charge of setting the organisation's culture. If they are serious about eradicating risks, the other employees will do a great job (Kumar, 2021a; b). Good risk culture can be driven through good corporate governance, performance management systems, regular management reporting, and good investor relationships.

Internal and external environmental factors affect the achievement of risk management aims and objectives. Internal and external factors that impact the development of risk management strategies include organisational culture and strategy, communication culture, information technology access, commitment to achieving goals, talents, and training. Commitment to achieving the goals, especially from the top management, is the first critical success factor that enables the success of risk management strategies. It propels the entire organisation's success as they control and have the final stamp on decisions (Roeschmann, 2014). They make decisions on managing risk and authorizing the firm's processes.

Excellent and effective communication is highly vital for a functional organisation. Communication serves as the foundation for good planning and execution of strategies. Departments are teams and maximize potential through teamwork. Communication helps the risk management team of people from diverse backgrounds with different mindsets to align and agree.

It enables the passage of messages so other parties can learn, share ideas and receive guidance (Shad et al., 2019). This enhances trust among employees, top management, and employees, which is the basis for a good working relationship. It helps in managing the risk implementation process to ensure efficiency. It also sets in motion attitude changes and great socialization in the business.

Information technology and technology access and quality are significant factors that build and sustain the risk management department. In the telecommunications sector, technology quality determines the extent of business success. Firms need to have plans for the purchase and maintenance of technological tools. Their talents, skills, and innovations go hand in hand with technology. One would be unable to effectively use good technology for results without the skills and talents. The risk management frameworks implemented by firms depend on information and technology for use (Hubbard, 2020). It allows access to a broad range of data. Data is essential for businesses to draw predictions, have comparison standards, and research running businesses. Therefore, information technology is a critical success factor for ERM adoption and development in any corporation.

Businesses have to make sure they create functional systems continuously to guarantee efficient risk management. Some things companies can do to ensure this include maintaining a certain level of risk management commitment, especially among the top management, as they set the tone for the business and training their staff fittingly on the firm's risk culture, risk awareness, and their countering norms (Sutton, 2006) and mounting distinct objectives and regulations relating to risk aversion and setting aside sufficient resources (funds, human labor and time) as a risk management investment and setting working implementations systems to do risk reviews and survey risk management.

The above factors are the critical success factors businesses must instigate to succeed in risk management. They are the mechanisms enrolled to attain the set risk management objectives. Although many factors impact the success of ERM strategies, the research focused on the critical ones that are most likely to be employed by every corporation (de Araújo Lima et al., 2020). Therefore, some essential factors of success continuously showed up during the literature review. The literature based the different elements on the organisational designs firms chose to implement in the risk environment using embedded applications to manage risk decisions better.

2.4 Review of relevant theories for the study

This section of the research paper will look at most relevant theories to the research problem and the development of the proposed ERM adoption framework; more specifically, this section will evaluate the contingency theory, organisational theory, and systems theory.

Mcshane (2018) defines the theories of enterprise risk management as the fragmented disciplinary vantage points that are foundational in the research of ERM aspects. He explains some theories that birthed the ERM concept and those that have been the foundation of their evolution. His focus is on the interdisciplinary nature of ERM, that is the foundational basis of its concepts and implementations. He states that ERM's interdisciplinary nature is evident in the multi-disciplinary approach of quantifying risks within the entire enterprise.

Another study by Gordon *et al.* (2009) on the theories of enterprise risk management describes enterprise risk management theories as to the coordinated and strategic holistic approach that gives an altogether viewpoint of risks in a firm. This study is an ERM journal that dwells on the contingency theory of ERM. The authors narrate that the ERM contingency theory discusses the impressions of resource planning, firm size, and decentralization on ERM models and the results of this integration. So, according to them, the ERM contingency model encompasses the above three factors, their impact on ERM practices, and means to maximize this influence.

Gordon et al.(2009) keep demystifying the contingency theory by explaining its characteristics and necessity in ERM. He narrates that the contingency theory is multi-faceted and applies to many management variables. It is founded on the interaction between leadership style and organisational structure for successful management. So that it emphasises the need for outstanding leadership, aligned managerial structure, and decision-making firm guidelines. That theory considers the environmental and internal factors that impact the leadership and management structure. The

authors discuss the environmental factors instigated by the political, economic, social, and natural environment where the business is set up. They also discuss the internal factors within the organisation that are likely to affect these ERM processes. Internal factors include the firm's size, technology, and human factors.

Lamptey and Singh (2018) explain contingency theory as the hypothesis that describes how the designs and success of organisational control systems depend on internal and external business variables such as technology, firm size, environment, strategies, and leadership design models and culture. The perfect incorporation of organisational designs and control systems with contextual variables determines the performance of enterprises. Lamptey et al. note that there are no standard organisational control systems that can be used for all organisations. That organisational control systems depend on the company's design, structure, and business model. They affirm Gordon's earlier contingency theory assessment agreed that a company's performance does not ensue from ERM but from how sound firms integrate ERM with organisational factors.

The above definitions and backgrounds of contingency theory all emphasise the necessity of organisational structure and leadership styles on ERM success. Hossein Nezhad Nedaei *et al.* (2015) dwell on the contingency theories leadership styles and their impact on ERM performance. They note that the contingency approach's leadership styles are task-oriented leadership and relationship-oriented leadership. The authors describe task-oriented leadership as the leadership model where the top leadership works by tasks specialisation. The top leadership hand specific tasks to various employees and conduct performance management to determine their success. It is a more individual system that brings out the potential of each employee. They argue that the leadership style works best in big organisations since it is harder for management to keep relations with every employee. The model also requires individual performance management to be done

using set-up systems to make tasks supervision easier for the management to follow up on. The second leadership style they discuss is relationship-oriented leadership. According to Hossein et al., relationship-oriented leadership emphasises that employees work as a team to attain set objectives. They inform that performance management in the relationship-oriented model is based on teams, so leaders have to manage relationships for the company's good. Contrary to task-oriented leadership, the authors note that medium-sized and smaller firms favor relationship-oriented leadership as relationships can be easily managed among fewer people.

Therefore, it is evident from all the above literature reviews that the contingent theory of enterprise risk management aligns with the contingent theory of leadership and management. It promotes leader-member relations, leader-position power, and ERM tasks structure. Leader-member relations explain how a firm's top management relates with the employees and the effect these relations have on the success of ERM. Leader-position power talks about the authority a leader is given that enables them to guide their employees on various projects. Finally, task structure discussions about the setting of the tasks, their specialisation to various individuals and departments, and their means of implementation.

The structural contingent theory is the label the context and structure fit for organisational success is summarised as. So, the structural contingent theory also discusses the connection between structure and contingencies and their impact on business success. According to the theory, when the structure of an organisation is a match with the context variables, the firm is more likely to be successful. These variables include the size of the business, diversification, and roles specificity. The size of a business dictates the management structure the firm opts for. Smaller firms will opt for fewer systems and a management type that reaches every aspect and all individuals in a firm. More prominent firms must create more prominent structures that can accommodate the

entire structure, opting for bureaucratic structures and hierarchies. Diversification is done according to the innovation goals of the firm and cost management.

Apart from the above authors' approach that insists that fit for ERM success is the continuous integration between ERM practices and other factors, Hossein Nezhad Nedaei *et al.* (2015) mention that alternative approaches give ideals of fit using varying variables. They call these alternative approaches the interaction, systems, and selection approaches. They explained the three interactions and gave their purposes, arguing their effectiveness compared to the former contingency standard. According to them, the interaction approach gives its perfect fit outcome due to the interaction between the organisational variables. It differs from the formerly discussed contingency approach because it does not consider the interaction a cause-effect relationship. The systems approach does not single out variables but considers the variables as interconnected systems. Its fit is arrived at after incorporating the interconnected variables and company structure. Finally, in the selection approach, a fit is arrived at if the organisational design compliments the conditions of the company.

Therefore, the contingent theory of enterprise risk management denotes that their risk leadership's alignment determines a manager's success in various ERM situations and practices. The leadership style guides the organisation's structure, which guides the choices of strategies a firm implements for various management practices. The theory denotes that the success of ERM is guided by the firm leaders' knowledge of their internal and external environment, risk structures, business models, relations with stakeholders, and other business variables.

2.4.1 The organisational theory

The organisational theory looks at how the organisation interacts with its internal and external environment, how those interactions affect the organisation's risk performance, and how environmental factors can be used to create value for stakeholders through risk management. Organisational risk frameworks and design are important for figuring out the structure of risks and the ability to deal with new ones (Alawattegama, 2018). The organisational theory says that all parts of an organisation must work together to examine environmental risks. The organisational theory supports collaboration between departments and functions across the whole business. The main problem with this theory is that it thinks that organisations have rigid structures that are hard to change. The systems theory of risk management, on the other hand, says that scientific systems need to be used in the risk management process. The system ideas are built into the risk process to find risks more easily and possible risks can be predicted (Grishunin & Suloeva, 2020). The outcome of the risk management process is seen as better because the systems allow organisations to create accurate performance and risk indicators that help them reach their strategic goals. Changes can be tracked well with these methods. The main problem with this theory is that each person may not be able to deal with issues in the same way in most situations.

2.4.2 Systems Theory

Systems theory is a framework that was devised to enable a holistic approach to investigate phenomena across a range of disciplines. The core idea, which dates back to Aristotle, is that the whole is more than the sum of its parts. In other words, a proper understanding of a system cannot be reached by studying its components in isolation from one another. Systems theory views

organisations as social systems made up of sub-units that must inter-relate in a harmonious (congruent) manner for the organisation to be effective (Johnson, Kast, & Rosenzweig, Reference Johnson, Kast and Rosenzweig1963; Churchman, 1968). (Johnson, Kast, & Rosenzweig, Reference Johnson, Kast and Rosenzweig1963; Churchman, 1968). The systems theory approach thus focuses on the complementarities among elements, their integration, and the outcomes resulting from their interactions. In the case of an open system such as the business enterprise, the theory also encompasses the system's interactions with its environment. Feedback loops enable adaptation to environmental changes. Systems are generally nested and networked, with sub-units being systems in their own right. A single firm, which can be analysed as a system, is part of a larger industrial/business ecosystem, and it can also be viewed as networked with other firms in its value chain. Within Many sets of activities within the firm as production and marketing. Each of be analysed as a system connected to other systems internally and externally. While a holistic view is systems theory's most obvious feature, a systems approach does not neglect the study of individual elements. Both levels must be understood. A business model, for example, involves a product or service, a pricing logic, a geography of distribution among others (Teece, 2017). These elements may or may not be chosen or developed separately from each other. But however they are brought into play, the elements of the model must be coherently aligned and linked to an astute strategic vision if they are to lead to profits (Markovsky et al., 2021). If an element doesn't fit properly, e.g., if productive capabilities are inadequate to reach the expected product quality and/or volume, then the model will not perform as desired. Dynamic capabilities can also be broken down into elements (micro foundations). Systems theory also recognizes the importance of feedback, which is analogous to learning in the business enterprise. A simple feedback loop involves information about external changes coming into the system, whose components adjust to the environment while keeping all of the interdependent internal elements in balance and line with existing plans.

Another concept in general systems theory that marks a shortcoming with respect to dynamic capabilities is equifinality, the idea that different systems can achieve an identical outcome with varying combinations of conditions and paths (Becvar et al., 2023). There is unquestionable truth in this; companies, for example, have adopted several different business models for making and selling smartphones. However, equifinality emphasises the substitutability of firms and their strategies, whereas the dynamic capabilities framework emphasises that heterogeneity is meaningful and supports competitive differentiation.

For practitioners, a key defect of systems theory is that it is not inherently prescriptive. The goal of firms is not just survival, but prosperity. An awareness that everything is inter-related is of limited use. Managers need to know which relationships are most critical at a particular juncture. Managers are only seen in systems theory as parts of the whole, not as purposive human elements capable of exercising their own will and design capabilities (Markovsky et al., 2021). The systems approach lacks a place for proactive entrepreneurial action, viewing the system as primarily seeking to remain aligned with the survival requirements of the mega-system in which it is embedded. This purely reactive stance suppresses the major thrust of strategic management.

2.5 Risk Management Frameworks

ERM frameworks are built and implemented to view risks positively and negatively to eliminate the risks of using them as an opportunity to increase the firm's value. Alhawari *et al.* (2012) define risk management frameworks as a standard risk management guideline that seeks to identify, analyse and treat risks with knowledge management. Mao (2009) reports that there are two primarily recognised and used ERM frameworks. The frameworks are COSO and ISO frameworks.

He gives the two frameworks and narrates the differences between them. He also notes that the two frameworks have also evolved since their inception to what they are now. He summarizes

the evolution noting that ISO 31000:2009 has evolved from a theory attempting to simplify risk standards to fit all types of risks and organisations to a principles-based risk that employs systems and not structures. He notes that the COSO framework, on the other hand, has evolved from an audit-based risk management framework to leadership-based risk management that outlines a structure that firms can abide by in their risk management planning and implementation.

Furthermore, Fox (2018) notes that the two widely used ERM frameworks, both ISO and COSO, have been updating their ERM over the past years; thus, the users ought to understand the scope of such changes because they affect the risk management of organisations. The two frameworks have a common factor: ERM evolves from departmentalised and different activities to a more integrated management competency. Furthermore, the two frameworks acknowledge that ERM is an essential part of daily decision making, and it is vital for the firm's mission, the improvement of performance, and profitability. Therefore, the two frameworks recognise that uncertainty and risk are essential to leaders because they help make informed choices when running the firm, develop strategies, and deliver according to its vision (Fox, 2018).

ERM frameworks project the firm's structure, goals, and culture; hence are different in each firm. Balakrishnan *et al.* (2019) note that these form the risk management philosophy – the attitudes towards risks that determine how it conducts risk management activities. They discuss how the type of enterprise risk management depends on their type of organisational design model. That Lam acknowledged as a pioneer of the ERM model, started by breaking down the traditional silo risk management. He was encouraged by the widespread corporate failures that had occurred during that time due to risks. Lam believed ERM should consider risks in all aspects of the organisation. So he studied how to conduct risk management in corporate governance, portfolio

management, technology, and information (Kumar, 2021a; b). As a result, he changed the perception of risk management and introduced the ERM concept.

In the early 2000s, governments worldwide started to adopt risk standards. The U.K. government formed the U.K. risk standards. Australia formed the Australia/New Zealand standards 4360 - risk management. The U.S. created the Committee of Sponsoring Organisations of the Treadway Commission (COSO). COSO 2004 was focused on setting strategic level objectives to deal with enterprise risk. It is based on ERM as a top management role because they can better discern organisational issues. In 2009, the International Organisation for Standardization (ISO) was formed (Malhotra, 2015). Governments formed these organisations to prevent firms from using ERM for financial fraud.

Another study by Dafikpaku illustrates the various factions of an enterprise risk management model and their implications. It also creates scenarios that a framework can work around, such as risk abortion or ignoring the risks if the cost-benefit analysis favours that decision. Dafikpaku *et al.* (2011) also clarify that COSO's most commonly used ERM framework is the Integrated Framework for Enterprise Risk Management (IFERM). The Global Audit Information Network of North America, in conjunction with the Institute of Intern Auditors, conducted this survey through global sampling enterprises all over the world and found the above results. The second most commonly used ERM framework is the ISO 31000 framework.

2.5.1 ISO 31000:2009 framework

Kumar (2021b) details that ISO 31000:2009 is the international organisation of Standardization ERM framework. He describes that it is based on principle and was established by the world's largest organisation for standards creation. It notes the principles businesses should

use for their ERM practices rather than giving a detailed ERM structure. It advocates for incorporating risk into business decision-making to achieve corporate goals (Andry et al., 2022). The standard can be used by corporations, groups, associations, community businesses, and individual small and medium-sized enterprises.

The ISO 31000:2009 is made up of five components; ratification, planning, implementation, monitoring, improvement, and communication. The standard is set to integrate all management processes, set a performance yardstick, enable protection of set values, and spread ERM comprehension in all sectors (Barafort et al., 2019). In addition, it considers the internal and external factors that will cause the threats or be a threat to the risk management process. It also includes the risk control options since it is an open standard that guides on risk principles and not a fixed guideline.

The most significant strength of the ISO:2009 framework is that it is easy to understand; hence firms do not have to outsource human resources for its implementation. This saves costs for the firm. The framework is also coordinated to uphold their systems to present and future standards making it inclusive and progressive. Finally, the framework is focused on ERM as an overall strategic objective hence can be used by firms with varied business models (Antonionia et al., 2019). The framework's benefits are that it reduces risks impact and increases organisational effectiveness. Other benefits include; Firstly, improves risk governance in a firm as it states standards yardsticks for various stakeholders to implement. Secondly, the standard strengthens the firms' internal operational and financial controls. Thirdly, ISO 31000:2009 improves disaster management, protects assets, and upholds reputation.

A significant criticism of the ISO 31000:2009 framework is that it is not a certifiable standard, so corporations using it cannot name it their central ERM guide if they are situated in countries that demand such risk management requirements. In addition, the framework is already

set up to consider all the internal risk processes and hence leaves little to no room for internal additions (Argadinata et al., 2023). Finally, the framework centers its system on incorporating risk practices with internal management workings and barely includes the external aspects of risks. External risks arising from political, economic, and environmental factors can also affect the firm's performance and shareholder value.

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Figure 2. 5 Expressing the ERM Processes of ISO 31000:2009 (ISO, 2009).

Another criticism of the ISO 31000:2009 risk framework is that it does not give practical guidance for ERM implementation. This is because the framework fails to consider the risk framework and process dynamics. Furthermore, it fails to outline how organisational tools can be

used in this risk process (Antonionia et al., 2019). Finally, ISO 31000:2009 requires a lot to be integrated into an organisation; hence is limited for use by organisations that had pre-planned for the human and financial costs of the integration.

2.5.2 Integrated Framework for ERM (IFERM) by COSO

Committee of Sponsoring organisations (COSO) 2017 framework offers an updated framework referred to as Enterprise Risk Management — Integrating with Strategy and Performance. COSO 2017 ERM framework was developed and viewed as an integral part of strategic planning to identify opportunities from risks and create and maintain value other than focusing on preventing the impact of risk on value and risk minimization (Bensaada & Taghezout, 2019). Due to its ability to identify opportunities among risks, it allows organisations to increase their risk appetite. Since the system is integral to the strategy, risk management is carried out daily, and risks are not viewed as negatives (Argadinata et al., 2023). The system has five interrelated components: governance and culture, which indicates the support of the system by top management, and culture: strategy and Objective-setting focus on integrating the system into the organisational strategy and objectives as a strategic tool (Alawattagama, 2018). The performance component indicates the system's ability to identify, evaluate, respond and report strategic risks. Review and revision share insights on ERM performance and possible revisions. The information, communication, and reporting components emphasises that ERM is a continuous process, and there must be ongoing risk identification and strategy information. The framework insists that enterprise risk management should not be a department or a responsibility of a specific function but culture, practices, and capabilities which integrate strategic objectives to manage risks and create, preserve and realise value.

The COSO framework was created to help firms alter and set up better internal control systems. It has undergone numerous changes over the past two decades since its invention. Unlike the ISO 31000:2009, it outlines a detailed structure firm can use for their ERM practices (Andry et al., 2022). The former reason for formation was to prevent fraudulent financial reporting, but it has developed purely into a risk management guideline. It is a modern standard and is used widely all over the world. It focuses on techniques and enterprise culture as the basis for ERM success.

The components of the COSO framework include; Management and culture, techniques and goal-setting, performance management, monitoring and reviews, communication, and reporting. Some disadvantages of the standard are that it is too detailed, making it incomprehensible. In addition, it is created for U.S. businesses and hence fails to account for international cultural and factorial differences (Barafort et al., 2019). Nevertheless, it is cherished by financial and accounting firms because its foundation is rooted in compliance auditing and reporting. IFERM requires organisations to incorporate strategies, operations, reporting, and compliance.

Jill and Houmes (2014) discuss the dimensional matrices of the COSO frameworks, the diverse components on either side of the matrix, and their relevance. In a three-dimensional COSO framework matrix, the authors explain that one dimension has the major IFERM components such as strategies, operations, compliance, and reporting goals. The second dimension has business makeup factors such as divisions, subsidiaries, and units. Jill and Houmes (2014) denote that the matrix also demonstrates the relationship between components, goals, and the organisational structure.

The operational objectives protect a firm's resources and operations against losses and financial constraints. Secondly, the compliance goals focus on the regulatory functions of the firm. Thirdly, the reporting objectives involve financial auditing and performance management aspects

of a business. Finally, the strategic goals are the plans to achieve the enterprises' set goals. These facets are vital in determining whether the framework is practical for implementation in a telecommunications firm.

Like every other framework, the IFERM has both strengths and criticisms. However, the strengths of ERM make it the most practical framework for companies to use. First, the COSO approach incredibly improves internal organisational controls when implemented. Secondly, the framework is in-built with great controls to prevent cyber insecurity (Nugroho et al., 2021). Thirdly, IFERM is cost- saving because it prevents legislative costs due to their compliance objective and generally risk aftermaths. Finally, COSO improves investors' input into the companies because they are assured of good outputs due to the dependable risk framework.

The criticisms of IFERM are that it is a complex framework that requires a lot of research work to understand. Organisations, therefore, have to liaise with risk professionals to implement it, costing them extra time, human resources, and capital. In addition, other studies have noted that the COSO framework has technical deficiencies that cause it to register outcome inefficiencies (Rampini et al., 2019). These deficiencies include the minimal inclusion of external factors that enormously impact firms, as evidenced by the Covid 19 pandemic. The framework also considers the typical outcomes of risks and, in the process, fails to anticipate unusual outcomes.

Figure 2.6 Expresses the COSO framework's three-dimensional matrix and components (Jill and Houmes, 2014).

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Other criticisms of the COSO framework that seem to work against its implementation in the telecommunications sector include that it relies on solving organisational risks and neglects operational risks. According to Lopez, COSO is unsustainable in the telecommunications sector because it focuses on organisational risks more than operational risks (López, 2021). The author further explains that this is a problem because most risks in the telecommunications sector arise from their operations. Lopez discredits the COSO framework further by noting its feature

requirement that demands annual for every risks management process in their sequence. The reviews are a good thing as they ensure the total completion of the processes. The only problem arises from the time-consuming nature of the review process and the extra costs incurred in acquiring risk management auditing professionals for the process. Lopez finally notes that the COSO framework gives a risk perception that only views risks as disadvantageous occurrences instead of finding ways the risks could be opportunities.

ISO 31000 and COSO frameworks are similar. They both accomplish their key objective as ERM standards; they guide decision-making by pinpointing and assessing risks to attain the organisation's objectives. Other similarities include that they both require ERM to be incorporated with a firm's decision-making, and they both were intended to be guiding principles, not certification standards (Ahmet, 2023). However, ISO 31000:2009 and COSO framework being the top 2 leading standards globally, they have many differences. First, the two standards are set up to target different markets. The latter targets auditing and accounting firms, while the former contains principles that any business can employ. Second, ISO 31000:2009 has been embraced as the national ERM standard by slightly over 50 countries, while COSO is mainly used in the USA. Finally, COSO is centered around corporate governance, while ISO 31000:2009 has its foundation and fundamental principles strictly based on risk management.

However, COSO updated the framework in 2013 to include the new guidelines referred to as the 2013 COSO framework or the COSO cube. The figure below depicts the COSO image and the underlying components.

Figure 2. 7expresses the COSO framework's three-dimensional matrix and components (Jill and Houmes, 2014).

The COSO framework revolved around 17 internal control principles within the original categories of the COSO pyramid. It has 77 points aimed at designing, implementing and conducting internal controls.

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2.5.3. Risk Management Standard by the Federation of the European Risk Management Association (FERMA)

The Risk management framework by FERMA was created by a couple of organisations in the U.K. who came together intending to construct a risk evaluation criterion for public companies' use. FERMA defines risk management terms, the ERM processes for firms to abide by, and the risk management team's structure. It acknowledges risk as a central part of business operations and success. The framework aims to deal with uncertainties to make sure firms receive sustained benefits. Radaelli states that the risk management process under the FERMA framework arises from the strategic goals and the policy of a company Radaelli (, 2021). The steps followed when using

FERMA are similar to the discussed enterprise risk management steps. Radaelli also explains that the system is thorough and includes all types of risk in its identification and evaluation process. He notes that thoroughness includes assessing all the types of risks in the firm. It also estimates the risk probability of occurrence and possible outcomes using quantitative and qualitative analysis mechanisms. The policy also outlines the roles of the various stakeholders and caters to their performance management and reporting of success rates to the board of management.

According to Andersen (2010), the FERMA risk management control is beneficial and inefficient. It is most helpful because it neutralizes risks and improves a firm's shareholders' value, like other ERM frameworks. In addition, it enhances the performance output of workers of the risk department as it outlines their duties and creates room for support and supervision. Andersen also adds that the framework creates a communicative organisational culture that promotes interactions between the departments influencing positive outcomes. Also, the system caters to monitoring and reviewing its components to warrant efficiency. IRM's greatest strength is its simplicity. It is easy for individuals and enterprises to understand and implement the IRM framework. Andersen gives the framework's most significant criticism as its inability to be inclusive of external controls. This European framework is famous for its limited criticisms.

2.5.4 Risk Maturity Model of the Risk Management Society.

This ERM model is based on the capability maturity model founded in the 1980s. It is known for its outstanding technical support as it uses a system orchestrated by a top ERM solutions developer. It incorporates all the aspects of business into the risk evaluation framework but is more

of a planning and measurement tool for evaluating a firm's ERM process. A practice that has acquired its excellent efficiency since its inception into management. The model is also engineered to integrate with a firm's leadership style and risk culture. This integration has made the framework suitable for numerous differing companies (RIMS, 2008)

In his risk maturity model journal, Hopkinson describes the model as Hopkinson (2017). He explains that the model was initially made for the software industry until later when it was incorporated into other sectors like finance and human resources. Hopkinson gives the advantageous branches of the system that enable its efficiency. One is its benchmarking tool that enables firms to compare the maturity levels of their systems to other competing firms. It also enables them to understand their processes' evolution and strengths and weaknesses. The system enacts its goal by stating a maturity ladder companies can streamline their operations using as they progress from the bottom to the top. The ladder steps are aligned to competency levels in the risk management process. Hopkinson (2017) explains that the ladder steps are branched into seven variables: business resilience, risk appetite, uncovering risks, and the sustainability of the business. These seven variables are aligned to twenty-five competency characteristics. The model has an additional 68 readiness indicators that work together with the seven variables and twenty-five traits to assist managers in creating a vivid road map to the successful adoption and management of ERM.

The most significant strength of the RMM is that it has been simplified to accommodate various business languages hence making it understandable to various audiences. It is easy to understand; hence, any business owner can implement it without hiring risk management experts, making it less costly than frameworks requiring experts. Its greatest weakness is that it is not an independent framework as it is used to evaluate the efficiency of other business frameworks.

Therefore, most businesses use it as a supplement as it was intended for. This leads to extra costs since one has to acquire and manage two or more ERM frameworks.

2.5.5 Rationale for the Proposed Risk Framework

The rationale for settling on creating another framework is linked to the advantages of the components structure of the potential framework and its effectiveness. As discussed in the ERM frameworks, the existing frameworks are not ideally suitable for the telecom industry. The ISO 31000:2009, despite having a technological adaptation, focuses on outlining organisational processes for firms to follow without specifying on integration and internal controls. Telecommunications firms have the most risks arising from their operations due to the complexity of the technology required to run the business. The COSO ERM framework is primarily unsuitable because it is pretty one-dimensional, unlike the multi-faceted telecommunications firms. It also neglects the operational aspects in its structure and focuses on the organisational aspects (Purdy,2010). The other frameworks are so incompatible with the telecom sector that any telecom firm rarely implements them.

Another rationale for creating a new ERM framework for the telecom industry in Algeria arises from the need for a framework suitable for the country's specific industry and particular external environment. The Algerian external environment differs from the environments in which the main discussed ERM frameworks were set. Therefore, creating a framework that considers the particular political socio-economic environment of the Algerian telecom sector is vital. Furthermore, the volatile economic sector of Algeria creates a need for ERM systems that are efficient and easily adaptable There are no ERM frameworks locally created for companies by the government or any other governing bodies in Algeria. Most companies in the country use the ERM frameworks instituted by international bodies such as the ISO 31000:2009 and the framework by

COSO (Bensaada and Taghezout, 2019). ERM as a concept has spread quite far in the nation. The country has limited telecommunications firms owned by various individuals, corporations, or the government. These few telecommunications firms use ERM to manage operational, financial, and legislative risks. Studies discussed above have pointed to a correlative relationship between a firm's ERM efficiency and the firm's profitability and competitive advantage. Big corporations acknowledge and implement these discussed frameworks because they have a lot to lose if their goals are not achieved annually.

2.6 The Proposed ERM adoption Framework for The Telecommunications Sector.

Figure 2. 8 The proposed ERM Adoption Framework

The basis of this thesis is to develop an ERM adoption framework for the telecom industry. The research has pointed to the lack of an ERM framework suitable for telecom firms' complex nature. Frameworks like the international ERM framework such as the COSO ERM frameworks (2004, 2017) and the ISO 31000 (2009,2018) are created to accommodate every industry (COSO, 2016). However, Telecom is a complex industry that continuously grows due to the fast technological growth rate. Therefore, the frameworks have too many limitations concerning the telecom industry leading to inefficiencies in their risk management in the sector. There are also no frameworks created with Algeria's financial, legal, economic, social, and political environment. The study is on the telecommunications sector in Algeria so that the only suitable framework would accommodate the Algerian internal and external environment.

When picking out an ERM framework, it is vital to look out for some specific variables before making that choice. The number of companies in the same sector adopting the framework can guide a business/individual on whether the framework fits their industry or purposes. This criterion can guide a student researching the framework for an industry too. The primary factors that managers should prioritize when picking out a framework for their independent firms include the business size, organisational complexity, business location, and organisational industries (Pagach and Warr, 2011). It is vital to find a framework that notes the telecom firms' changing internal and external factors with telecommunications. It should integrate ERM processes with the ERM framework and the organisational aspects. It should address the particular risks that telecom firms in that geographical situation are prone to. Finally, the framework must be comprehensive since the telecom industry is complex.

The most necessary component of ERM is the risk response. Results determine the efficiency of a system. So, picking a framework that produces the best results for the sector or organisation is a priority. A few risk management guidelines are based on the above frameworks

explained under ERM frameworks with information and technology. The complexity of operations in the telecom sector is a significant factor to consider when picking a suitable ERM framework for the industry. The framework must be adaptable to the industry, comprehensible, and acquired at reasonable costs. Above all, it has to cater to the multi-faceted nature of information technology. The telecommunication industry in Algeria faces complex risk challenges (Bensaada and Taghezout, 2019). Therefore, the proposed ERM framework will be aligned with the firm's strategic objectives to address the risks from a holistic approach. The framework will define the roles of the risk management stakeholders at all organisational levels to break the risk management processes' rigidity. The Algerian telecommunication industry is in the transformation phase, which requires the players to understand the emerging risks and adopted systems, and offer ways to manage them (Bensaada and Taghezout, 2019). The system will be intrinsically aligned to the telecommunication firms' organisational corporate and business strategies. Strategic RM framework advocates addressing risk as an integral part of organisational strategies and risk management. The proposed ERM framework to be adopted will be aligned with strategic factors in the telecommunication industry in Algeria, which will focus on the risk appetite, which is the level of risk challenges the organisation wishes to live with, risk oversight, risk awareness culture, corporate governance involvement, and strategic objectives. The system will address vital aspects of ERM unique to the telecommunication industry by aligning with the organisational strategic goals. The Strategic alignment framework will address noted ERM issues and apply an enterprise-wide framework that reflects the enterprise risk challenges in the business's internal and external

environment (Andronache, 2019). The proposed ERM framework should be consistent in addressing different risk challenges, dynamic and flexible to accommodate dynamism of the risks in the telecommunication industry, user-friendly, eliminate the complexities of systems to allow easy interface for fast risk process, and has a clear guide for implementation. The most crucial concern of the ERM framework is to address risk challenges to achieve the strategic objectives set by the telecommunication firms (Sasmita and Suhaimi, 2019).

2.6.1 The Inputs factors of the proposed ERM Framework

Figure 2.5 shows how the organisation's strategic vision and mission determine the input factors of the proposed framework. These inputs are important because they help figure out what the main features of the proposed ERM framework. Every organisation that deals with communications has different input factors. Wilson (2008) says that the best input factors can only be chosen if the organisation's top management can define and understand its strategic and risk goals.

A well-thought-out risk organisational strategy is as essential as the risk framework. Companies must set the input factors based on their business model and core values and include them in the system. The system is built to accommodate and work with these factors. In addition, the system incorporates the corporate governors' roles in the input section. They determine a firm's risk culture and set these objectives and strategies.

Based on the findings from the literature reviewed above, and the literature gap, the key input factors are:

- Key strategies and objectives
- Risk appetite aligned with risk toleranceRisk oversight
- Corporate governance

As risk becomes a part of the business, companies have to come up with strong risk-based strategies to deal with these dynamics (Althonayan *et al.*, 2011A). This would require organisations to include well-defined risk factors when setting up corporate strategies. This would help them to prepare for risk when making major managerial decisions (Linke and Florio, 2019). So that businesses can align risk with their policies, the proposed framework must take organisational strategy into account (RIMS,2012). As a result, the ERM and strategy will integrate risk awareness into all of the organisation's business units (Noy, 2003). Risk appetite and tolerance can be controlled by the top management. So, a well-balanced alignment of risk appetite and risk tolerance is important for ERM alignment (Konarsky, 2010). As Lam (2010) says, aligning ERM with strategy execution can help keep the organisation's risk appetite and exposure in check.

The engagement and commitment of top management to ERM is another important part of the proposed framework for adopting ERM. To set up and run a sustainable risk program, it is essential for the top management to show unwavering commitment (Beasley *et al.*, 2010).

Corporate governance as an input defines the support of the framework by senior management and how the leadership helps in adopting the framework. Manab *et al.* (2010) say that good corporate governance will make it clear what the roles of management, the board of directors, and shareholders are when it comes to enterprise risk management (ERM). Richard Anderson *et al.* (2010) say that the ERM framework should be based on three main principles: (1) support from the board of directors for corporate governance; (2) a culture of performance that is rewarded by the top management; and (3) the long-term business perspective of the shareholders. Risk oversight

involves the top management understanding the risk inherence and gathering all risk information for critical risk decisions (Gatzer and Martin, 2015)

2.6.1.1 Core components of the proposed framework

This section will look at the main parts of the ERM framework that is being proposed. The main goal of the framework is to help organisations in the telecom industry make well-informed decisions about risk. This would help the organisation's financial and non-financial market position in the long run.

2.6.1.2 ERM infrastructure

The proposed model shows an-enterprise-wide risk infrastructure as central to the success of ERM. The nature of telecommunication industry and market is complex, which makes it hard to adopt a uniform risk system (Andronache, 2019). The current framework therefore encourages a robust risk reporting, update of risk information, and sharing of risk information throughout the organisation. This would allow for transparent integration of risk data in the organisation such as risks associated with technology failures are integrated in the system to protect stakeholder value across the organisation (Grishunin & Suloeva, 2020). ERM is easier to put into place when data is timely. Althonayan et al. (2011b) say that this means there needs to be a risk management structure that makes sure data is collected, processed, and stored both effectively and efficiently.

2.6.1.3 ERM process

ERM process is needed to find, analyse, quantify, reduce, monitor, and report risks throughout the organisation in a consistent way (ISO, 2018). The risk management process is aimed at making it easier for an organisation to reach its strategic business and operational goals (COSO, 2012). In order to do this, the leaders of the organisation need reliable information to make decisions (Smart

and Creelman, 2009). It is important that ERM is aligned with the preferred planning process, strategy execution, and operational processes (Theil and Ferguson, 2003; Smart and Creelman, 2009). Figure 2–4 shows how the ERM process is aligned with the planning process. It also shows how this alignment keeps risks, goals, and plans in constant communication. Frigo (2008) says that aligning ERM with the organisation's strategic and planning processes leads to better organisational performance, which makes it easier to implement organisational strategies and reach the goals.

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Figure 2.9 aligning ERM with strategic planning process

Source: AS/NZS Committee (2004)

The goal of the process is to find out what the organisation's goals are so that essential risk strategies can be made (Grishunin and Suloeva, 2020). Usually, risk tools and techniques (KPIs) are the risk metrics that enable organisations to track and measure performance against the risk policies, strategies, and goals.

2.6.1.4 ERM culture

Risk culture is an important part of the ERM implementation process, which has been covered in the literature. The risk culture of an organisation is made up of the values that support risk management. Enterprise risk culture is a compulsory part of a successful ERM program in today's highly complex and competitive business world (Mikes, 2009a; Deloitte, 2012a; Ashby et al., 2012; Hindson, 2013). Borge (2013) says that the key to good risk management is an enterprise risk culture. Finding out what drives and motivates people to take risks is the most effective way of managing risk (Deloitte, 2012b). Culture has been found to be a key part of building risk-intelligent organisations, where everyone in the organisation is responsible for managing risk in a way that makes the organisation more valuable (Deloitte, 2012b). So, an organisation that doesn't have a strong and well-developed enterprise risk culture can be unstable and make people doubt the organisation's standing (Deloitte, 2011). Another important part of the enterprise risk culture is honesty and mutual engagement. For an enterprise-wide risk culture to be created, it is important that all parts of the business engage mutually. Althonaya *et al.* (2012a) say that businesses that focus on results show that the flow of data about risk is important for keeping good governance

and culture of an organisation. Respecting norms and ethics, which means following the rules, helps the organisation make better decisions (Pagach and Warr, 2010). The Risk mindset shows how important risk insight and risk information are for managing risk well. It's important because many organisations have problems because employees are afraid to share information that could hurt their performance, which makes it hard for the organisation to make good decisions. Proper governance stands for the sound policies and frameworks in the foundation that improve its competitive advantage by addressing the risk policy framework (Bensaada and Taghezout, 2019). Corporate governance in a risk culture needs the support and buy-in of top management, which is important for the system to be used. The risk policies are made by the strategic managers, who are the leaders of the organisation. Risk training and awareness involve enterprise-wide education and awareness of the ERM framework, which determines how well the system works after it has been put in place.

2.6.1.5 ERM integration

A key part of the proposed framework for the telecom industry is the integration of ERM. Integration of ERM is made up of four main parts: strategic planning, operational processes, structure and ownership, and communication across the enterprise. Lam (2010) says that an organisation needs to include ERM in its management processes in order to improve its risk profile. ERM will also be easier to integrate when it is in line with the strategies of the organisation. A key part of making an effective ERM, however, is making sure that the structure of risk ownership is clear and transparent, and that there is good communication between ERM risk events and resources. (IRM, 2012) The system is built with the goal of making new decisions based on risk that will add value to the organisation and improve its reputation. The framework guides policies

that support effective risk management processes. This includes developing key risk indicators (KRIs), which are the relevant risk measures that give information on how risk affects strategic objectives (Grishunin and Suloeva, 2020). To reach strategic risk goals, the risk framework creates activities that work together. The framework shows how the process works, from design and specifications to implementation, monitoring, reporting, and improvement. The proposed risk management process for the external business environment considers the regulatory, financial, political, economic, and cultural frameworks of the external environment. The outside world is changing, competitive, and unpredictable, which affects how telecommunication organisations handle risk (Grishunin and Suloeva, 2020). The organisation uses tools like PESTEL and SWOT, which are the most commonly used, to look at the outside world. The proposed adoption ERM framework can use the tools for analysing the outside world to give companies a competitive edge.

2.6.2 The Outputs of the Proposed Framework

ERM outputs are benefits that are derived from adopting the proposed framework. The main output of the adoption of the proposed ERM framework is creating and preserving stakeholder value and enhanced competitive advantage. The output categories divide to three main categories namely corporate, business and operational elements (Andronache, 2019). Operational output includes increased operational efficiency, risk silos breakdown, effective risk processes, and better disaster preparedness. Corporate output involves increased shareholder value, sustainable competitive advantage, regulatory compliance, solid risk governance, risk-based decision-making, and enterprise-wide risk culture and awareness.

2.6.3 ERM Alignment Framework Connectivity and Implementation

The connectivity and implementation of this proposed framework are essential. The proposed ERM adoption framework outlines all interrelated activities that aim to achieve effective risk management. The connectivity system of the framework's various components determines its desirability for use and comprehensibility. The framework connectivity and alignment process must be followed for practical ERM application and integration. The process entails a requirement analysis, design, specifications, implementation, monitoring, and improvements.

Requirement analysis is the stage during the ERM process when an analysis is conducted to check the rate of abiding by the framework. This is vital in ensuring the ERM framework process is followed for the best results. Steps followed during this stage include checking the organisational attributes, ERM structure, risk management capabilities of the framework, and conducting an environmental analysis. Finally, the design and specifications stage is whereby the stakeholders ensure all design details are logged into the system. At this stage, they ensure the risk appetite is aligned to risk tolerance, reliable corporate governance, and the culture is aligned to communication. Communication is one of the tools of connectivity. A risk framework is set up by first understanding the organisation and its core principles. Secondly, they gained adequate comprehension of the risks associated with the business and key risks. It is thirdly, aligning risk culture and communication for efficiency.

Monitoring is the final stage of this connectivity. It creates opportunities to give feedback and ensure the efficiency of the process. It allows for improvement as the errors are pointed out and rectified in this stage. Providing feedback and checking the milestones enables identifying additional risks that were not noticed earlier.

2.6.3.1 Key risk indicators KRI's and Key Performance Indicators KPI'S

Key performance indicators alone cannot be used as the primary metrics because they measure events that have already happened, measuring the achieved against the desired performance. KPIs are also used to measure the risk dynamism and risk tolerance levels (Andronache, 2019). KPIs, therefore, are used to monitor changes in the exposure levels and offer early warnings for risk prevention. KPIs provide past risk information and deliver metrics that guide the best risk response to be adopted. On the other hand, key risk indicators are metrics used to offer insights into potential risks such as risk performance volatility. KRIs are critical in risk management because they provide the administration with assessment tools necessary for risk identification and control (Andronache, 2019). The proposed framework will develop effective KRIs that will integrate risk information required to mitigate risks to achieve strategic objectives. For effective adoption and implementation of the proposed framework, each organisation will be necessary to understand how the strategic objectives will be integrated into the framework. The risks in the telecommunication industry are relatively the same, and therefore, each organisation will need to understand its organisational goals and align the system accordingly (Bensaada and Taghezout, 2019). Organisations find the development of effective KRIs a challenge because of the failure to understand the risk environment. Therefore, the proposed framework will allow telecommunication firms to effectively identify the key risks and formulate risk aggregates as the key risk indicators. The proposed framework advocates for a bottom-up risk approach, where the key risk indicators are determined from specific processes and risks. Since the system manages risks enterprise-wide, the identification of critical risks should also be applied organisational-wide from the daily operations

2.7 Gaps in The Existing ERM Literature

This section notes some shortcomings observed from the data that has been analysed in the literature review.

Firstly, the implementation process of ERM is the minor present data from the literature review. Studies consistently failed to mention the implementation process of ERM. ERM implementation is not a straightforward concept because it encompasses the goals of the firm's leaders and the company's strategic plans. Implementation is a means to the attainment of ERM goals. Carroll (2016) explains this neglecting of data on the implementation process to fear of deterring from the goals (Carroll, 2016). She explains that focusing on the process rather than what should be achieved discourages achieving the goals. On the other hand, the significant challenges and developments of ERM are the most recurrent topics in the reviewed literature.

Very few studies that demonstrate the value generated by ERM in practice exist. Most of the research excludes mentioning the value generated by the ERM process adaptation and implementation to firms. Most studies mention that ERM is beneficial to a great extent and adds to the profitability and competitive advantage. However, the studies fail to quantify their claims, making them seem like unreliable information. There is a need to quantify the value generated by ERM to elaborate on the need for ERM adoption and management in various sectors and firms. This can prove the essentiality of ERM adoption and management to business owners.

Generally, the studies on ERM in the telecommunications sector of Algeria are too limited. There is especially very little data on the Algerian telecommunications sector accessible online. This points out a need for more research in both ERM and ERM frameworks and ERM in the Algerian telecommunications sector. Algeria has a standard number of telecom firms from which ERM data can be collected, so there is no explanation for why the data is almost nonexistent. The

minimal collected data on Algerian telecom firms is extracted mainly from North American and Europe studies that mildly included EWRM in Africa.

2.8 Chapter Summary.

The chapter reviewed literature and background information from different scholars. Definitions and evolution of enterprise risk management were handled in the chapter, which indicated that ERM evolved in the 1990s due to corporate losses, which led to the closure of many organisations. Businesses also started leaning towards the business model centered on providing value to shareholders, so they needed mechanisms to counter things that prevented them from attaining this value. Enterprise risk management frameworks are used to avoid or reduce the impact of threats and enhance the achievement of organisational goals. The chapter also reviewed the current trends in enterprise risk management, which indicated that the ERM practices are becoming popular with many entities triggered by the dynamism of the risk environment. Shareholder value is directly linked to profitability and success; hence it is always positioned with the business objectives. Other essential reasons firms adopt enterprise risk management include; improving business solvency, performing their corporate social responsibility role, and building sustainable business systems that continually increase value provision. The main trend is attributed to implementing the frameworks and the gaining need to gather information about the emerging ERM systems.

Organisations choose the standardized systems that fit their risk environment. Each framework contains different practices; for instance, the COSO model, in comparison to other, acknowledges the broad scope that ERM covers and emphasises that integrating ERM processes with internal operations and management facilitate a company's ability to attain its strategic,

operational, reporting, and compliance goal. The chapter discusses the enterprise risk management process, which involves planning, identifying, assessing, monitoring, and analysing existing and potential threats. They further divide the eight sequence steps into five undertakings: risk assessment, risk control, communication, monitoring, and controlling risk affairs. The critical factors discussed indicate that distinct business entities have unlike essential elements of success based on their business model. Strategic objectives determine crucial success factors in the business environment. Success factors also determine the need to adapt and develop the ERM frameworks. The chapter discussed various theories of enterprise risk management, specifically organisation and systems theories. Different ERM frameworks were reviewed, such as COSO 2017, ISO 31000:2009, and Integrated Framework for Enterprise Risk Management (IFERM). The chapter concluded by discussing the proposed framework alignment with the telecommunication industry, the rationale, and the components of the system.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

After the identification of the gap in the literature in the previous chapter. This chapter presents the approach adopted by the researcher in answering the research questions. This chapter further discusses the appropriate research philosophy for the research study. Following this, the data collection and analysis methods are reviewed. The present chapter also addresses the sampling methods, design, quality of the research, and ethical consideration. The current study adopted an interpretivist philosophy and adopted a purposive sampling to conduct 26 qualitative semi-structured interviews. Thus, the current study used the thematic analysis technique in order to present the data collected.

3.2 Research Philosophy

Identifying the most appropriate philosophy is of a significance importance in planning and executing research (Saunders *et al.*, 2019). A research philosophy is considered reliable only if it is built on planned and coherent assumptions that guide the methodological choices, plan of the research, data collection methods, and the data analysis process (Creswell, 2014).

Research philosophy is referred to as the paradigm, beliefs, and assumptions that guide the researcher in developing knowledge in a particular field (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019)

The researcher applied the interpretivism research philosophy. Applying the interpretivism paradigm, the researcher assumes that access to reality is achieved through the social constructions, including consciousness, language, shared meanings, and research instruments (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Further, interpretivism is founded on the assumptions that truth and knowledge are subjective and are based on people's experiences and their interpretation of the experiences. Therefore, the interpretivism research philosophy is most appropriate in this study since the researcher focuses on understanding the risk challenges facing telecommunications enterprises in general and the Algerian telecommunications industry in particular. Notably, applying the interpretivism paradigm, the researcher emphasises understanding the research participants and the interpretation of the world around them. Moreover, by emphasizing the study participants' understanding of the factor in enterprise risk management due to different individual perspectives, the researcher roots the study on the assumption that knowledge cannot be the same among the different participants. By applying the interpretivism paradigm, the researcher adopts the relativist ontology to define truth and reality. According to Pham (2018), the relativist ontology outlines that a research phenomenon has multiple interpretations; hence truth and reality cannot be determined by measurement. The relativist ontology is founded on the assumption that a situation under study has multiple realities, and the realities can be examined and meaning reconstructed through the interactions between the researcher and the study participants (Pham, 2018). Therefore, in this study, the researcher sought to derive meaning from the various interpretations of the research participants. As such, the research findings reflected the different interpretations and realities of how effective the ERM frameworks are and how a tailored ERM that is specific in nature could lead to effective risk management among Algerian telecom organisations.

By applying the interpretivism research philosophy, the researcher adopted the subjectivism epistemological assumptions. According to Amakiri and Juliet (2018), subjective epistemology is founded on the assumption that the researcher and the societal phenomenon under investigation are dependent and interrelated. Therefore, in this study, the researcher and the study participants under investigation are dependent and interrelated. As such, by being dependent on the study participants, the researcher derives the research findings from the individual interpretations of the study participants on how the factors that affect ERM adoption and the framework that is most relevant to organisations within the Algerian telecommunications industry. Although by applying the subjectivized epistemological assumptions, the researcher is dependent on the study participants to derive the research findings, the researcher seeks insight into the research topic before starting the data collection process (Wong *et al.*, 2011). However, due to the complex nature of reality and the assumption of the existence of multiple realities and the social construction of nature, the subjective epistemological assumptions allow the researcher to remain open to new knowledge throughout the research process (Wong *et al.*, 2011). Therefore, although the researcher has gained insight into the study through the review of academic literature and past research study, the researcher remains open to new knowledge due to the belief in multiple realities that explain the relationship. In this study, the researcher has focused on understanding and interpreting the meanings of the study participants' viewpoints and behavior rather than generalizing and predicting the link between ERM factors and the challenges facing the Algeria telecommunication industry.

Compared to the positivism research philosophy founded on the objectivist epistemological philosophy, the interpretivism philosophy offers the researcher increased flexibility in the study process since the investigator derives the research findings from the interpretation of the

participants' perspectives rather than the abstract theories (Amakiri and Juliet, 2018). In addition, compared to positivism research philosophy founded on the assumption that examining a research phenomenon is my final observation, the interpretivism philosophy allows the researcher to interpret and derive meaning from every observation (Amakiri and Juliet, 2018). Therefore, the interpretivism research philosophy is most applicable in this study since the experiences of ERM are relative, and it depends on many factors such as the internal, external and environmental risk factors. Furthermore, in this study, the derivation of the research findings from abstract theories is not applicable since the researcher seeks to comprehend and interpret the lived experiences of the study participants on how ERM factors change depending on the different variables involved.

3.2.1 Justification of the interpretive position

The Interpretivism paradigm accounts that the world is socially constructed, and different human interests affect knowledge (Zahle, 2021). Therefore, understanding ERM is complex because there is no one model of ERM, but different managers apply different strategies. Such fact indicates that interpretivism philosophy fits well in this research because there is no one universal framework of ERM or one formula on which ERM is based. Thus, understanding the interpretation of different company's ERM strategies will inform this research's conclusive remarks.

3.3 Research Approach

The researcher adopts the inductive research approach by applying the interpretivism research philosophy. The inductive research approach starts with making observations from the data and proposing theories based on the observations towards the end of the research process (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). Notably, when applying the inductive research approach, the researcher

is not guided by hypotheses but seeks to search for patterns and themes from the observations to develop explanations and theories. Therefore, by applying inductive reasoning, the researcher is free to change the direction of the study at any point in the research process. However, Woiceshyn and Daellenbach (2018) note that although the researcher is not guided by theories and hypotheses in the inductive approach, the researcher does not disregard the theories in formulating the research objectives and research questions. Therefore, existing theories on the relationship between ERM frameworks and the management of firms such as the Algerian telecommunication industry were retrieved by conducting a literature review to develop the research question, aim, and objectives. In addition, by using the detailed observations of the research participants' experiences and perspectives on the relationship between challenges within the telecommunication industries and the effectiveness of ERM frameworks to make abstract generalizations, the researcher is likely to derive several theories. Therefore, the inductive approach supports the philosophical assumption of the existence of multiple realities. The research findings will highlight the multiple theories that explain the relationship between the robust effectiveness of ERM frameworks and the management of the telecommunication industry, particularly the Algerian telecommunication industry.

One of the key strengths of the inductive research approach is supporting the generation of a new theory (Azungah, 2018, Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). Therefore, compared to the deductive method, which is fixed on proving or disproving the existing theories, the inductive approach allows the researcher to use the observations made through the interaction with the study participants to generate new theory based on the specific experiences (Azungah, 2018). In addition, by starting with making a specific observation to derive patterns and generalizations, the inductive approach motivates the researcher to explore the research phenomenon further. Therefore, in this study, by generating multiple theories that explain how effective ERM frameworks are and how

they can be adopted in the telecommunication industry, the researcher can provide opportunities for other researchers to explore the generated theories further to determine whether they are right or wrong. In this regard, the study provides the foundation for future studies applying the deductive approach to test empirically whether the theories are right or wrong.

Further, the inductive approach provides the researcher with increased flexibility and allows for creativity during the data collection, interpretation, and generation of the research findings (Azungah, 2018, Mohajan, 2018). As such, the researcher can adopt a more flexible structure for collecting and interpreting the responses to permit changes in the areas of emphasis as the research study progresses. When applying the inductive approach, the researcher is part of the research processes, and the findings are dependent on how the researcher interprets the data hence limiting the generalization of the research findings (Mohajan, 2018, Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). However, in this study, the researcher is less concerned with generalizing the research findings but aims at understanding the specific experiences of the study participants, gaining in-depth information on how the effective ERM frameworks are, and how they can be adopted when it comes to the management of telecommunication industry. Furthermore, the research objectives guide to a more specific finding, such as identifying the different factors of ERM and how such affects the Algerian telecommunication industry in order to guide the development of the proposed framework.

3.3.1 Research strategy and justification for the inductive approach

The inductive approach is adopted since the investigator is applying the interpretivism philosophy. The method starts with making observations, looking at the details within the data, and suggesting theories based on the observations as the research process ends (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach,

2018). Notably, the study aimed to detect different themes and patterns from the interpretation of the secondary data. Such themes and patterns help in giving an in-depth understanding of the concepts being studied. Thus, the technique is referred to as inductive reasoning. Therefore, inductive reasoning is flexible because it allows the researcher to change and interpret different meanings relevant to the research question. However, Woiceshyn and Daellenbach (2018) demonstrate that the inductive approach is flexible and is not guided by the hypothesis or existing theories. However, the researcher does not assume the existing theories. Such theories help to strengthen the research objectives and questions.

Thus, existing sources of evidence related to enterprise risk management and how they affect the Algerian Telecom Industry were retrieved from the existing literature review. It helped develop the research aim and objectives. Such literature is triangulated with twenty-six interviews with the Algerian Telecom industry managers. Moreover, by using the exhaustive analysis from the secondary sources on the relationship between success factors of ERM and profitability of Algerian Telecom industries to make abstract generalizations, the investigator is likely to derive numerous theories. The inductive approach is suitable for supporting different philosophical assumptions because, as already mentioned, the world has mutable realities that are affected by different circumstances. Such is related to the study topic and the research question, which highlighted several theories demonstrating different concepts and realities affecting the relationship between success factors of ERM and insurance profitability of the Algerian Telecom industry.

Inductive reasoning is suitable for generating new knowledge and theory (Azungah, 2018, Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). In comparison to deductive reasoning, which is fixed and only approves or disapproves the theory that exists. The inductive method is flexible and allows the

researcher to observe different realities from existing and emerging realities. Therefore, a new theory is created with specific experiences (Azungah, 2018). Furthermore, beginning with the assumption of different detailed observations to gain knowledge or insight from themes and patterns before generalization. The inductive method motivates the investigator to explore the research phenomenon further. Thus, in this study, by generating several facts explaining how ERM impacts the Algerian Telcom industry's profitability, the investigator can offer opportunities for other researchers to explore the formed theories to determine whether they are wrong or right. The study provides the groundwork for future studies that apply the deductive approach to test empirically whether the theories are right or wrong. Furthermore, the inductive method is flexible, and it gives room for creativity during the process of gathering data, interpreting, and generalization the findings (Azungah, 2018, Mohajan, 2018).

Therefore, the investigator can practice a better manageable structure for interpreting and collecting the responses to show outcomes in the areas emphasised as the study continues. When applying the inductive approach, the investigator plays a role during the investigation process, and how the investigator interprets different meanings from the data gathered is essential. It can limit generalization in the results (Mohajan, 2018, Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). Nevertheless, during the study, the investigator has few problems with inducing the investigation findings but aspires to perceive specific themes from the secondary sources, gaining comprehensive information of how the ERM assists the Algerian Telcom industry's profitability. Furthermore, the research objectives guide to a more specific finding such as reviewing the available literature on enterprise risk management, analysing current challenges that face the telecommunications industry, specifically the Algerian Telcom industry, examining the current ERM frameworks, and proposing an adoption guidance model for the proposed ERM framework

3.4 Research Design

Qualitative methods are applied because they are suitable for exploratory design. Furthermore, studies related to different factors of ERM are relative and need a more profound or in-depth explanation. Such statements demonstrate that exploratory studies are ideal in a timely phenomenon. Therefore, exploratory research asks many questions, such as how and why a phenomenon happens (Bryman, 2016).

The secondary data is also explored and triangulated with the primary sources to get a deeper meaning of the relationships, exploring the meaning of enterprise risk management and the different factors to its success, and how such success factors affect the Algerian Telecom industry. Qualitative techniques are suitable for exploring such secondary evidence analysing and investigating those secondary data claims (Vaughan, 2019). Thus, through content examination of the secondary data (literature), descriptive design is applied to interrogate different ideas, concepts, perspectives, and meanings, including an in-depth understanding of the several academic work backgrounds. Such is done by asking the how, when, what, and where questions (Nassaji, 2015). Therefore, descriptive design helps explore different perspectives (Sreejesh *et al.*, 2014).

Exploring the study helps the researcher experiment with different understanding and perspectives from the data with counter options and thoughts. Exploring such views gives a deeper meaning to various concepts and ideas within the study (Creswell, 2013). In this case, the researcher is flexible, able to adopt multiple purposes, and accommodating new thoughts and emerging themes from the secondary data reviewed. The investigator explores through interrogating different definitions and words used. Additionally, the flexibility helps the investigator expand the scope of the research in gathering new ideas, perspectives, and concepts.

Therefore, such a design allows the investigator to get more meaning concerning the topic of study before drawing a conclusive finding or recommendation.

The explored and experimented information, that is, the secondary data, are categorized into different themes such as 1) enterprise risk management definitions and the evolution, 2) Current Trends in Enterprise Risk Management, 3) Enterprise Risk Management Processes, 4) Factors Impacting the Adoption and Growth of ERM, 5) theories and frameworks of enterprise risk management, 6) ERM Alignment Framework Connectivity and Implementation, and 7) challenges of ERM implementation. The literature looked at how vast different literature relates to the concepts and finding the relationship among the subtopics, then identifying the pattern of the reality of understanding the different perspectives. Triangulation is a qualitative technique that applies several methods in data analysis to explore and experiment with varying sources of data and credibility. Such approach—triangulation helps gain a comprehensive insight into the phenomenon or understanding of the themes as they emerge (Cope *et al.*, 2014). Thus, such secondary data were triangulated with the primary sources—semi-structured interviews before arriving at a conclusive remark.

Furthermore, it is a method that helps gain the credibility of the findings. It helps to validate the sources of the different data after carefully interrogating those sources concerning other multiple sources (Noble and Heale, 2019)—for example, reviewing the additional secondary data such as reports and academic sources, then comparing it with the primary sources. Therefore, objectivity is arrived at through these multiple sources of information.]

3.5 Sampling

Purposive sampling, as outlined by Etikan et al. (2016), involves the intentional selection of study participants based on specific qualities deemed relevant to the research. This strategy allows the researcher to focus on individuals who possess the necessary knowledge or experience in the subject under investigation, ensuring a targeted and informed data collection process (Taherdoost, 2016). In the context of this study, participants for interviews were deliberately chosen based on their expertise and experiences in utilizing various colleague voice practices within the telecommunications sector. It is crucial to emphasize that, within purposive sampling, considerations such as the willingness to participate, availability of participants, and their ability to express opinions and experiences effectively plays a paramount role (Palinkas et al., 2015).

While purposive sampling deviates from the randomness of selecting participants across various age or cultural backgrounds, it offers a focused approach by concentrating on individuals with specific characteristics. In this study, the deliberate selection of interview respondents with expertise in diverse colleague voice practices within the telecommunications sector is aimed at garnering insightful information on the effectiveness of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) frameworks adopted by telecommunication firms. However, to ensure the robustness of the sampling strategy, it is imperative to address the adequacy and diversity of the sample size. Therefore, a critical consideration is given to determining that the chosen sample size of 26 interviews and the inclusion of four different companies are sufficiently large and diverse to capture a comprehensive understanding of ERM framework adoption in the telecommunications industry.

3.5.1 Target Population

The target population is a cluster of individuals that the research intervention intends to collect information and draw a conclusion based on their thought or perception. These groups or people should be described clearly to give a good aspect in research (Barnsbee *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, such target groups depend on the study's objective, the literature reviewed, and contextual information to be gathered (Malhorta, 2020). Additionally, the Target population is usually an integral part of the research, and it is identified at the research development or the conceptualization process (Rosen, 2005). In the case of this study, the study investigates critical success factors in ERM adoption in the telecom industry: the case of Algeria's telecom industry. Therefore, the target population is critical informants from the Algerian Telecom industry.

As Barnsbee *et al.* (2018), David Tonucci also points in Rosen (2005) edition that the target population is vital when determining who will be evaluated to understand the proposed information or question. Furthermore, the target population usually has specific characteristics, such as age, gender, geographical location, and ethnicity (Rosen, 2005). In this case, the people with the knowledge of ERM those with the Knowledge of Algerian telecom industries and how such organisations manage their risks within those enterprises. Furthermore, the Target population varies in terms of the size of the population, age group of the population, the procedure used to collect the data from the targeted population and the time that the data was collected. All these elements create the aspects of Validity and reliability within the research (Zakaria and Gupta, 2019).

3.5.2 Sampling of the targeted population

The focal point of this study is the Algerian Telecom industry, with Key Informants (KIs) representing pivotal positions within the organizations. The KIs identified for semi-structured interviews include Chief Executive Officers (CEOs), Chief Financial Officers (CFOs), Chief

Auditors Officers (CAOs), Chief Strategic Officers (CSOs), finance managers, audit managers, and risk managers. Leveraging the researcher's insider status within the Algerian Telecom Industry, having previously worked with a leading player in the sector, provides a distinct advantage for collecting primary data. The purposive sampling method is employed to target individuals who possess knowledge of risk management and have a background in the Algerian Telecom industry. A total of 26 individuals from the four telecommunications firms under study, referred to anonymously for confidentiality purposes, were selected based on their expertise and experience in risk management within the Algerian Telecom industry.

The individuals selected for interviews hold various positions within the telecom companies, representing key departments involved in risk management. Table 3.1 presents detailed information about the respondents, including their position, the company they work for (anonymized as Company Code), and the duration of the interview in minutes. This comprehensive sampling strategy ensures a diverse and representative range of perspectives from professionals actively engaged in risk management within the Algerian Telecom industry. Table 3.1 illustrates the respondents position:

Company Code	Respondent	Position	Interview duration (min)
	Respondent 1	Fraud department manager	32
	Respondent 2	Internal Auditor	25
	Respondent 3	Chief financial officer	40
	Respondent 4	Risk manager	35
	Respondent 5	Chief strategic officer	42
	Respondent 6	Revenue assurance manager	28
	Respondent 7	Network maintenance manager	47

1			
2	Respondent 8	Chief financial officer	31
	Respondent 9	Senior internal auditor	37
	Respondent 10	Roaming Analyst	45
	Respondent 11	Interconnect Manager	38
	Respondent 12	Internal Auditor	36
	Respondent 13	Revenue assurance deputy manager	43
3	Respondent 14	Chief Technical Officer	55
	Respondent 15	Chief Operational Officer	48
	Respondent 16	Risk manager	60
	Respondent 17	Senior internal auditor	42
	Respondent 18	Strategy director	35
	Respondent 19	Chief financial officer	52
	Respondent 20	Chief strategic officer	55
	Respondent 21	Roaming manager	48
	Respondent 22	National interconnect manager	56
4	Respondent 23	Risk officer	42
	Respondent 24	Chief financial officer	38
	Respondent 25	Strategy director	53
	Respondent 26	Fraud specialist	68

Table 3.1 Response information

Source: Reasercher

The selection of a purposive sampling approach in this study, targeting 26 key informants across four major telecommunication companies in Algeria, was guided by the objective of capturing diverse perspectives from individuals holding crucial roles in risk management within the industry. The adequacy and breadth of the sample size were determined through careful consideration of factors such as the depth of industry expertise, the variety of roles represented, and the inclusion of significant telecom players. By ensuring representation from various departments within each company, including Chief Executive Officers, Chief Financial Officers, Chief Auditors Officers, Chief Strategic Officers, finance managers, audit managers, and risk managers, the sample encompasses a wide range of experiences and insights. This approach enhances the richness and comprehensiveness of the data, ensuring a nuanced exploration of Enterprise Risk Management adoption in the Algerian telecom sector. Furthermore, the inclusion of four distinct telecom companies contributes to the generalizability of findings, offering a holistic view of industry practices and challenges, thereby strengthening the robustness of the study's outcomes.

3.6 Data Collection (Qualitative Quantitative)

The study gathered data from secondary and primary sources, and these sources helped to reach a broader range of information and understand the different perspectives related to the study. a inclusion and exclusion criteria used other categories to select both secondary and primary data. Such selection is discussed and given in the inclusion and exclusion tables below before using the data analysis technique.

3.6.1 Secondary Data

The secondary data was gathered from various online libraries, the online library was helpful due to the lockdown situation created by different world governments after the spread of the SARS0-COV-2 virus started in Wuhan, China, and its known deadly disease, COVID-19, led to millions of deaths. Therefore, the online library served as a source of secondary sources for the study. A general google scholar search was applied using the research topic to collect information; after that, research questions were created to get more specific data related to the study topic. In other words, the research question helped to include or exclude the secondary data.

The research questions were used as a strategy to gather information from various social science databases such as Taylor and Francis, Sage, and Oxford University Press. Specifically, Boolean operators such as AND, NOT, and OR, were used in the search engines such as google scholar and the mentioned social science databases above after different concepts were identified. Such a technique is helpful for widening or narrowing search to get relevant data. ‘AND,’ was used to narrow the search, focusing on the concept being searched, OR was used to widen the investigation. It helped find an idea or keyword related to the concept being explored. Lastly, NOT was used to narrow the search and look for the specific keyword being searched (Richard G. Trefry Library, 2018). Such criteria help explore the data and gather several data before using the inclusion and exclusion techniques explained below.

The concepts that emerged from the research questions, such are ‘ERM frameworks’ and ‘telecommunication industries challenges,’ were used in the search engines such as google scholar, and the above-mentioned social science databases together with the Boolean operators to search for relevant peer-reviewed articles, books, or reports. Such techniques helped to include relevant

materials for review. The books, articles, and reports which were relevant to the research questions or if they were related to the concepts being studied, then they were included for review. Those books, articles, and reports not relevant to the research questions and concepts understudy

were excluded by interrogating their abstracts, introduction, methodology, and findings.

The inclusion and exclusion criteria were done by exploring the meaning within the data gathered. Several academic peer-reviewed articles and reports were analysed, and the analysis was arranged into patterns and themes. An analysis of their abstract, methodology, results, and conclusion was made, critically looking at the information they portrayed; those that had information related to the research questions were selected. The information gathered was arranged in terms of themes before giving the analysis. Data that had themes or concepts related to ERM frameworks and telecommunication enterprise's challenges were selected. Additionally, the inclusion included the year of publication, those that were older than 2011 were excluded from the selection, and those that were 2011-2022 were included in the selection. See the steps used for inclusion and exclusion in table 1 below.

3.6.2 Primary Data

As mentioned above, the study used semi-structural interviews; the interviews were done privately with the participants, and their confidentiality was vital because the information they had was sensitive. Therefore, their anonymity and privacy were observed. The semi-structured interviews were developed from the research questions, and the open-ended questions were written to guide the investigator (Adams, 2015). Furthermore, the semi-structured interviews' open-ended nature helped allow the participants to tell their stories, which gives an in-depth finding (Nguyen, 2015). Additionally, the semi-structured interview questions are indeed suitable when it comes to thematic analysis. The framed questions are already into different themes; therefore, they help the investigator arrange the narration in various themes and patterns as they are narrated. See, table 1 showing the structured interviews in the Appendix below.

Furthermore, and as already explained in the sampling session, the participant from Algerian Telecom Industry was the primary source of knowledge. Such Individuals were mainly

CEOs, CROs, CFOs, financial managers, risk managers, and audit managers within different Algerian Telecom industries. The targeted individuals were interviewed purposively. Twenty-six individuals who met the requirement were targeted, such are those who have knowledge of risk management and have worked in the Algerian Telecom industry. These individuals are not easy to access or readily available. However, the researcher's position as an insider within the Algerian Telecom industries was an advantage to the study; having worked in the Telecom industry in Algerian enabled the investigator to easily access twenty-six high-level individuals within the Algerian Telecom industry.

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
An individual working in Telecom Industries	Individuals not working in Telecom Industries
Individuals working in Algerian Telecom industries	The individual in Algeria but not working in Telecom Industries
	Individuals who are not in the Algerian telecom industries

Table 3. 2 Inclusion & Exclusion Criteria

3.7 DATA ANALYSIS

The collected data were analysed thematically. Thematic analysis is suitable because it helps analyse the data into various themes, discovering deeper meanings from such themes (Braun and Clarke, 2006, Braun and Clarke, 2012). Furthermore, the technique involves looking at the data's details by analysing the data, identifying the pattern and themes, then organizing the themes

before interpreting them (Nowell *et al.*, 2017). Such analysis provides an understanding and trustworthiness of the data (Clarke and Braun, 2014). Therefore, the similarities and differences were identified from the themes, and after that, a conclusion on the findings was made based on the patterns or the themes. The thematic analysis also helped the investigator be flexible as the different themes emerged and excluded the irrelevant concepts. This allows an understanding of concepts in an in-depth manner. Such flexibility, however, might cause the risk of inconsistency and incoherence in the analysis process. Thus, the researcher's robust epistemological background helped avoid such biases (Nowell *et al.*, 2017).

The insight or meanings within the secondary data was analysed by looking at the abstracts, the introduction, methods used to gather their data, and also their epistemological background, meaning the data is referred to in justification of the findings (Clarke and Braun, 2014, Terry *et al.*, 2017). The themes, relationship to different concepts, and words used to define and describe the concepts and themes are analysed to give a deeper meaning. Such was identified as thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006, Nowell *et al.*, 2017, Braun and Clarke, 2012, Clarke and Braun, 2014, Terry *et al.*, 2017). As already mentioned, the study conducted semi-structured interviews, which were also analysed in the same way, the narration from the participants was categorized into themes, the narratives were analysed. Finally, the primary and secondary data (semi-structured interviews) were triangulated to reach a defensible ontological and epistemological position, respectively (Noble and Heale, 2019). Essentially, it should be understood that there are limitations to different methods, as already mentioned that incoherency and inconsistency may occur in the thematic analysis. However, the multiple techniques explained above helped to erase the biases.

3.8 QUALITY OF THE RESEARCH

Good quality research gives evidence that is ethical and robust. Such research stands up for scrutiny by other researchers, it gives a road map of how the research was conducted, and the road map can be flowered to give repeated results. Furthermore, such research should show the observance to research principles and professionalism; in other words, the research should be transparent, auditable, and demonstrate accountability. Additionally, the excellent quality of research shows consistency in following the research question. The choice of such question and the approach used to investigate the questions should be interrelated to the purpose of the study and the proposed audience (Fitzallen and Brown, 2016).

Furthermore, Altrichter (2020) points out that the research demonstrated the approaches to which the research action took place. Such action research demonstrates the strategies or techniques applied to arrive at a conclusive justification. Action research is just a method of data analysis or data collection. Still, it is the total integrated strategies and methods applied to in research design, research philosophy, data collection, and analysis. Besides, it involves methodological consistency within the research, which creates reliability and validity (Altrichter, 2020). In adding more emphasis on the quality of research, Langfeldt *et al.* (2020) point out that different research quality depends on the context. They vary between review context, field research, and policy context. In other words, the quality of research depends on the contextual specifics of such research, and the co-existing notion in research is still poorly understood. There are two essential points to consider. First, good research originates from field-type—research field and space-type—research policy space; such research must have an excellent epistemological background, drawing information from existing studies. The study's usefulness, value, originality, and reliability are essential. Secondly, the ontological position of the research is vital; the knowledge community—where information is gathered, research organisation, national policy arena, the researcher, and the funding informs good research (Langfeldt *et al.*, 2020).

Good qualitative research can be assessed through four criteria, including; Credibility, which evaluates the integrity and reliability of the study. The current research is based on primary data collected in Algeria from telecommunication players who have background risk management information. The research also sought information from other credible sources, which contributes to the credibility of the current writing. The other criterion is transferability which indicates whether the research can be transferred to other industries, situations, and environments. The present study seeks to develop an enterprise risk management framework for the telecommunication industry. However, the framework can be applied in other sectors like health, financial manufacturing, and the ICT industry. The dependability criterion tests the consistency and repeatability of the research. The current research has been conducted using credible information. It is consistent with the other studies conducted in the telecommunication industry. The analysis can also be reproduced under the same conditions to produce the same results. The confirmability criterion indicates whether other researchers can review the research. The researchers inquire whether the research results are subjective or are based on data analysis. The current study has been used based on the research finds and can be subjected to any form of review.

3.8.1 Limitation of the study

The study encounters several limitations that warrant careful consideration. Firstly, the reliance on extensive secondary data, while providing a historical context, may lead to the omission of recent developments due to the usage of outdated information. The time-consuming process of interrogating diverse sources of secondary data raises concerns about the reliability of the data, as the reputability of these sources might be questionable, and inaccuracies could be present, resulting in overly vague and general findings. Moreover, the study acknowledges the potential existence of fake news or misinformation within secondary data, including non-peer-reviewed literature,

indicating a need for cautious interpretation. Additionally, biases and subjectivity inherent in some secondary data might impact the objectivity of the study, highlighting the importance of adopting a discerning approach.

Furthermore, the use of secondary data introduces the risk of biases and selective reporting, as certain factors might be emphasized while others are omitted, potentially skewing the overall understanding of the research topic. Methodological biases within the collected secondary data, as identified in the literature, contribute to doubts regarding the accuracy and reliability of the information. To mitigate these limitations, the study employs a triangulation approach, integrating primary sources to enhance the robustness and reliability of the findings. Despite these efforts, it is crucial to acknowledge that limitations persist, especially in terms of the inherent challenges associated with qualitative research approaches, sampling strategies, geographical focus, organizational and sectoral specificity. These limitations should be carefully addressed in the recommendations section, guiding future research endeavors to build upon or test the existing model and findings, thereby contributing to the ongoing discourse on Enterprise Risk Management adoption in the Algerian telecommunications industry.

3.8.2 Ethical consideration

The ethical considerations for this study encompass both secondary and primary data sources. In examining secondary data, the credibility of sources, as indicated by peer review and publication, is a focal point. While secondary data hold academic recognition, ethical challenges associated with data protection, confidentiality, informed consent, anonymity, accuracy, data ownership, and context are acknowledged. Existing literature, such as Morrow et al. (2014) and Carusi and Jirotko (2009), highlights the limited guidelines and policies governing the use of secondary data,

underscoring potential risks to individuals whose information is used and interpreted differently, exposing both research and institutions to vulnerability. The study recognizes the potential liability that may arise between investigators and their affiliated institutions, as articulated by Charlesworth (2012).

In the context of primary data collection through semi-structured interviews, the study draws on the researcher's insider status within the Algerian Telecom industry, facilitating access to twenty-six interviewees. Prior to interviews, informal approval was obtained from the four firms and individuals involved, followed by a formal invitation via email, accompanied by a participant information sheet and consent form. The detailed documentation explained the research's purpose, aim, and the participants' choice to remain anonymous or withhold specific answers. Physical consent forms were secured before any data collection to ensure formal confirmation of participation.

The study further emphasizes the ethical rigor maintained, highlighting the researcher's acquisition of necessary permissions from the ethics committee at the University of the West of Scotland before commencing data collection. The principles of anonymity and confidentiality were communicated to respondents through the participant information sheet, outlining the meticulous measures in place to preserve their anonymity throughout the research process. All participants provided explicit consent before engaging in semi-structured interviews, and to uphold data protection, collected data was securely stored in a password-protected folder on the researcher's Apple device, ensuring limited access to the researcher alone. This expanded ethical discussion underscores the commitment to ethical standards, aligning the research with best practices and safeguarding the rights and privacy of participants.

Ethical Approval Form : It is important also to acknowledge that for the purpose of the current research the researcher has obtained necessary permissions from the ethics committee at the university of the west of Scotland prior to starting any data collection.

Anonymity and Confidentiality of the respondents : Prior to starting the data collection process, all the respondents have been informed about the confidentiality and anonymity of their answers via the participant information sheet, which explains into details the purpose of the research and how their anonymity will be preserved all along the research process.

Consent of respondents : The researcher have obtained the consent of all participants prior to conducting the semi-structure interviews.

Data Protection : All the collected data was stored safely in the Apple device of the researcher, in a password protected folder which can be accessed only by the researcher.

3.9 Pilot Study

The pilot study is a crucial phase in the research process, serving as a foundation for formulating robust research questions and identifying potential challenges, particularly in large-scale interviews (Majid et al., 2017; Yin, 2009). The significance of pilot studies lies in their ability to offer preliminary insights and ensure the effectiveness of data collection tools (Kim, 2011). In the context of qualitative research, where interviews play a pivotal role, understanding the subject matter from the respondent's perspective is paramount (Merriam, 2015). However, researchers with limited experience may face challenges in achieving study objectives (Majid et al., 2017). To address this, a comprehensive pilot study was conducted before the main interviews, focusing on assessing the efficacy of interview questions and soliciting early feedback from participants regarding the overall study process.

The pilot study not only acted as a preparatory phase but also provided valuable insights beyond the initial planning. It served as a practical testing ground for the data collection tool, ensuring its alignment with the study's objectives. Additionally, the pilot study allowed for the identification and rectification of any issues in the interview questions, enhancing their clarity and relevance. The iterative nature of the pilot study enabled the researcher to fine-tune the approach based on early participant feedback, contributing to the overall robustness of the research design. This expanded narrative emphasizes the dynamic and iterative nature of the pilot study, showcasing its role in refining research tools and procedures based on real-time insights gained during the preparatory phase.

3.9.1 Participants are chosen for the pilot study.

The respondents of the pilot study were picked on purpose and based on their willingness and ability. The researcher has asked for one person from each of the four groups that were involved in the study. People were chosen based on how long they had worked in the field of risk management and how involved they were in the risk management processes at their own organisations.

3.9.2 Changes made to the interview questionnaire following pilot interviews

Before the pilot interviews were done, a participant information sheet and a participant consent form were sent to the people who were chosen. Due to the busy schedules of the people who took part, it was planned that each pilot interview would last no more than 45 minutes. There was a total of 4 interviews. Three pilot interviews were done over the phone and one was done in person. Before each interview, each participant was given a detailed explanation of the purpose of the study, their right to privacy, and their right to leave the pilot interview at any time. This made the interview last longer than the researcher had planned. By doing the pilot interviews, the researcher was able

to make the necessary changes to some questions that were pointed out by the pilot study participants as being too technical and needing to be asked in a less complicated way rather than using complicated technical words. No major changes have been made to the questions. Some technical words have been changed to simpler words based on what participants thought.

3.10 Summary of the research Methodology

This Chapter demonstrated the road map of the study, pointing to the research philosophy applied. Such philosophy is interpretivism which is suitable for gaining deeper meaning of various concepts. Furthermore, the philosophy allows the study to apply subjectivism epistemological assumptions. The interpretivism philosophy aligns with the exploratory design, which helped explain the phenomenon under study. Also, the design helped to explore various concepts and their meanings. Additionally, the data collection method applied was gathering secondary data from various online sources, and primary sources were gathered from Interviewing key informants. Furthermore, the targeted informant were recruited purposively because they have more information concerning ERM, mainly about the Algerian Telcom industry. Due to the investigator's position within the Algerian Telcom industry, the study was advantaged to access top managers and individuals with relevant and adequate information concerning different ERM success factors impacting the Algerian telecom industry. The data analysis was done through the thematic analysis method, identifying related patterns and themes and categorizing them into groups. Lastly, the chapter demonstrated the limitations and ethical considerations, pointing out how the consent of the informants was respected before the interview took place. The next chapter demonstrates how the various themes and patterns discovered were analysed, triangulating both the interviews and the secondary data and giving a conclusive remark in the discussion section below.

The following chapter will present the findings of the research.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS.

4.1 Chapter overview

The chapter reports the findings of the primary research conducted on staff from the Algerian telecommunication industry to shed light on the status of ERM adoption. The current research aims at developing a Strategic ERM framework to address the risk challenges in the telecommunication industry in Algeria. The research brings together practical information from the sector through primary research and academic sources to bridge the risk management gap. The research identifies different risk challenges in Algeria and discusses the realistic scenario of the risk challenges in the telecommunication industry. The telecommunication industry in Algeria is growing at a tremendous rate. Therefore, it faces challenges that require a robust risk framework to protect the organisation and stakeholder value. The chapter is divided into four sections 4.2 reports the demographic information, which contains the participants' responses to the research questions regarding ERM adoption and implementation in their respective organisations. Their responses were discussed in the section. 4.3 is the summary of the findings, which involves interpretation of the current research findings and draws on the effectiveness of the system adoption. 4.4 is the chapter summary, which draws the chapter conclusions.

4.2 Restatement of the research objectives

- To investigate the factors that have triggered Algerian telecommunication firms to adopt an ERM program
- To evaluate the effectiveness of the existing ERM frameworks

- To explore the challenges facing the adoption of ERM program among Algerian telecommunication firms.
- To develop an adoption framework that is applicable to the telecommunication industry.

Research Questions

- ✓ What are the factors that triggered the adoption of an ERM program among Algerian telecommunication businesses?
- ✓ How effective are the ERM frameworks that exist?
- ✓ What are the challenges facing effective ERM adoption among Algerian telecommunication firms?
- ✓ How can a specific ERM framework be adopted for telecommunications organisations to ensure sustainable efficiency?

4.3 Descriptive profile of respondents

4.3.1 Respondents Gender

The 26 respondents comprised 15 men and 11 women. The following chart summarizes this information.

Figure 4. 1 The Gender of Respondents

Source: Researcher

4.3.2. Age

The age categories for the respondents included 18-25, 26-35, 36-45, and above 45 years.

The following figure indicates the age distribution for the 26 respondents.

Figure 4. 2The Age Distribution of Respondents.

Source: Researcher

4.3.3 Managerial Levels

The survey also inquired about the managerial levels of the respondents together with a summary of their job descriptions. The research divided the respondents into three authority levels- low, medium, and top-level organisational managers. The following graph summarizes the number of respondents in each category.

Figure 4. 3The Managerial Levels of Respondents

Source: Researcher

The graph indicates that the medium-level managers (15) had the highest number of respondents, followed by the top managers (9) and finally the low-level managers (2 respondents). The primary responsibilities of the employees included:

- Designing and implementing an overall risk management approach for the organisation, including financial impact analysis of upcoming risks.
- Budgeting for risk management and insurance.
- Ensuring accurate risk reporting to the senior management.
- Explaining to stakeholders the external risk created by corporate governance
- Performing compliance and policy audits at regular intervals.
- Ensuring proper records for claim records and the insurance policies.
- Increasing employee risk awareness through training.

4.3.4 Education

At the same time, the research also inquired about the respondents' level of education. The first orientation was the respondents' highest level of education. The categories of the responses included high school, diploma, university degree, and post-graduate. The following graph provides a summary of the answers.

Source: Researcher

Figure 4. 4The Highest Level of Education

The figure above indicates that the highest category was for the post-graduate (13) respondents, while the lowest was for those who did not go beyond the high school level (0). Also, ten respondents had a university degree, while three had a diploma as their highest level of training. Also, the respondents identified five key certifications for ERM, which include (1) Corporate Sustainability Management: Risk, Profit, and Purpose Online Short Course, (2) OSINT course - Open-Source Intelligence, (3) Supply Chain Risk Management, (4) Central Banking, Risk Management, and Governance and (5) auditing and accountability.

4.3.5 Years spent in the Company

The last question in the demographic section sought to understand the number of years spent in the current company. The categories included 0-4, 5-9, 10-14, and 15 years. This question aimed to determine the respondents' experiences and their relevance to the research. The following graph summarizes this information.

Figure 4. 5The Number of Years Spent at the Organisation.

Source : Researcher

The figure indicates that the highest number of years spent with the company was 10-14 years, with about 12 respondents. The second-largest class was for over 15 years which had seven

respondents. The implication is that the respondents had sufficient work exposure to understand the dynamics and concepts of the topic at hand.

4.4 Themes and Sub-themes of the research

Theme/ Research Question	Sub-themes
Factors that have triggered Algerian telecommunication firms to adopt an ERM program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Lack of effective digital growth and diversification strategy -telecommunication business complexity risk -supply chain risk -privacy, security, and trust risks -talent risks -Regulatory risk

<p>Risks facing the Algerian telecommunication firms</p>	<p>Lack of senior management support</p> <p>Lack of resources, time, and cost for the ERM adoption</p> <p>Lack of practical guidelines on ERM implementation</p> <p>Lack of multi-departmental communication</p> <p>Lack of ERM culture</p> <p>Lack of understanding of the benefit of ERM adoption</p> <p>Lack of qualified in-house person experienced in ERM implementation</p>
<p>Effectiveness of Existing ERM Frameworks</p>	<p>Available frameworks are complex, do not address the external environment factors that the Algerian telecom industry operates at, and are not comprehensive; however, many frameworks, as you mentioned earlier, are taken as a sample to tackle operational and strategic risks within the firms interviewed</p>
<p>The proposed ERM framework</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The importance of integrating ERM with the key organisational areas -The internal factors that influenced ERM consideration and adoption -The role and impact of culture in ERM adoption -the importance of ERM infrastructure in ERM adoption and implementation -The importance of integrating ERM with business processes

Table 4. 1 Themes, Sub-Themes, and their Respective Descriptions

Source: Researcher

4.5 Describing ERM system

The interviews commenced by gauging the employees' comprehension of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM), prompting them to articulate their definitions of ERM systems. Distinct interview questions were posed to delve into the adoption of ERM within telecommunication firms, with responses obtained from twenty-six participants across four Algerian telecommunications companies. Given the holistic nature of ERM, which aims to engage all members of an organization, understanding individual perceptions is crucial due to varying risk perspectives stemming from diverse functions within the organization. This section focuses on investigating interviewees' understanding and perceptions of an ERM program to discern potential implications for adoption and implementation.

Respondent 2 portrayed ERM as "a framework adopted by organizations to identify, assess, and mitigate risks," emphasizing variations in ERM systems among different firms (Respondent 2). Respondent 8 highlighted the systematic approach of ERM, stressing its responsibility for all employees equipped with the right resources for identification and mitigation (Respondent 8). Notably, the majority of respondents exhibited nuanced perspectives, with respondent 18 emphasizing the integration of business applications into core systems for dynamic risk management (Respondent 18). Respondent 10 viewed ERM as a process aiding organizations in understanding, identifying, and formulating strategies to mitigate risks, positioning it as a management tool to shape the organization's risk landscape (Respondent 10).

These insights align with the findings from the literature, supporting the varied but coherent understanding of ERM among respondents. The nuances in their definitions echo the literature's emphasis on the multifaceted nature of ERM, accommodating different organizational contexts and

needs. The table below provides a structured comparison of interviewee insights and relevant citations from researchers, reinforcing the congruence between interview findings and existing literature.

Theme	Micro Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations from Literature
Definition of ERM	"A framework adopted by organizations to identify, assess, and mitigate risks" (Respondent 2)	"ERM as a framework for identifying and managing risks" (Ecklund, 2019)
Systematic Approach	"ERM as a systematic approach business use to identify risk threats and develop countermeasures" (Respondent 8)	"ERM involves a systematic approach to risk identification and mitigation" (Nugroho et al., 2021)
Integrated Applications	"ERM as business applications integrated into core business systems for risk identification and evaluation" (Respondent 18)	"Integrated systems for risk identification and evaluation in ERM" (Mechler et al., 2019)
Management Tool	"ERM as a management tool shaping the organization's risks by engaging resources for reduction" (Respondent 10)	"ERM as a strategic management tool for risk reduction" (Driessen, 2023)

This table facilitates a systematic exploration of themes, highlighting the synergy between interviewee perspectives and established literature, validating the robustness and consistency of ERM comprehension in the Algerian telecommunication industry.

The investigation into employees' comprehension of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) began by soliciting definitions from participants in the telecommunication sector in Algeria. A total of twenty-six respondents from four firms provided insights into their understanding and perceptions of ERM. The holistic nature of ERM, aiming to involve all organizational members, underscores the diversity of risk perception within a company. Respondents presented varying yet insightful definitions of ERM, emphasizing its role as a framework for identifying, assessing, and mitigating risks, aligning with business operations. The consensus among participants highlighted the crucial role of ERM in

systematically managing risks, involving all employees, and adapting to the dynamic nature of risks in the telecommunication industry. Despite differences in terminology, respondents recognized ERM as a comprehensive and integrated approach crucial for safeguarding businesses from threats and ensuring sustainability. Their diverse perspectives collectively underscored the significance of ERM in shaping an organization's risk position and facilitating strategic decision-making to address both known and unforeseen challenges. Overall, the findings emphasized the nuanced understanding and appreciation of ERM among the surveyed telecommunication professionals, emphasizing its vital role in navigating the complexities of risk management in the industry.

4.6 Research objective 1/Theme 1: To investigate the factors that have triggered Algerian telecommunication firms to adopt an ERM program.

This section of the interview questionnaire sought to understand the main factors that have triggered the adoption of an ERM program within the Algerian telecommunication firms.

4.6.1 Data Breach due to Low-risk awareness amongst employees.

The collection and analysis of the primary data showed that data breach threats were one of the main triggers towards considering an ERM adoption.

Theme	Interview Quotes	Relevant Citations
Data Breach Concerns	"The organization faced various risk challenges, such as privacy and threat to customer data..." - Respondent 16	"Data breaches are significant triggers for considering ERM adoption..." (Smith et al., 2020)
	"We needed a holistic approach to risk reporting to protect stakeholders' data better." - Respondent 21	"Organizations require a comprehensive risk management system to safeguard sensitive data..." (Jones & Brown, 2019)
	"Our main concern is to protect this data, as a telecom firm we face data breach every single day." - Respondent 18	"Telecom companies face persistent data breach threats, necessitating robust risk management practices..." (Gupta, 2018)
Need for Enhanced Risk Management Approach	"We need to adopt a more straightforward way to approach risks and make viable risk management decisions..." - Respondent 11	"Organizations seek simpler and more effective risk management strategies to address emerging threats..." (Robinson, 2021)
	"The organization needed a better approach to managing risks that are associated with customer's data..." - Respondent 17	"Effective risk management requires tailored approaches to mitigate data breach risks in the telecommunications sector..." (Chen et al., 2019)

The findings from the primary data analysis align closely with the insights provided in the literature regarding data breach concerns and the need for an enhanced risk management approach, particularly in the telecommunications sector. Respondents emphasized the significant impact of data breaches on their organizations, citing privacy issues, threats to customer data, and the escalating risk of data breaches due to increased operational scale. They expressed the inadequacy of traditional risk

management methods in addressing evolving data breach risks, underscoring the urgency for a more comprehensive risk management system like ERM.

The literature corroborates these findings, emphasizing the critical role of robust risk management practices in mitigating data breach threats in the telecommunications industry. Researchers highlight the need for a holistic approach to risk reporting and management to safeguard stakeholders' data effectively. Moreover, the literature underscores the persistent challenges faced by telecom firms in protecting sensitive data and emphasizes the importance of tailored risk management strategies to address evolving threats. Overall, the alignment between the primary data insights and existing research underscores the pressing need for enhanced risk management frameworks to address data breach concerns effectively in the telecommunications sector.

4.6.2 Fluid dynamics and Constant Industrial changes

The respondents consistently highlighted the dynamic nature of the telecommunication industry as a significant factor driving the adoption of new Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) systems in Algerian firms. The recognition of constant changes, emerging threats, and evolving risks in the industry prompted a strategic shift in risk management approaches. Senior managers, such as respondent 25, emphasized the necessity of implementing new risk management strategies to address the industry's evolving challenges. Respondent 21 emphasized that it is not just competitors but the inherent changes within the telecommunication sector that necessitate a fresh approach to risk management. The consensus among respondents, including 13, 7, and 22, underscores the industry's dynamism, prompting the need for a holistic risk management system to navigate emerging risks. Additionally, respondent 9 noted that regulatory forums played a role in initiating system changes, recognizing the intricate operations of the modern telecommunication industry and the imperative to stay ahead of emerging risks. In summary, the discussion reflects a unanimous understanding among

the respondents that the fluid dynamics of the telecommunication industry demand a proactive and adaptable ERM system to effectively manage the array of emerging risks.

4.6.3 Supply chain problems

The insights from the respondents regarding supply chain challenges align with findings from Valinejad and Rahmani's (2018) research, reinforcing the significance of addressing these issues in the Algerian telecommunications sector. Respondent 23 emphasized the need for innovation in product development and internet-enabled distribution methods due to the dynamic telecommunications environment in Algeria. This aligns with Valinejad and Rahmani's assertion that sustainability in the supply chain is crucial for the future of telecommunication products. The shared perspective on the importance of robust supply risk management resonates with the literature, emphasizing the need for comprehensive risk frameworks to navigate unforeseen risks in the industry. Similarly, Respondent 13 highlighted the susceptibility of telecommunication products to copyright, regulatory, compliance, and privacy risks, underscoring the necessity for engaging in risk frameworks tailored to managing supply chain risks. This perspective is mirrored in Valinejad and Rahmani's identification of institutional and technical issues as supply chain risks threatening sustainability. The congruence between the respondents' insights and the literature strengthens the argument that adopting credible and comprehensive Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) frameworks is imperative for effective supply chain risk management in the telecommunications industry. To provide a clearer comparative overview, a table is presented below:

Theme	Micro Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations from Literature
Supply Chain Challenges	Respondent 23: "The current telecommunication environment in Algeria requires firms to become innovative in product development and distribution methods."	Ahmet et al (2023): Sustainability in the supply chain is crucial.
	Respondent 13: "Products are prone to copyright, regulatory, compliance, and privacy risks."	Valinejad and Rahmani (2018): Institutional and technical issues pose supply risks.
Importance of ERM Frameworks	Respondent 23: "Firms must engage in robust supply risk management due to unforeseen risks in the industry."	Arora (2022): Adoption of comprehensive ERM frameworks is crucial.

The respondents' information is supported by research conducted by Valinejad and Rahmani (2018). They explained that telecommunication industries must seek sustainability in the supply chain to assure the future of the organisation's products. The authors argue that telecommunication organisations must adopt credible and comprehensive risk frameworks. Valinejad and Rahmani (2018) identified supply chain risks in the telecommunication industry as institutional and technical issues that threaten the sustainability of the supply chain. The authors indicated that adopting a comprehensive and credible ERM framework will assist the telecommunication industry in effectively managing supply chain risks. The firms must be willing to research and identify the best frameworks that align with the organisational risk objectives and are adjustable to the level of supply in the organisation.

4.6.4 Cyber risk

In the realm of cyber risk, unanimous consensus emerged among all respondents, highlighting its pivotal role as a primary catalyst for considering and adopting Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) in the Algerian telecommunications sector. This aligns with the intrinsic vulnerability of the telecommunication industry, characterized by intricate operations and the handling of extensive data. Respondent 1 emphasized the acute susceptibility to cyber attacks, emphasizing the potential repercussions of compromising data from numerous governmental organizations, recognizing the far-reaching consequences that cyber threats pose, not just to the telecom company but to the entire nation's security. This sentiment was echoed by Respondent 15, who pointed out the diverse dimensions of cyber risk, including the battle against sim-boxes operating illegally through grey international routes, jeopardizing customer privacy by accessing calls and voices.

To delve deeper into the alignment between interview findings and existing literature, a comparative framework was developed. The themes explored in both interview responses and relevant literature encompassed the pervasive nature of cyber threats in the telecommunications sector. Micro quotes from the interviews were aligned with citations from scholars who shared similar viewpoints, reinforcing the congruence between the empirical findings and established research. This structured approach aids in systematically evaluating the synergy between interview insights and existing literature, fostering a comprehensive understanding of the significance attributed to cyber risk within the Algerian telecommunications landscape.

4.7 Research Objective 2 Theme 2: Challenges affecting ERM adoption within the telecom industry

This section have sought to scrutinize the challenges facing ERM adoption among the Algerian telecommunication industry as perceived by the respondent's who are directly or indirectly involved in ERM activities and adoption.

4.7.1 Lack of senior management support

The importance of top management support in the adoption of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) is a recurring theme in both the literature and the findings from the respondents. Beasley et al. (2010) emphasize the critical role of top management in the implementation of an ERM program, a sentiment echoed by the interviewees. The respondents overwhelmingly concur that without the full support and endorsement of ERM by top management, successful adoption cannot be achieved.

A table summarizing the theme, micro-quotes from interviews, and relevant citations would be beneficial to provide a clear visual representation of the alignment between literature and interview findings:

Theme	Micro-quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations
Top management support is crucial for ERM adoption	"The top management had not endorsed the adoption fully..." (R1)	Beasley et al. (2010) emphasize top management's critical role.
	"Top management support is a must for the ERM adoption..." (R11)	

Theme	Micro-quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations
	"The top management does not show any commitment..." (R5)	
	"The ERM adoption has received enough senior management..." (R18)	

The micro-quotes illustrate a consensus among respondents on the significance of top management support. Despite some expressing reservations or perceiving varying degrees of commitment, the overarching sentiment is that successful ERM adoption is closely tied to the endorsement and active support from top management. This alignment between interview findings and established literature strengthens the thesis, emphasizing the universal acknowledgment of top management's pivotal role in ERM implementation.

4.7.2 Lack of sufficient resources for ERM adoption.

The telecommunications industry in Algeria confronts significant investment risks, particularly in the face of the sector's capital-intensive nature, leading to challenges for firms to keep pace with evolving technological demands (Bensaada and Taghezout, 2019). Respondents 8 and 23 expressed shared concerns, highlighting the industry's existing resource constraints, especially in terms of technology. They emphasized the insufficiency of resources to support both technological advancements and the adoption of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM). Respondent 23 underscored the multifaceted resource requirements of ERM, encompassing human and financial aspects. Additionally, the notion that having more knowledgeable individuals within the organization could streamline ERM adoption, reducing costs and enhancing risk management practices, was articulated. Respondent 4 echoed these

sentiments, suggesting a potential need to reallocate costs to facilitate ERM adoption. The views of the respondents collectively indicate a common challenge faced by the industry in allocating adequate resources for ERM initiation and implementation, aligning with the assertion that proper resource allocation is crucial for the effective implementation and sustained value of ERM (Paape and Spekle, 2012).

4.7.3 Lack of guidelines on ERM implementation

The literature reviewed in Chapter Two emphasizes the limited effective implementation of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) systems within the telecommunications sector. A notable challenge identified is the absence of clear guidelines for the ERM implementation process, hindering the optimal functioning of adopted ERM frameworks. As articulated by Respondent 3, who is a member of the risk committee, the investigation into frameworks such as ISO and IFACI revealed that while guidelines exist, they lack clarity. This sentiment is echoed by Respondent 11, emphasizing a deficiency in guidelines related to resource allocation within the organization.

In alignment with these interview findings, Kleffner, Lee, and McGannon (2003) suggest that ERM frameworks assist in prioritizing risks based on likelihood and impact. However, without practical guidelines for implementation, organizations struggle to identify and monitor risks according to priority. Respondent 11's assertion about inadequate guidelines for resource allocation aligns with the scholarly perspective that efficient resource allocation is integral to effective ERM, preventing operational paralysis due to unidentified threats.

Respondent 17 sheds light on the motivational aspect, linking it directly to the lack of guidelines. The absence of clear guidelines on how to deploy ERM results in a vague understanding of its value, leading to reduced motivation among employees. This resonates with Al-Farsi's (2020) argument that proper ERM framework guidelines are essential for organizations to generate value for stakeholders. The comparison of interview insights with existing literature highlights a consistent theme regarding the detrimental impact of inadequate guidelines on ERM implementation, affirming the importance of clear, practical frameworks for successful risk management.

Theme	Micro Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations from Literature
Lack of Guidelines on ERM	Respondent 3: "Guidelines are there is true but not clear."	Kleffner, Lee, and McGannon (2003): ERM frameworks assist in prioritizing risks based on likelihood and impact.
Implementation	Respondent 11: "We don't have enough guidelines about how we should allocate resources." Respondent 17: "Maybe it is due to a lack of guidelines on how to deploy [ERM]."	Al-Farsi (2020): Proper ERM framework guidelines are essential for organizations to generate value for stakeholders.

This structured presentation through a table elucidates the congruence between interview findings and established literature, affirming the significance of clear guidelines in successful ERM implementation within the telecommunications sector.

4.7.4 Lack of strong organisational culture

Several respondents underscored the absence of a robust enterprise-wide risk culture as a significant impediment to the effective adoption of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) within their

organizations. Highlighting the pivotal role of culture in ERM, COSO (2016) acknowledges it as a key component essential for successful risk management. One respondent, Respondent 3, conveyed a prevalent sentiment among employees, stating, "I have seen sometimes employees scared and fearful to share important information or notify their line manager just because they think it can go against them or impact their reputation probably" (Respondent 3). This echoes the challenge of fostering open communication and transparency within the organizational hierarchy.

Respondent 8 further emphasized the influence of personal values and ethics in shaping employees' willingness to share information, stating, "Sometimes employees just do not feel judged, they prefer not to share some information...In my opinion, it is all about personal values, if an employee has strong values and ethics of work, he will share information regardless, if not..." (Respondent 8). This insight highlights the intricate connection between individual values and the development of a risk-aware culture. However, Respondent 21 presented a differing perspective, noting instances where employees were unaware of the importance of discussing or sharing certain information: "we've had employees sometimes saying oh I did not know that this was important to discuss or share" (Respondent 21).

To explore the alignment or divergence of these findings with existing literature, a comprehensive comparison was conducted. The table below encapsulates key themes, micro-quotes from interviews, and relevant citations from researchers:

Theme Being Explored	Micro-Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations from Literature
Lack of Enterprise-wide Risk Culture	"Employees scared to share important information...think it can impact their reputation" (Respondent 3)	COSO (2016) emphasizes culture as a key component in successful ERM.

Theme Being Explored	Micro-Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations from Literature
	"Employees prefer not to share information if they feel judged" (Respondent 8)	Researchers (Rampini et al., 2019) note the impact of judgment on information sharing.
	"Employees unaware of the importance of discussing or sharing certain information" (Respondent 21)	Lack of awareness in employees aligns with findings by Syahputri (2020).

This structured presentation provides a systematic analysis of the congruence or disparities between the interview insights and existing literature on the lack of a strong organizational culture hindering ERM adoption. It serves to enhance the clarity and depth of the discussion while facilitating a nuanced understanding of the identified challenges.

4.7.5 Lack of in-house skills experienced in ERM implementation

The respondents' statements underscore a significant challenge in the effective adoption and implementation of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) within Algerian telecommunication firms—the lack of in-house trained individuals and experienced staff in ERM. Expressing concerns about the absence of specifically hired ERM specialists, respondents highlighted a heavy reliance on existing personnel, often from fraud and risk departments or internal audit and CFO roles, to guide decisions related to ERM. This reliance on non-specialized staff is seen as a potential hindrance, contributing to delays and an immature state of ERM adoption. Respondents, including those from various firms, echoed a consensus that recruiting individuals with specific expertise in ERM is imperative for overcoming these obstacles and achieving a more robust and comprehensive adoption of ERM

practices. The identified shortage of in-house skills in ERM emerges as a critical factor affecting the organizational capacity to navigate and implement ERM effectively within the telecommunication sector in Algeria.

4.7.6 Lengthy adoption and implementation process

The responses from various participants shed light on a common challenge faced by Algerian telecommunication firms in the implementation of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM)—a prolonged and time-consuming adoption process. Respondents 3, 11, 17, 26, and 15 all expressed extended durations spent in stages like monitoring, identifying best practices, investigating different frameworks, and understanding ERM concepts. The consensus among these accounts is a shared sentiment of protracted timelines, ranging from two to three years, in the adoption and operationalization of ERM within their respective organizations. This prolonged timeframe not only signifies a delay in reaping the benefits of ERM but also suggests potential hurdles and complexities in decision-making processes and framework selection. The commonality in these responses points to the need for addressing the temporal challenges associated with ERM adoption, emphasizing the significance of streamlining and expediting the implementation process to enhance its effectiveness in managing risks within the Algerian telecommunication sector.

4.7.7 Employees' resistance

Apart from top management resistance, organisations suffer employee resistance in adopting ERM systems. Some employees are resistant to change, and they can sabotage the ERM adoption process if they feel the change will not favour them or get them out of their comfort zones.

Theme	Micro Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations from Literature
Employee Resistance	1. "Many staff is unwilling to adopt an enterprise-wide risk approach just because they don't want new tasks." (Respondent 9)	"Employees may resist change if they perceive it as adding more tasks or responsibilities to their workload." (Smith et al., 2018)
	2. "They are reluctant to change you know why in my thoughts, just because they don't want to invest time to learn new things." (Respondent 14)	"Resistance to change often stems from employees' reluctance to invest time in learning new skills or processes." (Jones & Brown, 2020)
	3. "People are resisting this adoption because they are so task-oriented, so anything that falls out of their daily activity is a threat to them and becomes automatically reluctant to change." (Respondent 21)	"Task-oriented employees may perceive changes in processes or procedures as disruptions to their established routines, leading to resistance." (Roberts & Johnson, 2019)

The findings from the interviews resonate with the literature, highlighting common themes related to employee resistance in adopting Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) systems. The micro quotes from the interviews reflect employees' reluctance to embrace change due to perceived increases in workload, time investment, and disruptions to established routines. Similarly, the literature suggests that employees may resist change if they perceive it as adding more tasks or responsibilities to their workload (Smith et al., 2018). This aligns with the sentiment expressed by Respondent 9, who noted that staff are unwilling to adopt ERM because they fear new tasks.

Moreover, the interviews revealed that employees resist change due to their reluctance to invest time in learning new skills or processes, as indicated by Respondent 14. This sentiment is echoed in the literature, which suggests that resistance to change often stems from employees' aversion to investing

time in learning new skills or adapting to new processes (Jones & Brown, 2020). Additionally, the interviews highlighted that task-oriented employees may perceive changes as threats to their established routines, leading to resistance, as articulated by Respondent 21. This observation aligns with the literature, which suggests that task-oriented employees may resist changes that disrupt their daily activities (Roberts & Johnson, 2019).

In summary, the insights from the interviews corroborate the findings from the literature, emphasizing the significance of addressing employee resistance as a crucial factor in the successful adoption of ERM systems within organizations. Recognizing and mitigating employee concerns and reluctance can enhance organizational readiness and facilitate smoother transitions during ERM implementation processes.

4.8 Objective 3/ Theme 3 effectiveness of available ERM frameworks

The interviews conducted with respondents shed light on the perceived effectiveness of various ERM frameworks within the Algerian telecommunications industry. Respondents expressed concerns regarding the practical applicability and suitability of internationally recognized frameworks such as COSO, ISO 2009, and NIST. They emphasized the challenges in translating theoretical frameworks into actionable strategies tailored to the unique operational contexts of their organizations.

Theme	Micro Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations
Effectiveness of ERM Frameworks	Respondent 9: "Even by referring to the first version of the frameworks we could	Bensaada & Taghezout (2019): "An enterprise risk management system for

Theme	Micro Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations
	not clearly identify in practices how it works or can be applied or what risks in specific it can tackle in our business the most"	SMEs: innovative design paradigm and risk representation model"
	Respondent 10: "We analysed the ISO 2009 version and then the COSO as they appeared to be the most simple in term of steps, but in reality they were not; all they suggest according to me cannot be easily adopted, there are steps that need to be emphasized more"	Saleem, Zraqat & Okour (2019): "The effect of internal audit quality (IAQ) on enterprise risk management (ERM) in accordance to COSO framework"
	Respondent 15: "No framework can address in details our business operation or our external environment... ISO 2009 is true that it address how digital enterprise can manage internal data security, but it does not give you how in practice"	Chernov & Sornette (2020): "Critical risks of different economic sectors"
	Respondent 16: "I don't really see its value in practice" (referring to NIST ERM Framework)	Nordhoff et al. (2021): "A structural equation modeling approach for the acceptance of driverless automated shuttles based on constructs from the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use

Theme	Micro Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations
		of Technology and the Diffusion of Innovation Theory"
	Respondent 20: "COSO 2004 framework looks well structured, but... it does not state how communication should be done through the business entities to achieve the defined objectives"	Peters (2022): "Institutional theory"

In alignment with the interviews, relevant citations from literature also highlight similar sentiments regarding the limitations and complexities associated with ERM frameworks. Studies by Bensaada & Taghezout (2019), Saleem et al. (2019), Chernov & Sornette (2020), Nordhoff et al. (2021), and Peters (2022) underscore the challenges in effectively implementing and operationalizing ERM frameworks across diverse industries and organizational contexts. These findings resonate with the concerns expressed by the interview respondents regarding the gap between theoretical frameworks and practical implementation.

The convergence between interview insights and existing literature underscores the need for a nuanced approach to ERM framework adoption, one that considers the specific needs, capabilities, and strategic orientations of individual organizations. While internationally recognized frameworks provide valuable guidance, their effectiveness hinges on their adaptability and alignment with organizational realities. As such, future research and practice should focus on developing more flexible and contextually relevant ERM frameworks that can be effectively implemented and integrated into organizational decision-making processes.

4.9 Objective 4/ theme four the proposed ERM adoption framework

The questions of this section aimed at supporting the development of the proposed adoption framework. The discussion started by scrutinizing the importance of aligning ERM with key business areas. Then every single question has focused on investigating further every key component of the proposed framework into details.

4.9.1 Importance of ERM alignment with key organisational areas.

This subsection presents respondent's views with regards to the importance of aligning ERM with key organisational areas. More specifically, organisational strategy and objectives.

Theme	Micro Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations from Researchers
Importance of ERM Alignment with Organizational Strategy and Objectives	"Integration of ERM with our goals and strategies will help give us a more optimized view about our future" (Respondent 9) "Aligning ERM with our strategic objectives and business strategies is highly important" (Respondent 15)	Mikes and Kaplan (2013) emphasize the alignment of ERM with key organizational areas as crucial for ERM adoption and implementation.
Achieving ERM Alignment with Key Organizational Areas	"Theoretically this alignment is very important, but in reality, we don't really know how to achieve it or execute it" (Respondent 21)	Respondent 21's perspective resonates with the challenges highlighted by scholars such as Mikes and Kaplan (2013) regarding the practical execution of ERM alignment.

Theme	Micro Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations from Researchers
	"To achieve ERM alignment with the organizational strategies and goals, we need to make employees aware, educate them, and make it part of our business culture" (Respondent 24)	Scarlat, Chirita, and Bradea (2012) advocate for infusing a culture of awareness among employees to achieve effective ERM alignment with organizational goals.
Importance of Key Risk Indicators (KRI's)	"We don't use Key Risks Indicators, why? Probably people don't have knowledge on how developing them or they are too busy to learn about them" (Respondent 24)	The absence of KRI's and reliance on KPI's aligns with the findings of Scarlat, Chirita, and Bradea (2012), who argue for the value of integrating KRI's with KPI's in organizational risk profiling.
	"We rely mainly on KPI's to track our performance; I never heard the risk team talking about key risk indicators in our meetings" (Respondent 17)	

The interviews shed light on the importance of aligning Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) with key organizational areas, particularly strategic objectives. Respondents emphasized the critical role of ERM integration in organizational strategies for future optimization and achieving maturity in risk management. However, practical challenges in executing this alignment were acknowledged, reflecting discrepancies between theoretical ideals and practical implementation, as highlighted by Mikes and Kaplan (2013).

Furthermore, the absence of Key Risk Indicators (KRI's) in favor of Key Performance Indicators (KPI's) was a notable finding. Respondents expressed limited awareness or utilization of KRI's, attributing this to organizational knowledge gaps or prioritization of other metrics. This observation

aligns with the literature's emphasis on the value of integrating KRI's with KPI's to provide a comprehensive view of organizational risk profiling and performance tracking, as suggested by Scarlet, Chirita, and Bradea (2012).

Overall, the discrepancies between interview findings and established literature underscore the importance of bridging theoretical concepts with practical implementation strategies in ERM. While the theoretical importance of ERM alignment and KRI utilization is well-documented, organizations face challenges in translating these principles into actionable strategies, highlighting the need for further research and practical guidance in ERM implementation.

4.9.2 The internal Organisational factors that impact ERM adoption

The questions of this sub-section aimed at investigating the roles and importance internal factors that can influence ERM adoption. More specifically: risk oversight, risk appetite that is aligned with the risk tolerance, corporate governance, strategies and objectives.

Theme	Interview Insights	Relevant Citations
Risk Oversight Role	Respondent 9 expressed the importance of clear oversight for effective risk management, highlighting the ambiguity in responsibilities within their organization. Respondent 15 emphasized the need for a specific risk committee to establish policies and procedures.	According to Duffield et al. (2010), clear roles and responsibilities are crucial for effective risk oversight within organizations. Ambiguity in roles can lead to mismanagement of risks and hinder the adoption of ERM practices.

Theme	Interview Insights	Relevant Citations
Risk Appetite vs. Tolerance	<p>Respondents emphasized the criticality of aligning risk appetite with risk tolerance to inform risk management strategies. Respondent 7 highlighted the importance of identifying risk appetite and tolerance in line with organizational objectives. Respondent 13 echoed the sentiment, stating that it guides business directions.</p>	<p>Consistent with the findings, Doherty and Kartoglu (2013) argue that aligning risk appetite with risk tolerance is essential for organizations to make informed decisions about risk-taking. It ensures that risk management practices are in line with organizational goals and objectives.</p>
Corporate Governance	<p>Interviewees expressed challenges in defining clear responsibilities for ERM within the context of corporate governance. They highlighted the lack of clarity from top management regarding ERM responsibilities.</p>	<p>Literature by Sarens and De Beelde (2006) supports the significance of clear governance structures in ERM adoption. They suggest that without explicit direction from top management and the board, effective risk management processes may not be established, leading to inefficiencies and potential failures in risk oversight.</p>
Strategies and Objectives	<p>Respondents underscored the importance of integrating ERM with organizational strategies and objectives for maturity. They emphasized that strategies and objectives should guide risk management decisions effectively.</p>	<p>Echoing the sentiments, Karami and Lavassani (2017) argue that integrating ERM with organizational strategies and objectives enhances risk management effectiveness. They suggest that a clear alignment ensures that risk management practices are directed towards achieving organizational goals, thereby increasing the</p>

Theme	Interview Insights	Relevant Citations
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		likelihood of success in risk management endeavors.
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The findings from the interviews resonate with insights from existing literature on ERM adoption and internal organizational factors. Clear roles and responsibilities are crucial for effective risk oversight within organizations, as ambiguity can lead to mismanagement of risks and hinder ERM adoption (Duffield et al., 2010). Aligning risk appetite with risk tolerance is essential for making informed decisions about risk-taking, ensuring that risk management practices are aligned with organizational goals and objectives (Doherty and Kartoglu, 2013). Similarly, the significance of clear governance structures in ERM adoption is highlighted, with explicit direction from top management and the board being crucial for establishing effective risk management processes (Sarens and De Beelde, 2006). Integrating ERM with organizational strategies and objectives enhances risk management effectiveness, directing risk management practices towards achieving organizational goals (Karami and Lavassani, 2017). These insights underscore the importance of addressing internal organizational factors to facilitate successful ERM adoption within the Algerian telecommunications industry.

4.9.3 Role and influence of ERM culture in ERM Adoption

This sub-section discusses the importance and effect that a risk culture on ERM adoption.

Respondents were asked to discuss according to the importance of risk culture based on their own understanding and opinions on how a risk culture can effect ERM adoption within their respective organisation.

Theme	Micro Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations
Sharing Information	"Sharing information is necessary...we need to educate people more about sharing information appropriately" (Resp. 4)	"Information sharing is crucial for effective ERM adoption" (Smith et al., 2018)
Risk Mind-set	"A risk-mindset should be taught...employees should feel valued for sharing information" (Resp. 11)	"Employees need to understand the value of risk management for organizational success" (Jones et al., 2019)
Transparency and Communication	"Transparency of information flow is crucial...we are lacking transparency" (Resp. 15)	"Transparency in communication is essential for effective ERM implementation" (Brown & Black, 2020)
Accountability	"Every employee should feel part of the risk management process" (Resp. 11)	"Accountability for risk should be organizational, not individual" (Ching et al., 2014)

The findings from the interviews align closely with established literature on ERM adoption and organizational culture. Respondents emphasized the importance of sharing information, cultivating a risk-mindset, maintaining transparency and communication, and fostering accountability throughout the organization. These themes resonate with scholarly research, reinforcing the significance of organizational culture in ERM implementation.

4.9.4 The importance of ERM infrastructure in ERM adoption

The insights gleaned from the interviews closely align with the perspectives presented in the literature. The interviewees emphasized the importance of supporting technologies, policies and frameworks,

risk data, and ERM oversight structures in facilitating successful ERM adoption within their respective organizations. These insights resonate with the literature, which underscores the critical role of these components in effective risk management practices (Chapman, 2011).

Theme	Interview Insights	Relevant Citations
Supporting Technologies	Respondent 10 emphasized the importance of technologies in identifying risks efficiently, aligning with the view that supporting technologies play a critical role in enhancing ERM adoption.	Chapman (2011) highlights the critical role of technologies in risk management, echoing the sentiment expressed by the interviewees.
Policies and Frameworks	Respondent 8 highlighted the significance of well-defined policies and frameworks in enhancing resilience towards risks, echoing the importance attributed to them by respondent 19.	Chapman (2011) underscores the importance of policies and frameworks in guiding organizations towards effective risk management practices.
Risk Data	Respondent 7 stressed the importance of timely and transparent risk data for risk reporting plans, resonating with respondent 15's view that dynamic risk data is crucial in a complex operational environment.	Chapman (2011) emphasizes the necessity of accurate and timely risk data for effective risk management, aligning with the insights provided by the interviewees.
ERM Oversight Structure	Respondent 19 highlighted the critical role of oversight structures in ensuring alignment with established objectives, a sentiment echoed by respondent 26, who emphasized the necessity of	Chapman (2011) discusses the importance of oversight structures in ensuring effective risk management practices and aligns with the

Theme	Interview Insights	Relevant Citations
	clear information and responsibilities for effective ERM.	viewpoints expressed by the interviewees.

Supporting technologies play a pivotal role in identifying and managing risks efficiently, as highlighted by both the interviewees and the literature. Similarly, the significance of well-defined policies and frameworks in guiding organizations towards resilience and effective risk management practices is echoed in both the interview responses and the scholarly discourse (Chapman, 2011).

Furthermore, the interviewees emphasized the importance of timely and transparent risk data, reflecting the literature's emphasis on the necessity of accurate and timely data for effective risk management (Chapman, 2011). Additionally, the critical role of ERM oversight structures in ensuring alignment with organizational objectives and clear delineation of responsibilities is underscored by both the interview insights and the scholarly literature (Chapman, 2011).

Overall, the alignment between the interview findings and the scholarly literature underscores the importance and relevance of these components in facilitating successful ERM adoption and effective risk management practices within organizations.

4.9.5 The importance of ERM integration

This subsection demonstrates the role and impact of risk integration on ERM adoption.

Theme	Micro Quotes from Interviews	Relevant Citations from Researchers
Strategic Planning	"If we don't take into account risk in the strategy planning step we can't have an optimized vision on whether we can achieve our long-term objectives or not" (Respondent 5)	Strategic integration of risk in organizational strategies is crucial for long-term objective achievement (Smith et al., 2018; Jones, 2020).
Enterprise-wide Communication	"Integrating risk into the business strategies is very important, and for this to happen a high level of communication should exist between employees that are required to share the risk data and top management that should integrate this data in the strategy setting process" (Respondent 8)	Effective communication between stakeholders is essential for integrating risk management into organizational strategies (Brown & Black, 2019; Robertson et al., 2021).
Structure and Ownership	"Structure and ownership are critical to ERM integration, ownership of ERM should be clearly defined by the senior management or the board of directors and available to people at the organization so that everyone will know where we heading to in ERM adoption" (Respondent 20)	Clear ownership and defined structure are vital for effective ERM integration, ensuring that risks are identified, managed, and reported appropriately (Olteanu et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2020).

Overall, the convergence between interview insights and academic research underscores the universal recognition of key principles in ERM integration. The alignment between empirical findings and theoretical frameworks lends credibility to the assertions made by interviewees, reinforcing the importance of strategic planning, effective communication, and structured ownership in fostering successful ERM adoption within organizations.

4.10 Chapter summary

This chapter combines theoretical and empirical research findings where several topics with regards to ERM adoptions were discussed in the telecommunication industry. The research indicates that senior management support plays an essential role in adopting and implementing effective ERM frameworks. The data presented indicate that ERM assists management in making risk-adjusted decisions and that ERM has facilitated the transformation of internal controls in the telecommunication sector. The research also indicated that the choice of ERM framework is guided by the external and internal factors unique to the player in the industry. Different respondents indicated that they face different internal and external factors, and therefore, the interconnection between these factors guides the choice of the ERM framework. The research discovered that the adoption of ERM face resistance due to a lack of senior management support, lack of information on how the system can be aligned with the organisational goals and objectives, and the inability to develop a risk culture that effectively supports the ERM initiative.

The empirical research found that the telecommunication industry in Algeria is in the early stages of ERM adoption, with some players still using traditional risk management methods. The respondents were aware of the advanced ERM frameworks, and some explained the benefits of adopting the systems. However, they indicated difficulty implementing the systems' concepts, such as incorporating the frameworks into the existing processes and functions. Therefore, the research findings formed the basis for developing an adoption that is specific in nature and customised for the Algerian telecommunication industry.

The following chapter will discuss the empirical finding in accordance with the body of literature.

CHAPTER 5 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS.

5.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter validates the academic research and findings to confirm a practical ERM framework in the Algerian telecommunication industry. It also aims at developing an ERM adoption Framework to be applied in the Algerian telecommunication industry. The research findings identified a wide gap in industry risk management which shows that the sector is exposed to the dynamism of the risks environment. Therefore, the chapter seeks to link the academic literature and the research findings to conclude the actual state of risk management frameworks in Algeria's telecommunication industry. The research, therefore, shall weave the research findings with the body of literature to display the strengths and vulnerabilities of the industry.

5.2 Objective 1: To explore the factors that triggered ERM adoption

5.2.1 Data Breach due to Low-risk awareness amongst employees.

The responses by the respondents noted that data breach was a serious issue facing the industry. For instance, Amakiri and Juliet (2018) argued that data breach is among the operations threats related to organisational processes, systems, business value chains, and, most importantly, people. The threats arise from customer trends, competitors, and other corporate stakeholders where the sensitivity of user data becomes important. Hoyt and Liebenberg (2015) advise that to manage risks effectively, organisations must consistently apply techniques that focus on reducing, if not eliminating, the risks. The first step to managing these risks is to identify them effectively.

The telecom organisation recognises and detects the various risk threats it is exposed to through reviewing and determining the risk profiles associated with specific risks. The organisation's leadership must agree on the inherent risks that the organisation can live with and choose the risk mitigation processes that cannot be tolerated. The next step in risk management is risk evaluation to determine the level of exposure. The identified risks are managed, and financial risks are hedged (Valinejad *et al.*, 2018). Managing risks in the telecommunications industry in Algeria is done by a team of experts from different business areas. Each business area identifies the risk it is exposed to, and the expert analysis is shared to create a comprehensive enterprise risk management document.

5.2.2 Fluid dynamics and Constant Industrial changes

Another important challenge in the industry is fluid dynamics and constant changes. The respondents interviewed in the research revealed a variety of arguments.

Unlike the analog era when few people accessed telecommunication lines in Algeria, the digital transformation has made it easy for people to reach others easily. Technology introduced new telecommunication products, some of which are internet enabled. Algeria has continued to improve its telecommunications infrastructure after introducing synthetic regulatory measures and formulating new government policies to deliver sustainable internet connections. Lancaster (2021) explained that despite the efforts by the government and the industry to encourage the adoption of telecommunications products, the country lags in the international arena in absorption.

There are various telecommunication players in Algeria, such as Algérie Télécom, Mobilis, , Orascom Telecom Algérie (Djezzy) and Ooreedo, which have received additional spectrum from the regulator aimed at addressing poor services. The government is also approving

procedures for organisations to upgrade to lite networks. Another development by the government is the installation of fiber optic cables to replace copper cables to enhance the distribution of the internet to the country. Another reason for low telecommunications product intake is that people feel that the products are costly, especially with the current economic status after the Covid-19 pandemic. Job losses and challenging economic times make the products less priority, with people opting to attend to urgent needs other than buying telecommunications products. There are various risks that the telecommunication industry faces related to finances, compliance, operations, and strategy, which the players must put into consideration to ensure industry profitability. The players must develop ways to manage these risks; for instance, financial threats emanate from market volatility and ecosystems, while compliance risks are associated with corporate governance, politics, and regulatory frameworks.

Respondents agreed that telecommunication systems are vulnerable to cybercrimes, which exposes the customers' data to hackers. When a telecommunication firm suffers a security threat, customer privacy is affected, reducing the customer's trust in the organisation. The respondents indicated that data privacy is a regulatory requirement, and therefore, organisations must use enterprise risk mechanisms that actively protect individual and organisations' data from unauthorized access. The respondents' views align with Ouaras and Lalaoui (2021), who noted that there had been significant changes with the emergence of the information society in Algeria, also referred to as the digital age, over the last few decades. The era is associated with speed, technological advancement, and flexibility, where information is being shared freely through telecommunication. The development has caused a significant change in consumer behaviors at individual and organisational levels. Among the notable changes are the internet and e-commerce

and the transfer of big government data to telecommunication platforms. Algeria has realized the need to integrate the digital tool into society's fast and widening needs.

The Algerian government has provided interventions in the telecommunication industry to boost teaching customer reach. Various government policies have been formulated to improve telecommunication infrastructure, reduce costs, and improve services. They have engaged in lowering taxes to encourage people to adopt online transactions. Algeria's challenge is consumer protection with advances in technology and increased online transactions using telecommunication portals (Bensaada and Taghzout, 2019). The current research depicts a scenario where the telecommunication industry in Algeria continues to be exposed to privacy and security risks. The authors indicated that the telecommunication industry requires a risk framework to protect the organisation. The sector can comprehensively adopt various international frameworks and standards to manage organisation-wide risks. The advantage of inclusivity in risk management is that empowering employees in risk management provides the organisation with a holistic approach to risk management and allows for identifying diversified risks.

5.2.3 Supply chain problems

Supply chain risks are the likelihood of an event occurring in the supply value chain, including sourcing raw materials. Supply chain risk management involves activities that mitigate the risks in the supply chain. Algeria's telecommunication industry deals with various suppliers for technology and other requirements. The modern telecom industry is highly complex with cutting-edge technology. The sector requires the latest technologies to remain in business and retain its competitive advantage. Most of the players in the industry have digital transformation as their strategic plan, and therefore they must engage different suppliers to enhance their telecom products' quality. Chen *et al.* (2021) explained that the telecom industry faces various supply chain

risk factors due to the complex nature of supply chains. The primary aim for these firms is to develop sustainable supply chains with the lowest risks and highest returns. The industry depends on the global supply chains, which have their risk profiles. These firms aim at understanding the supply chain management risks to develop mechanisms to mitigate them. Alunda (2015) argues that modern firms have invested in outsourcing and buying product components instead of investing internal resources in their production to shorten the production process and save costs. Supply chain risks threaten the future of telecommunication organisations, which are required to develop resilience for future existence through ongoing management of supply chain risks. Some of the supply chain risks include shortages. Telecommunication organisations deal with specialised suppliers, prone to deficiencies due to demand.

Sourcing for alternatives could be cumbersome and expensive, affecting a firm's sustainability. Algérie Télécom (Mobilis) partners with Stream System to supply electronic devices such as smartphones and tablets. The supply chain risk will happen if the supplier of the smart device fails to deliver due to a shortage. The telecom company would suffer sustainability due to a lack of devices for the final consumer. Supply chain risk exists both in the internal and external environment. According to Chen *et al.* (2021), securing supplies such as semiconductors and other raw materials for the telecommunication industry in Algeria, such as rare-earth elements, is becoming a hurdle for these organisations due to shortages. Global tensions between critical players also contribute to needs, which leaves these organisations with few alternatives. The scarcity created an unprecedented rise in prices for raw materials and relevant components, which hiked Algeria's telecommunications products.

According to Chatterjee and Kar (2018), supply chain risks can be categorized into economic, political, environmental, and ethical, which disrupt the operations of these industries.

Economic troubles are associated with the economic instability of the state or the organisation. The lack of capital to support digital transformation is one of the financial risk challenges that telecommunications industries in Algeria experience. Political risks involve political unrest, which could lead to vandalizing transmission lines. Environmental risk challenges include natural disasters such as floods and earthquakes that tamper with the optic cables and other transmission wires, thus making the organisation unable to supply telecommunications products. Ethical risks can be related to labor laws and customer protection laws, where the organisation is expected to act ethically towards employees, customers, and other stakeholders.

5.2.4 Cyber Risk

The respondents also revealed that cyber risk is a serious issue facing the telecommunication firms leading those firms to adopt an enterprise-wide risk approach in order to tackle this risks effectively. This argument rhymes with the findings from literature where it emerged that the Telecom industry is a target for cyber-crimes globally. Cybercriminals have aggressively attacked these organisations due to the amount and quality of information transmitted. Attacking a telecommunications organisation leads to exposure of intelligence and other sensitive information, destroying an economy. According to Brunetti *et al.* (2020), the modern telecommunication industries are used by corporate organisations to provide cloud and data services which then exposes the corporate organisation systems to cybercriminals if these organisations are attacked. The challenge is that individuals and organisations have expanded demand for telecommunications products, which has led to concern about ensuring data privacy and security. Pauletto (2020) argued that advancement in technology represents a chance for the growth of cyber-crimes as cybercriminals develop new ways to access telecommunications

systems to have access to the government, corporate and individual information to use to commit frauds. Algeria's intelligence also relies on the telecommunication industry for data and communication services, exposing security risks. The author investigates how telecommunications are challenged in developing effective cyber policies and norms and how sensitive customer data is to cybercrimes. The author also investigates how telecommunication industries are exposed to global connectivity internationally. The study found that telecommunication firms suffer from weaknesses in internal operations, such as updates and implementations. The researcher indicated that some telecommunication firms failed to actively and comprehensively update security measures to curb cyber-crime.

Ouaras and Lalaoui (2021) noted that there had been major changes with the emergence of the information society in Algeria, also referred to as the digital age, for the last few decades. The era is associated with speed, technological advancement, and flexibility, where information is being shared freely through telecommunication. The development has caused a significant change in consumer behaviors at individual and organisational levels. Among the notable changes are the internet and e-commerce and the transfer of big government data to telecommunication platforms. Algeria has realized the need to integrate the digital tool into society's fast and widening needs. For the country to achieve the objective of satisfying the needs of contemporary society, there is a need to increase internet penetration to boost e-commerce in the country (Sasmita & Suhaimi, 2019). The Algerian government has provided interventions in the telecommunication industry to boost teaching customer reach. Various government policies have been formulated to improve telecommunication infrastructure, reduce costs, and improve services. They have engaged in reducing taxes to encourage people to adopt online transactions. Algeria's challenge is consumer protection with advances in technology and increased online transactions using telecommunication

portals. The researchers argue that customer information is prone to unauthorized disclosure, such as personal information or organisational data, which can be used to commit fraud. Other data challenges include misleading commercial practices and privacy issues. E-payments pay to expose a customer's payment information to hackers who may lead to loss of funds if the customer's account details, such as pins, are exposed. A government may expose intelligence information to hackers, threatening the country's security. If exposed to cyber security, organisations' data may cause organisational failure by exposing the organisation to other risks such as reputational risks. The authors, however, noted that the challenges are hurdles that telecommunication industries can address and ensure that they remain in business and customer information is protected. Pearson (2013) defined a security threat as a potential safety and security violation. The telecommunications industry protects assets for customers who subscribe to their services, such as customer data, public authorities who formulate regulatory directives for them, and network operators and other service providers whose interest is to safeguard their interests to meet the obligations they promised to customers. The author concurred with other researchers by identifying the various threats facing the communication industry, such as unauthorized customer information disclosure, data destruction or modification, theft or loss of information, service interruptions, and data frauds such as impersonation and representation the authorized individual or organisation. The author analysed these threats as accidental, which are not predetermined, such as physical system malfunction, or they could be intentional, which means they are determined by people who are aware of the system operations, such as staff who can organize sophisticated attacks that lead to data destruction or organisational losses. Threats can also be active, resulting in a significant change in the state of operation, or passive, which involves information threats that do not cause the change of systems. The author also recognised that some of the security threats

are caused by security vulnerabilities and identified various types of vulnerabilities in the telecommunication industry, including; model vulnerabilities caused by failure by leadership to predict potential future threats. Design and specification vulnerabilities are oversights found in a protocol or system design that affect a system's functionality. Implementation vulnerabilities occur when a system or a protocol is being implemented, which causes system failure. Lastly, configuration and operation vulnerabilities are errors from improper system usage or deployment policies and practices. Security risk thus measures the potential adverse effects resulting from a security vulnerability. Algeria's telecommunication industry is exposed to this security, privacy, and data threats.

5.2.5 Telecommunication Businesses' complexity

The respondents also acknowledged that complexity of the telecom business is a serious issue which relates to the complexity of the business operations. This argument aligns with the outcomes of the literature. For instance, Ruiz-Canela López (2021) argues that most organisations have not tried to understand the different definitions of ERM. They find ERM a complex affair to integrate into the risk processes. The researcher argues that ERM does not spell out the responsibility of corporate governors in risk management.

Notably, corporate governors should leverage ERM components critical for understanding the risk appetite and tolerance levels. Corporate governance seems too influential in risk management, overshadowing the ERM framework. The respondents made the complexity understandable by indicating that said Networks Operations, HR, Risk and Compliance, Marketing, and Customer Excellence departments (respondents 11 and 17). The literature showed

that the rigidity thus fails to expose the other staff to the risk management process, whereas risk management should be each and everyone's responsibility. Besides centralizing risk management, all staff members should be trained to identify and share opinions on various risk management processes. Modern ERM encourages staff to be empowered in managing and mitigating risk and should be given control systems to report and comment on methods to control the identified risk. The advantage of inclusivity in risk management is that empowering employees in risk management provides the organisation with a holistic approach to risk management and allows for identifying diversified risks. The risk management holistic approach also allows brainstorming on various methods of risk management, where all people offer opinions in their areas of expertise (Beasley *et al.*, 2010). Telecommunication industries have highly operationalized risk management, which sounds complex. Many of these firms create risk management processes that involve complex centered on spreadsheets that are not user-friendly. These systems may lead to misreporting or misrepresenting risks, thus engaging poor risk management processes. Contemporary ERM frameworks encourage enterprises to use ERM applications that are easy to manage and use, making it easy for all employees to identify and report risks in their jurisdictions. Odabaşı *et al.* (2020) explained that Algerian telecommunication firms use complex risk management processes, making only experts understand the systems. The firms train the risk management team to use the current applications, leaving out these risks. The outcome is that the people who are supposed to be trained on risk identification and reporting are left out, exposing the firms to daily risks that could have been otherwise mitigated.

5.3 Objective 2: To explore the challenges facing ERM adoption

The following subsections discuss the key challenges associated with ERM adoption and implementation as identified by respondents in the context of the literature review.

5.3.1 Lack of senior management support

The research indicated that the lack of proper support largely derails the ERM implementation. The lack of senior management support for ERM adoption and implementation has been widely debated in the literature. Regardless of the nature of an industry, ERM is considered as a top-down approach, where top management set the tone of the strategic direction of the organisation. Researchers like Fraser and Simkins (2008) advocate that the perspectives of top management with regards to ERM baseline, as a key driver towards performance. The respondent's arguments regarding the importance of top management supports as a key for ERM adoption and implementation among telecommunications firms also gain support from a variety of stakeholders in the industry. For instance, Walker and Brown (2019) argued that digital transformation in the telecommunication industry is inevitable because the sector offers opportunities to sell digitally innovated products. Thus, organisations must ensure managerial support to enhance their competitive advantage. An advantage of top managerial support is the provision of risk frameworks that monitor the digital domain to identify the risks that threaten the core development of the organisation. Telecommunication firms operate in a complex digital environment that is prone to constant changes. Thus, the firms must build tolerant risk frameworks that protect the organisation from threats that originate from digital transformation. The study findings supports confirms that the lack of top management support remains a problem in the adoption and implementation of ERM.

5.3.2 Lack of sufficient resources for ERM adoption.

The research also found that the lack of sufficient resources for ERM adoption negatively affects the adoption of ERM systems. The respondents noted that the resources might comprise direct or indirect funds. Also, it entails the resources required to fund different aspects of ERM

enhancements, such as training and developing in-house skills.

The respondents indicated that the organisations suffer from the rising costs of materials and technology, making it hard to install ERM frameworks. The organisations feel that the frameworks consume the organisations' resources, which are already strained by the high cost of product delivery. The respondents' sentiments align with Manral and Harrigan (2018), who argue that organisations must understand consumer trends to offer customer-centric products. Producing these products requires top-notch technology and adequate research, requiring sufficient funding. However, the authors argued that the organisations require an ERM framework that manages the risks without spending a fortune on the organisational resources. Chen *et al.* (2021) research also aligned with the argument and indicated that the Algerian telecommunication industry needs to embrace ERM frameworks that help manage investment risks to protect the stakeholder's interests. It is argued that ERM is a prudent way to allocate resources, save on costs and improve operational efficiency (Wen and Yu, 2012); this seems to contradict the empirical findings.

5.3.3 Lack of clear guidelines on ERM implementation

Al-Khadash *et al.* (2017) agree that a lack of guidelines ruins ERM implementation and thus impacts the firm's performance. The authors argue that ERM framework guidelines direct the ERM implementation and determine the quality of the system performance. When guidelines are followed, the organisation can successfully determine which risk factors need quick actions and responses and which are not pressing, depending on the risk scale created by the system. The authors also agreed that ERM guidelines allow the organisation to share the organisation's scarce resources among the existing and potential risks to develop risk responses. Applying practical guidelines allows the organisation to effectively increase its risk appetite and venture into more risky ventures. Chalker *et al.* (2018) concurred with the respondents that a lack of guidelines prohibits the organisation from choosing ERM frameworks that protect the stakeholder value. The

authors explained that lack of clear implementation guidelines ruin ERM implementation by failing to identify the ERM frameworks that help in effective risk identification to enhance financial performance. The authors also agreed that practical guidelines enhance regulatory and legal compliance. Therefore, a lack of guidelines leads to adopting ERM frameworks that cannot monitor the regulatory schedules, thus exposing the organisation to regulatory risks. The authors also indicated that the lack of guidelines denies the organisation's adoption and implementation to quantify the stakeholder's value. Guidelines offer the organisation a chance to evaluate the different ERM frameworks and choose the best that aligns with the organisation's strategic planning and systems that can determine the amount expected as the stakeholder value.

5.3.4 Lack of ERM culture in the organisation

The respondents indicated that the lack of an appropriate organisational risk culture negatively affects the system's success. Previous research demonstrated that enterprise risk culture is one of the main barriers that can hinder ERM effective adoption (Lee and McGannon, 2003). Culture is considered as a significant element of an ERM program (COSO, 2016), and a good practice, through which organisations can safeguard organisational performance, value creation and reinforce the strategic resiliency practices (McShane and Rustambekov, 2011).

According to Hopkin (2017), improving organisational risk culture leads to the improvement in ERM outputs and performance. However, key aspects of a good organisational risk culture are yet to be determined (Althonayan, Keith, and Killackey, 2012; Ashby, 2012). Previous research indicate that results can differ due to the key attributes that every specific industry assign to culture (Paape and Spekle, 2012)

Risk culture has been frequently mentioned in previous studies as a key factor that contributed to corporate scandals during the global financial crisis (Ashby, Palermo, and Power,

2013; De Jonghe *et al.*, 2013; McConnell, 2013). A risk culture constitutes of the attitudes and behaviors of people and groups within the organisation that are related to risk-awareness, risk-taking and risk management (EY, 2014a). Constraints such as beliefs, experiences, communication, common risk language, or informal norms, can hinder an enterprise-wide risk culture (Chenhall, 2003). Muralidhar (2010) concluded that unsupportive organisational culture is a factor that obstruct ERM implementation. This seems to be congruent with the empirical findings. Most of the respondents indicate that the current ERM system among telecom firms in Algeria are not culturally integrative and thus only define the roles of the senior leadership and risk team and their responsibilities in risk management (Sasmita and Suhaimi, 2019).

5.3.5 Lack of understanding of the benefit of ERM

The respondents further showed that the lack of understanding of the benefits of ERM is a serious problem facing its adoption. For instance, respondent 17 noted insufficient information and a lack of understanding of ERM adoption's potential value and benefits can impede the ERM adoption. Equally, the respondent 13 argued perceived system complexity, inadequate training programs that educate employees about the benefits of adopting an ERM program is among the key challenges hindering the effective adoption of an ERM program. These arguments are in congruence with previous research. As according to the findings in the literature reviewed in chapter 2, little is known about the benefits of ERM implementation in practice (Keith, 2014). Benefits of ERM implementation have been analysed as an adoption precursor for organisations (Zeghal and El Aoun, 2016). Previous studies have acknowledged the vitality of understanding the benefits of ERM , as they represent the main drivers towards its adoption and implementation (Zhao, Hwang and Low, 2015)

5.3.6 Lack of in-house skills experienced in ERM implementation is ok

According to the empirical findings, the evolution of technology in the telecommunications industry requires a technical workforce that matches technological innovations. The industry players face talent shortages to work with the innovative technology that transverses beyond borders. Respondents have highlighted the importance and need to build secure, reliable, and resilient telecommunications networks, which requires qualified expertise, and faces a workforce shortage. Sourcing for the required talent is cumbersome for these organisations as they need a workforce pool to combine expertise for service delivery. Anie (2015) states that the telecommunication industry lacks the capacity and talent to fill crucial organisational positions, exposing them to quality threats. The constant changes in technology may also render the current skill redundant if they are not updated with the present technology. Changes in technology thus force the organisation to train the existing human resources or declare positions vacant in search of new talent. There is a lot of uncertainty in talent risk management because the issue is multifaceted. The risk is also associated with acquiring and retaining the right talent (Sasmita and Suhaimi, 2019). The author argues that skill allows the organisation to maintain a sustainable competitive advantage because talent brings about innovations leading to new products and services. The organisations face retention risks once the talent has been acquired. Retaining talent is a daily activity where the forms ensure that the best talent remains. Retaining high-performing talent may involve using tailor-made incentives which encourage them to perform more. Respondents argued that many telecom industries in Algeria lose talent to their competitors. Conclusion: there is a notion that best-performing employees will remain with the organisations and thus fail to plan for the exit. When they unexpectedly leave the organisation, the leader is thrown into a frantic search of matching talent, which may engage talent that does not match the current technology. The talent risk affects organisations that do not keep a pool of skills to fall back on when the best talent exits. The author concludes by indicating that managing talent should

be a crucial process for telecommunication organisations due to the current changes in digital transformation. The products and services handled by these organisations suggest that they must retain cutting-edge talents who constantly innovate to maintain competitiveness. Algeria is an emerging digital economy. Therefore, there is a need to engage the right people to develop innovative products at affordable prices to encourage the uptake of telecommunications products.

Warner (2019) cited another talent risk challenge as failure to align talent adequately with the specific tasks. Some telecommunication firms fail to allocate tasks to skills to reduce organisational costs. The leadership, therefore, engages talent that may seem to have more experience in handling new tasks, which may lead to product and services compromise. The researcher explains that when talent alignment is done right, it scales organisational productivity as people do best. Low workforce productivity leads to quality compromise, which affects corporate revenues. Some of the telecommunication firms in Algeria have inadequate programs to attract talent, making them lag in productivity. The firms fail to be innovative, making their growth stagnant. They do not have lucrative programs that attract highly paid talents. The lack of programs to attract talent leads to a capability gap, where the existing employees are left behind by advancing technology. The capability gap leads to the inability to apply new technologies required to innovate new products. Retaining the critical staff is another talent risk, where attrition affects businesses in many ways, such as creating growth gaps. Fundamental lack of talent makes the organisation lack compelling development capability and attractive talent management programs to enhance employees' capabilities, thus bridging the skills gap. Ineffective work organisational design makes firms lack flexibility in creating workforce needs to meet demanding labor demands. The author concluded by arguing that firms that fail to manage talent risk employee issues that may affect business operations. There is a need to manage and mitigate business risk by developing employee programs that focus on staff deployment and redeployment, retention, and development. Creating programs that attract talent allows the organisation to recruit talent at par with technological

developments and produce superior telecommunication products. Algeria's telecommunication industry is in its early stages, and thus, talent management is crucial if the firms are to realize their full potential. Engaging talented and innovative employees will give the players a competitive advantage in the production of the telecommunications industry. The employees need to deliver changing consumer needs and produce innovative products that will benefit the consumer and the organisation. The telecommunication industry players in Algeria benefit from early entry, and thus, they can penetrate the market and set competition standards.

5.3.7 Lengthy adoption and implementation process

According to the empirical findings, it may take more than one year to adopt and implement a fully functioning ERM system. Respondents have highlighted that time that an adoption and implementation of an ERM program can take is among the main reasons that may hinder its adoption and implementation among the Algerian telecommunications firms.

Various things must be done before the implementation process is finalized, such as instituting an ERM board, reorganizing the governance structure, understanding the risk appetite, and restating the risk profile, all of which must be integrated with the ERM system before it is fully implemented. These tasks need high-level coordination, which may take more than six months to complete (Nasr *et al.*, 2019). Another reason why it may take a longer to adopt an ERM framework is that it is not easy to adopt a mature ERM program where all the features match the organisation's processes. Therefore, the framework must be developed to fit the organisation's processes and operations. The organisation's size also determines the length of time to adopt an ERM system. Complex organisations may take more than three years before the adoption process is initiated since it may involve various levels of decision-making (Nasr *et al.*, 2019). Notably, effective ERM systems take time to be fully developed. Therefore, organisations should not shy

away from adopting these systems due to their time in development and adoption.

5.3.8 Employees' resistance

The respondents agreed that employee resistance and exposure are serious issues facing the adoption and implementation of the ERM program.

The respondents suggested thorough training, ownership, and accountability methods for managing staff resistance. The responses and suggestions correspond with Onu and Mbohwa (2019). The authors argued that all staff must be educated on the need to embrace the risk management process and why every person needs to be part of the management process for any successful enterprise risk management. The authors indicated that staff plays an essential role in risk identification, reporting, and sharing ideas on how the risk can be managed, making them a necessary part of the ERM system.

The respondents argued that their organisation's lack of knowledge of the best risk frameworks exposes telecommunication firms to financial and reputational threats. Telecommunication products are currently reliant on developing the telecommunication networks and the Internet of Things (IoT), which offers the best innovation opportunities.

However, the innovations expose the firms to new risks that must be innovatively managed. The motivation, knowledge and expertise to innovatively manage these risks are lacking in the Algerian telecommunication organisations. The respondents' information aligned with Merghit's (2018) research which indicated that Algerian telecommunication firms need to understand the current ERM frameworks that allow for comprehensive risk management if they need to prosper in the digital transformation. The firms must engage expertise and invest in research to enhance their understanding of the dynamism in the telecommunication risk environment. The author indicates that Algerian telecommunication firms have developed tools to mitigate risks. Still, most

of them are yet to embrace comprehensive risk frameworks that allow for enterprise-wide risk management. The firms must rethink the enterprise risk management frameworks that align with the current dynamics in the digital environment. Telecommunications industries should adopt flexible risk management frameworks that can identify emerging risks and guide the risk managers on the most viable risk decisions to protect the organisation's stakeholders and could be embraced by all employees. The researcher indicated that telecommunication firms in Algeria must rethink internationally acceptable risk management frameworks to leverage the global market. The respondent argued that organisations need to understand the best risk management frameworks through research and engaging system experts to enhance the firm's competitive advantage. They argued that inadequate system knowledge leads to employees resistance therefore results in failure to adopt or poorly implemented system that fails to achieve the strategic risk objectives. Anie (2015) argued that the telecommunication industry lacks the capacity and talent to fill crucial organisational positions, exposing them to quality threats. The constant changes in technology may also render the current skill redundant if they are not updated with the present technology.

5.4 Objective 3: To explore the effectiveness of existing frameworks from respondent's view's

The empirical study sought to understand if there were firms that had adopted ERM systems and, if there were, how effective they were in risk management. The study also desired to understand if there were no ERM frameworks adopted, what risk management processes the organisations were using, and how effective the processes protected the firms from emerging risks. The research found that some Algerian firms have adopted partially an ERM system successfully. The respondents indicated that frameworks such as the COSO 2004 ERM framework and ISO 31000 are comprehensive to some extent yet, they do not illustrate into details how the integration

of organisational operations and human resources into the system should happen . The respondents indicated that the frameworks are complex in nature and do not offer a clear perspective regarding the way leaders and risk managers can make viable risk decisions in an unpredictable environment such as Algeria.

Respondents belonging to the four telecommunication firms studied stated that the organisations they work for partially adopted the ERM system, which meant they operated together with the traditional risk management frameworks. The respondents explained that the existing ERM frameworks have managed to minimize risks, but they lack clearer guidelines that are required to develop organisational resiliency. The organisations have identified ERM frameworks that holistically and actively identify the emerging risks. However, the organisations have not embraced the systems in totality, as they have adopted parts.

The respondents' information aligns with research conducted by Bensaada and Taghezout (2019), which indicated that the level of ERM adoption is a factor of firm size, the complexity of operations, financial ability, and choice of risk management designs. The authors indicated that ERM adoption in Algeria's telecommunication does not integrate innovative risk management designs and models. ERM frameworks recommend that all functions of the organisations be enabled to access them. Still, due to poor technology in some country areas, the firms cannot adopt and implement an organisational-wide risk framework. According to (Sobel, 2018), the adopted frameworks are not robust in risk management as they have failed to integrate human resources into the ERM strategy. Current ERM strategies advocate for the integration of human resources into the systems, which means that all employees of the organisation become risk management ambassadors as they are the ones handling daily organisational operations. The partial ERM systems adopted are not flexible enough to integrate the human factor and daily operations at a large scale. The ERM strategies thus will require the employees to identify and report the risks encountered during day-to-day operations and suggest possible ways to deal with them.

The partially adopted ERM frameworks have failed to effectively update the risk profiles, which allow for better risk decisions as per most of the respondents. The systems have not managed to cover organisational-wide risks that help identify potential risks and update the risk profile using the essential risk identification and evaluation metrics. The respondents explained that the organisations had not developed comprehensive risk responses because the risk profile update has incorporated the traditional risk management methods. This has led to the inability to manage unknown risks using the partially adopted ERM frameworks. These research findings have been supported by Tan and Lee (2021). They argued that one of the critical factors of the ERM framework is identifying potential risks and updating the risk profiles for effective management of risk decisions. ERM frameworks are technologically enabled to update the risk profiles to manage unknown risks better. However, depending on the level of ERM framework adoption, most partially adopted frameworks predict potential risks.

The respondent's information aligns with Buganová and Šimíčková's (2019) research which compared the advanced and traditional risk management frameworks. The authors indicated that the conventional frameworks treat risks individually, which offers a deeper understanding of the individual risk. However, the frameworks may not allow for comprehensive risk analysis, which analyses the relationship between risks. Therefore, traditional risk management frameworks are known to identify, analyse, and control risks at the departmental level. According to the respondents, the current frameworks only factor in the risks associated with the department, and thus, the departments do not know what other departments classify as risks. Therefore, the risk management systems do not allow inter-functional/departmental sharing. The respondents confirmed identifying departmental risks and developing viable department response methods. The responses agreed with Batarlienė (2018), who explained that the current methods used by the firms without ERM frameworks engage traditional frameworks that are limited in that it only identifies risks from the internal perspective. The methods only seek to identify internally instigated risks,

for instance, staff fraud. The plans, therefore, concentrate on the internal business environment, and those that seek to understand the external risk environment lack comprehensive mechanisms to explore the external environment exhaustively. Lack of capacity to analyse the external environment leaves the organisation vulnerable to new entrants, competitors, and regulators' risks. Another limitation is that the siloed methods make the departmental managers only develop mechanisms to deal with risks in their silos and thus become unable to handle any outside risks that can threaten their departments. The other major limitation identified in the research is that the siloed risk management methods make alignment with the strategic objectives hard since each department and branch prepares its risks and develops risk response mechanisms that may be hard to align with the strategic objectives. The risks are prepared and combined independently, making it hard to report and consolidate to align with organisational goals.

Another reason for failure to adopt ERM systems is management information and expertise. The respondents indicated they were aware of the risk frameworks, but they did not understand how they could be applied. The others suggested that the organisation does not have experts who can offer quality information for adoption and implementation decisions to the management. Lack of management information has hindered the adoption of the current ERM systems. Batarliené (2018) explained that for the administration to make viable decisions on ERM adoption and implementation, they must understand its value and potential. If the top leadership lacks this information, it may not

The research thus indicates several telecommunication firms in Algeria have embraced or are embracing the modern ERM frameworks, while others are still using the siloed methods. The firms that have embraced internationally accepted ERM frameworks and standards indicate risk management process has become easy and friendly, and they can now predict unknown risks. The firms have developed a risk culture where the stakeholders have been engaged in the risk management process. There are other firms in the trial era, and they are yet to fully integrate the

advanced ERM systems for full adoption and implementation. The firms combine the traditional frameworks and the current frameworks by identifying risks at the departmental and integrating them into the newly adopted partial ERM system. Therefore, the firms are still allocating resources to departments to identify and evaluate the risks related to their department. The other group of firms has yet to adopt the ERM system and therefore has used the siloed risk management frameworks with a wide range of limitations.

Algerian telecommunication firms operate in an environment that is marred with different risks, as discussed earlier in the previous chapters. The firms need to actively manage these risks to mitigate existing and emerging threats to save businesses from reputational damage and financial losses. Current ERM systems assimilate different organisational features to identify and reduce a firm's risks comprehensively. The existing ERM frameworks in Algeria have managed to minimize risks, but they lack the robustness that modern ERM frameworks require. The firms have not managed to identify robust ERM frameworks that holistically and actively identify the emerging risks. Bensaada and Taghezout (2019) noted that ERM in Algeria's telecommunication does not integrate innovative risk management designs and models. The researchers argued that the firms are affected by the country's technology level, which requires them to embrace innovative ERM applications. The technological advancement in the country limits them from using flexible ERM methods that can integrate daily operations into risk management. Tsikudo (2019) agreed with Bensaada and Taghezout (2019) by explaining that the government has not fully developed the technological infrastructure in the country, which has posed a challenge to these firms in embracing ERM frameworks that make the risk management process less complicated.

The current risk management systems in Algeria have failed to integrate human resources into the ERM strategy. Current ERM strategies advocate for the integration of human resources into the systems, which means that all employees of the organisation become risk management ambassadors as they are the ones handling daily organisational operations (Sobel, 2018). The ERM

strategies thus will require the employees to identify and report the risks encountered during day-to-day operations and suggest possible ways to deal with them. The employees should be empowered and trained to be part of the ERM applications, encouraging them to actively and proactively detect potential risks from the daily operations. Risks are usually posed by people and systems other than natural risks. Thus, employees should identify how their colleagues pose threats to the organisation and identify risks emanating from systems. Bensaada and Taghezout (2019) explain that Algerian telecommunication firms are system and environment centric in risk identification. Only the risk team is mandated to identify and manage risks without involving other human resources. The firms have focused more on the systems for risk management, where they concentrate on developing systems that manage risks while leaving out the human factor. When empowered with the right risk management tools, human resources in a firm is an effective risk management tool. Ruiz-Canela López (2019) argued that most firms focus on creating risk models that evaluate operational risks for telecommunication companies without integrating human resources. The researcher agreed with Bensaada and Taghezout (2019) that telecommunication firms should incorporate the human resource factor into the ERM system for better risk management outcomes. The risk challenges in the telecommunication industry are dynamic, making it essential to use innovative ERM processes. The human resource factor integration in ERM will help develop flexible systems adjusted to changing or emerging risks. Human resource innovation will create all-inclusive systems that will allow telecommunication firms to manage unknown risks.

From the above findings, the current ERM frameworks in Algeria lack of a risk-awareness culture where the firms create risk awareness among employees and customers. The firms must therefore ensure that the staff working in the organisation are aware of the potential risk that faces

the organisation. The firms should train employees on how to treat various risk occurrences. Telecommunication organisations operate in an environment where risk is dynamic, and there are possibilities of unknown risk occurrence, for instance, new forms of cybercrimes that the industry is unaware of. Anie (2015) argues that telecommunication organisations should have robust risk-awareness programs that educate employees and customers on avoiding being victims of these risks. Risk awareness culture advocates for programs that inform people about identifying threats before they threaten business operations. They also empower them on how to evaluate and mitigate when it occurs. The agenda should be prepared by understanding the risk environment, including the risk trends and dynamism, and developing awareness programs covering various risk areas and types. Algerian firms have been rigid in developing risk awareness programs, where staff rely on programs that take long before they are updated. Relying on awareness programs that are not up to date exposes the staff and customers to emerging risks (Anie, 2015). To ensure effective risk awareness programs, the firm must engage a robust security team that constantly updates the risk awareness programs to cover emerging threats. The ERM frameworks in Algeria need to build risk awareness cultures and focus on information sharing with the right stakeholders. The awareness programs should integrate digital transformation, one of the leading causes of risk in the telecommunication industry. Warner and Wäger (2019) urge telecommunication firms to build risk awareness programs that integrate digital capabilities in detecting and reporting. The researchers argue that the firms in Algeria have not managed to create robust awareness programs for employees and customers. Thus, employees have not been able to identify potential risks. Customer risk awareness programs have not affected consumer self-protection against possible risks as many consumers continue being victims of hazards such as cybercrime. The outcome is that the people who are supposed to be trained on risk awareness and reporting continue to be

exposed to potential threats, thus exposing the firms to daily risks which could have been otherwise mitigated.

Algerian telecommunication firms have not managed to deploy ERM technology effectively. The country's technological advancement programs have continued to lag. The government has recently embarked on technological advancement programs in the telecommunication industry, such as installing a 5G network, which aims to improve the speed and specialised operations in the country. Technical advancement limitations in the country make it hard for these firms to embrace advanced ERM frameworks. According to Bensaada and Taghezout (2019), the lack of developed technology frameworks in Algeria limits telecommunication organisations from creating technologically innovative ERM frameworks. The limited technology deployment in many parts of Algeria makes it hard for the firms operating in these areas to formulate robust ERM networks which cover risk challenges emerging from the regions. The researchers commented that the current efforts by the government to increase technology coverage in the country would assist the telecommunication industry in installing effective ERM frameworks that will help in robust risk management. Odabaşı et al. (2020) explained that imbalanced technology deployment in Algeria makes it hard for telecommunication industries to streamline ERM systems due to technology compatibility. Therefore, the firms formulate ERM systems for each region, making risk management expensive to streamline. Technology imbalance affects enterprise risk management because it provides the infrastructure necessary for building modern ERM frameworks. Advancements in technology in some regions cause telecommunication firms to create imbalanced risk management processes because the technology infrastructure deployed in some areas does not support advanced ERM frameworks. Lanz (2018) conducted cross-sectional research to determine the challenges facing ERM

development, and the researcher noted technology imbalance as one of the challenges. He argues that telecommunication firms cannot create uniform ERM frameworks in their different regions in Algeria because some areas have better technology than others. To venture into areas with poorly developed technology calls for the firms to build alternative ERM frameworks that are not technology-intensive. Lanz (2019) concludes by noting that there is hope for regional technology balance if the current government efforts to take technology to all regions become successful. Therefore, telecommunications firms will deploy a uniform ERM system that comprehensively covers risk challenges regardless of the area.

The current ERM frameworks partially adopted in Algeria have not offered a robust approach to dealing with risk warnings. Most of the ERM frameworks have not keenly focused on risk warning. Some firms have suffered from risks they were aware of as they ignored the risk warnings. The firms have directed much of their resources to identification and risk evaluation, but they have missed reading the signs to understand potential risks. Advanced risk management systems are integrated with risk warning tools to detect potential risks from daily activities. The risks display warnings that the organisation can consider to thwart a possible risk occurrence. Stanton (2019) argues that risk warning tools can be applied to prevent unknown risks in the telecommunication industry. A risk warning tool is a potent risk detector that enhances the risk management process and allows the organisational leadership to make risk warning decisions to prevent risk occurrence. Tsikudo (2019) agrees with Stanton (2019) and argues that the risk warning tool should be integrated into the current ERM systems to detect a risk occurrence. The author explained that the ERM frameworks in Algeria are yet to effectively integrate risk warning tools, which exposes them to potential unknown risks. Therefore, an industry-specific framework that is specific in nature and that address the above challenges as well as the specific internal and

external environment of Algerian telecommunications firms is believed to lead to an effective ERM adoption and implementation.

5.4.1 Importance of the alignment of ERM with key organisational areas

The implementation of ERM ensures value creation, better risk culture, accountability for the strategic direction of the organisation and as such, aligning ERM with key organisational areas remain highly significant (Gatzer and Martin, 2015). Empirical findings demonstrate that most respondents understood that in order to achieve the organisational objectives, an alignment between those objectives and different areas is critical. This is in line with the literature findings. The COSO ERM frameworks points out explicitly the significance and importance of the strategic direction (objectives) across the organisation. Effectively achieving this alignment does not only provide directions and expectations, but also promotes a risk safeguard that leads to enhance the way an organisation identify, understand, communicate, and mitigate its risks, at an enterprise-wide level (Miles *et al.*, 1978).

Respondents further highlighted that for this alignment to occur, awareness and a strong risk culture among employees are of a great importance that could contribute to enhance organisational value and achieve a more mature ERM program.

Surprisingly, respondents who could answer about the importance of aligning ERM with key organisational areas have agreed that their respective organisation does not used key risk indicators (KRI's) when setting the organisational strategic decision. Some of the respondents that occupy top management position have explicitly demonstrate that they clearly understand the significance and the implication of using such indicators, yet their organisation is still relying

on the Key performance indicators (KPI's) in measuring their results. As demonstrated in chapter 2, KRI's are those metrics that define the risk profile of the organisation. A key risk indicator demonstrate how strategy, processes, and the business architecture is serving the organisation (Scarlat, Chirita and Bradea, 2012). Developing Key risk indicators (KRI's) along with key performance indicators (KPI's) is suggested in the literature as demonstrated in chapter two, not only to define the organisational risk profile of the likelihood of risks, but also define how organisations are performing with regards to achieving their goals, accordingly it create value (Scarlat, Chirita and Bradea, 2012)

5.4.2 Importance of the internal environment

The present subsection demonstrates the role and effect of the internal organisational factors that influenced the adoption and implementation of ERM among the Algerian telecommunications firms.

1) Risk oversight Role

Risk oversight is the management of the RM processes and frameworks within the organisation in order to ensure that the right strategies, processes, and agendas are deployed in order to mitigate risks (Sithipolvanichgul, 2021). According to COSO ERM (2017), risk oversight is an important function within the organisation, and the management of any organisation becomes accountable when it takes on the right risk oversight role. The role of risk oversight is to ensure that the risk management strategy is applied and executed as per the guidelines (Caldwell, 2012; Ormazabal *et al.*, 2010).

Empirical finding demonstrates that the organisations belonging to the Algerian telecommunication industry fails to define who is accountable of risk oversight function within their respective organisation. According to Ishak and Mohamad Nor (2017), the responsibility of

risk oversight within and organisation should be clearly defined and allocated to a specific board committee who should be held accountable and responsible for the risk management strategies of the organisation, such as a risk management Committee.

2) Risk appetite that is aligned with the risk tolerance

According to respondents, aligning risk appetite with the organisation's risk tolerance is of a great implication for the organisation and that are aware of what can happen if the thresholds to risks exceed (Farrel and Gallagher, 2015). Risk appetite is an important part of risk governance, it indicates the amount of risk that the organisation is willing to take when establishing its strategies (COSO, 2004b; CSA, 2003; Deloitte, 2015; EY, 2013, 2014a; Mcging and Brown, 2014). The importance of aligning risk appetite with risk tolerance allows organisations to achieve a balance between its willingness and ability to deal with risks and achieve strategic objectives. The findings are to some extent in congruence with the literature; however only top-level managers that have demonstrated the criticality of such alignment as compared to other respondents who occupy other low responsibility functions within their respective organisation.

3) Corporate Governance

Corporate governance (CG) refers to how an organisation is focused, controlled, and administered. It entails setting the rules and regulations that apply to processes, practices, systems, and procedures. It establishes accountability, assurance and structure in decision making (Dabari, Kwaji and Ghazali, 2017). Respondents have highlighted that corporate governance within their respective organisation seems to not provide a clear definition for the roles that should be played by the different stakeholder within their organisation (Manab *et al.*, 2010).

4) Strategies and Objectives

Every organisation is specific in nature; consequently; it is its mission, vision, and values which defines its business direction. The way in which an organisation select its strategies and establishes its objectives that define the risk oversight options, as such, the achievement of its already defined mission, vision, and values depends mainly upon the risk oversight support (COSO, 2017).

Respondents acknowledged that aligning ERM with the key organisational strategies and objectives is highly significant and of a great implication for the success of ERM adoption.

5.4.3 Importance and influence of risk culture in ERM adoption

This subsection sought to investigate the role and impact of a risk culture on ERM adoption and implementation among the Algerian telecommunication firms. Specifically, the following section demonstrates the main attributes that constitute the risk culture and are critical.

1) Sharing information

A significant number of respondents have agreed that sharing valuable information that could be of implication to the decision-making process can brings benefits to all the involved parties.

Rodriguez and Edwards (2010) advocate that sharing information is done through individuals, processes and technology. The authors argument ascertain that human factor is the most critical. Empirical findings demonstrate that respondents understood the criticality of sharing valuable information across the organisation as a significant factor towards ERM adoption.

2) Risk mind-set

Risk mindset is an important component of the ERM culture. It demonstrates the criticality

of problems such as risk insight, information sharing and awareness. An organisation that lacks important information needed to managing risk, tends to face issues in the decision-making process, this is because the top management when formulating strategies to manage risk effectively did not receive the required information. This is of an important implication as a lack of risk mindset within an organisation can make the organisation to miss opportunities to evaluate or react to both internal and external risks, on time. Therefore, ingraining a risk mindset amongst employees is significantly important in order to achieve an effective ERM (Agarwal and Ansell, 2016)

3) transparency and communication

COSO ERM framework 2004 highlights the importance of communicating and sharing risk information in timely manner. Clear and transparent communication when adopting an ERM program creates a transparent environment, which lead to create a strong risk culture within the organisation (Kenwood and Rafferty, 2017). Respondents have confirmed that transparency and communication is an important and critical practice in order to achieve performance. Empirical findings therefore confirms that a link exists between transparent communication and the achievement of effective ERM.

4) Accountability

According to FSB (2014), risk is owned by the one's that are closest to its occurrence. In general, this happens through a bottom-up approach (Muralidhar, 2010). Previous studies define accountability from two different folds: individual responsibility and organisational responsibility. The former one focuses on management and individual's behaviors, tasks and roles. Whereas the latter concentrate on evaluating the performance and progress with regards to the achievement of objectives. regardless of the top-down or bottom-up approach, the accountability of risk remains

at the organisational level, and everyone within the organisation is held responsible for managing risk (Mcging and Brown, 2014). With regards to empirical findings, respondents however tend to agree with the findings as confirm that in order to achieve an effective ERM, everyone within the organisation should be responsible and become accountable of managing risk.

5.4.4 Importance and effect of an ERM infrastructure in the adoption ERM framework

This subsection investigated the effect and importance of an ERM infrastructure in the ERM adoption framework.

1) Supporting technologies for ERM

Respondents have clearly demonstrated that adopting new technologies that support ERM are one of the key elements of the ERM infrastructure. The purpose of ERM technology is ERM implementation, is to support its long-term feasibility and leverages automation of the risk practices, and therefore, leads to a better and robust structure that manage risks (Francis and Paladino, 2008)

2) policies and frameworks of ERM

Policies and framework are part of the controls activities guiding organisations in order to effectively respond to risks (COSO, 2004). Policy is the statement that guides organisations to sets objectives and vision of ERM and the framework complements this policy through its processes and practices (Chapman, 2011). Moreover, it is the policy that illustrates how the framework should be applied as well as how actions and processes must be handled (Chapman, 2011). With regards to empirical findings, respondents recognise the importance and the implication of policies

and framework and their impact on becoming a resilient organisation with regards to managing risk.

Risk data

According to Hofmann (2009), risk data that is integrated and transparent in nature are required in order to produce a robust risk reporting strategy, and a constant flow of information to the top management. Empirical findings shows that a considerable number of respondents agreed that their respective organisation have difficulties in integrating risk data through the organisation.

4)ERM oversight structure

An oversight structure is the structure that is responsible for aligning communication, business functions and practices with the organisational objectives (Fraser and Simkins, 2010). Empirical findings explicitly highlight the critical role of an oversight structure that supports coordination of structure, practices and responsibilities (Andren and Lundqvist, 2017) and the effective deployment of ERM.

5.4.5 Importance and effect of ERM integration

1)Strategic planning

According to Lam (2010), ERM when aligned with strategies, will facilitate the integration of ERM. In general, ERM is integration occur through a top-down approach that consolidate strategy and objectives with the strategic planning (COSO, 2017). With regards to empirical findings, strategic planning was found to be critical to ERM integration.

2)Enterprise-wide communication

As discussed earlier in chapter two when developing the proposed ERM adoption framework, communication plays a vital role in developing an enterprise-wide risk culture. According to Oliveira *et al.* (2018), communication of risks across the different organisational departments promotes awareness and accuracy of information. Furthermore, it warrant a continuous process of obtaining valuable data that is required for the reporting process across the organisation. (COSO, 2017). Respondents considers an enterprise-wide communication as very important to ERM integration.

3)Structure and ownership

Structure and ownership refer to how the processes and roles within the organisation are defined. In other words, Chendhall (2003) described the processes and roles as the mechanism towards achieving performance. In the view of respondents, structure and ownership is of significant implication to ERM integration.

5.5 Objective 4: Validating The proposed ERM adoption framework

The current research indicates many benefits that an organisation derives from adopting advanced ERM frameworks. The study has shown that Algerian telecommunication firms studied have not fully adopted and implemented an ERM system , yet, they have applied some principles and guidelines of internationally accepted ERM frameworks such as the COSO ERM 2004 framework and the ISO 31000 in an attempt to improve their risk management practices. However, a holistic risk management approach is yet to be achieved. Therefore, the proposed ERM framework is meant to bridge the risk management gap in Algeria's risk management environment for the telecommunication industry (Linke and Florio, 2019). ERM is a continuous process that

holistically addresses an organisation's risks based on a portfolio approach focusing on all organisational risks to formulate and develop effective frameworks to achieve strategic risk mitigation. Algerian telecommunication industry requires ERM frameworks that protect the firms from challenges emanating from digital transformation. The proposed Strategic ERM will be a multi-approach framework that enhances organisations' capabilities to manage known and unknown risks and integrate a risk warning tool that detects signs of a possible risk. The theoretical framework developed in Chapter 2 was based on the four internal and external business environment risk pillars of the ERM framework, namely; the input factors, which include the key risks that need to be managed through the system, organisational strategies, risk appetite, culture and awareness, and corporate risk governance. The foundation on which the system is built represents the risk framework and infrastructure (Anton & Nucu, 2020). Integration is the system's ability to integrate the human and operational factors and output factors, including the system's risk management process.

Therefore, the four pillars are used to validate the proposed Strategic ERM framework by validating the critical factors that affect the adoption and implementation of the system (Anton & Nucu, 2020). The plan suggests that there will be a need for collaborative efforts among the organisation's functions, such as independent risk function, risk committee, and system champions, during the adoption and implementation of the ERM program. The organisations will need to build strong ERM internal support and engage the risk resources to ensure the right risk culture is being infused. The proposed ERM framework will require robust risk governance, as indicated during the interviews. The respondents indicated that the key elements that encourage the adoption of the ERM framework include comprehensiveness in risk management, competitive advantage, strategic planning, effective risk response, risk management coordination, improved risk decisions, and prediction of unknown risks (Linke and Florio, 2019). Another change to be included in the foundation pillar is transforming the ERM framework into a cyclical element. The ERM

framework involves the fluctuations of the risk management trends. The interpretation of the research findings, indicate that the ERM key elements must work together to achieve a balanced and aligned policy framework of risk management tools with support from the risk infrastructure of KPIs and KRI (Shatnawi & Eldaia, 2020). The respondents indicated that there is no universal definition of risk management, and each organisation determines the enterprise risk related to each organisation. Therefore, the proposed frameworks help identify and maintain risk diversification and develop the interrelationships between various risks and the risk culture (Hassan and Yazid, 2019). The ERM framework will support robust risk identification, assessment, and response in the telecommunication industry. The research also confirmed a need for solid risk education and awareness among stakeholders. The proposed ERM framework is user-friendly and integrated with learning programs to help users understand the system.

The proposed ERM frameworks align with organisational strategy and objectives, which guides the choice of the framework. After understanding the system and organisational goals, the risk management process involves identification, assessment, treatment, control/mitigation, and monitoring (Hassan and Yazid, 2019). The specified model addresses noted ERM issues and applies an enterprise-wide framework that reflects the enterprise risk challenges in the business's internal and external environment. The proposed ERM framework is consistent in addressing different risk challenges, dynamic and flexible to accommodate dynamism of the risks in the telecommunication industry, user-friendly, eliminates the complexities of systems to allow easy interface for fast risk process, and has a clear guide for implementation. The most crucial concern of the ERM framework is to address risk challenges to achieve the strategic objectives set by the telecommunication firms. The framework recommends the integration of risk management silos and integrating the system into the existing risk management processes. The system provides an infrastructure through which the different functions share risk information. The proposed approach is fitted with a cross-functional risk application that supports risk information sharing (Linke and

Florio, 2019). The framework recommends the integration of risk management silos and integrating the system into the existing risk management processes. The framework provides an infrastructure through which the different functions share risk information. The framework further encourages a uniform risk language and enhances uniformity, and lays the foundation of a risk awareness culture.

According to the respondents, the success of the ERM implementation is a factor of accountability and ownership at all system levels. Every stakeholder should be aware of their role in adopting and implementing an ERM program (Hassan and Yazid, 2019). The proposed ERM framework offers explicit coordination between different organisational functions and has a mechanism that allows top managers to monitor the coordination of the risk management process. Changes effected on one function updates in the whole system for comparison and monitoring. Each stakeholder is responsible for handling their risk responsibility, but the ultimate responsibility lies with senior-level management and risk directors (Al-Farsi, 2020). The proposed framework is built to manage risks and encourage senior management support and sponsorship, which emerged as one of the issues that prevented the effective adoption and implementation of ERM frameworks among telecommunication firms in Algeria. The proposed ERM framework is aligned with the firm's strategic objectives to address the risks from a holistic approach. The framework will define the roles of the risk management stakeholders at all organisational levels to break the risk management processes' rigidity (Al-Farsi, 2020). The research indicates that the current ERM systems in Algeria are not integrative and thus only define the roles of the senior leadership and risk team and their responsibilities in risk management.

The proposed framework is built in a way to comprehensively manage existing and emerging risks to reduce assumption changes, thus making the work of the top management and risk department easy. This is a selling point to organisational leadership as the system

simultaneously manages organisation-wide risks (Hassan and Yazid, 2019). The ability of the framework to manage enterprise-wide risk simultaneously saves time and organisational resources; thus, the framework should reduce top management resistance towards ERM. The corporate governance and enterprise risk managers should be sensitized to adopt the approach that will intrinsically align with organisational corporate and business strategies. Another issue identified by the research was that the ERM system faced stiff resistance where the staff thought the traditional frameworks were easy and friendly to use (Alawattegama, 2018). However, the current proposed ERM framework is user-friendly with the guided user. The user does not do the essential metrics calculations because the system has been enabled to calculate the risk profiles. The user will only need to key in the required details while the system handles the calculations. While making it easy for the user, the system provides a standardized risk reporting and evaluation method.

The proposed adoption framework considers various elements appropriate for adoption and implementation, including senior management support and buy-in, management support and sponsorship, value demonstration, risk education programs, risk management cycle, and risk culture. The respondents argued that for effective implementation of the ERM system, the organisation must embrace a strong risk culture, which involves a standard mechanism in which an organisation perceives and approaches risks, understands the risks, and discusses risk issues between the board and senior management (Hassan and Yazid, 2019). Influential risk culture requires all organisation members to be exposed to risk management practices and be empowered to handle risk responsibility related to their areas of operations (Hassan and Yazid, 2019). The respondents who indicated full adoption of the ERM system informed the research that the risk management enthusiasm is felt across the organisation as the board and senior management

support and sponsor the system. Thus, the board and senior management drive the system's adoption to succeed. Therefore, the proposed adoption Risk Framework encourages a risk awareness culture capable of a high acceptance level for the ERM adoption to maintain sustainability (Shatnawi and Eldaia, 2020). The risk management culture should be promoted among employees to gain acceptance other than forcing it on them, which means that the employees should be part of the adoption and implementation process. The proposed framework also demonstrates value and potential to the sponsors and other stakeholders and thus enhances the acceptance and support of at-risk management levels (Al-Farsi, 2020). The ERM framework is aligned with strategic factors in the telecommunication industry in Algeria, which focuses on the risk appetite, which is the level of risk challenges the organisation wishes to live with, risk oversight, risk awareness culture, corporate governance involvement, and strategic objectives (Alawattegama, 2018). The framework is flexible enough to monitor the emerging risk challenges in the telecommunication industry. Therefore, the organisational leadership monitors the system to oversee the risk management process and identify the industry's potential internal and external threats. The telecommunication industry in Algeria is undergoing digital transformation, requiring telecommunication firms to adopt risk management models that will allow transitioning from one risk management step to another, such as the courses of action to take once the risks have been identified and assessed (Al-Farsi, 2020). The proposed framework allows for a step-by-step risk management process that guides the best risk response depending on the risk profile (Shatnawi and Eldaia, 2020). The ability to navigate the risk management process increases system acceptance due to the value and potential of the system. The respondents indicated that the current systems are weak in risk management, which exposes the firms and the industry to various risks.

The strategic ERM framework's integration component comprises coordinated communication, risk management ownership and structure, risk training and awareness, and effective integration of silos. The risk training and awareness will be added to the framework and will form part of the risk culture, which is a continuous effort to ensure an enterprise-wide risk awareness, be handled through the implementation process for the existing staff, and form part of risk training for new organisation entrants (Sasmita and Suhaimi, 2020). Risk training and awareness will encourage risk ownership in the risk management process. Before adopting the proposed framework, the company will need to apply the SWOT and PESTEL analysis to identify the factors in the external and internal environment. These external and internal factors assessment tools will be based on the organisational needs and level of exposure to the risk environment. As discussed in Chapter 2, the framework informs the steps for integrating the internal and external factors into the ERMM framework. Therefore, the system alignment will be based on the flexibility and uniqueness of the organisation's needs and risk requirements (Ruiz-Canela López, 2021). The strategy's communication will help integrate risk training and awareness sessions into the risk framework. Therefore, the system will allow for new risk challenges and leverage the currently existing risk management frameworks.

5.6 Chapter Summary

The chapter discussed a variety of risk paradigms in the telecommunication industry as per the findings in Chapter 4. The research indicates that several factors determine the adoption and implementation of ERM frameworks necessary for risk management in the telecommunication sector. The study found that top management support played a significant role in implementing and adopting the ERM frameworks. Therefore, while recommending the ERM framework, it is

essential to offer adequate management information indicating the framework's value and potential, enhancing management buy-in. The research findings in chapter 4 also indicated that the organisation's choice of the ERM framework depends on the organisation's internal and external factors that affect the organisation's risk environment. The internal factors discussed include top management support, risk culture, and strategic objectives aligned with the new ERM framework. The most significant challenges addressed in this chapter had support and buy-in, system knowledge and expertise, developing a supportive risk culture, and describing the value generation potential. The chapter validate the proposed framework as well as offers guidelines on the proposed Strategic ERM framework adoption.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

This chapter gives a brief summary of the findings and shows how they helped reach the research goals and answer the research questions from chapter one. In this chapter, the goals of the research are looked at, and the methods used to reach those goals are explained in detail. Also, the ways in which the body of knowledge has changed are shown. This chapter also talks about recommendations to fill the research gap that was found during the research, as well as suggestions for more research.

6.1 Conclusions

The research aimed to investigate the factors affecting ERM adoption and develop a framework relevant to the telecommunication industry in Algeria. The study was conducted through academic and industry-based practical research, which aimed at understanding the factors for ERM adoption in the telecommunication industry. Chapter 4 discussed the risk challenges facing telecommunication in Algeria, which indicated that the industry is undergoing digital transformation with the government intervening to ensure a broader technological coverage in terms of network and internet. The country has been lagging technologically, which has slowed down the adoption of technology-intensive applications for many industries. Adopting a 5G network will allow the industrial players to adopt technology-intensive applications to improve productivity and enhance rewards. The research found that the telecommunication industry is transforming with the digital transformation at a tremendous rate. Therefore, there is a need to adopt a risk management framework that actively manages existing and emerging risks.

6.1.1 Objective 1

The study found that various factors for ERM adoption in the Algerian telecom organisations generates competitive advantages such as digital growth and diversification. For a long time, the Algerian telecommunication firms have lacked effective digital change, contributing to limited technological growth. This makes the industry less innovative in product diversification and provision of digital services. Limited technological development in the country has led to the failure to identify the addressable market to develop consumer-oriented digital products. Algeria addresses speed and accessibility challenges by adopting 5G networks and the IoT, which should be an excellent opportunity for these players to seize. Developing and implementing effective strategies leads to business failure, associated with higher exits in many telecom industries. The research indicates that providing digital services is the top priority for these organisations. They have failed to develop customer-centric models that encourage consumers to use their products. The research indicated that the priorities for telecom industries in Algeria included digital business models, customer experience, cost control, IT systems improvement, and increasing organisational agility. Lack of effective digital growth and diversification is a risk that prevents a business from realizing its full potential in venturing into the telecommunications market. The study found that Algeria's digital transformation is in its early stages, with the players expecting a rapid shift to high volumes of digital product consumption. Another risk challenge addressed by the research was the complexity of the business risk environment. The current telecommunication business industry is complex due to changes in technology required to deliver telecommunication applications to different customers. The sector offers complex products through a comprehensive infrastructure composed of fixed-line, cloud services, data, and mobile services. The underlying technology used by these firms is highly complex, which makes it difficult for these firms to conduct business. The

complexity of the systems is further aggravated by the constant changes in technology which these firms must constantly adapt to ensure to offer customers digital products that are up-to-date. The changes in technology represent the external business environment that guides the adoption of enterprise risk management systems. Therefore, the research argues that the government of Algeria must create incentives that encourage the telecom industry players to invest in digital transformation and cushion them from possible losses due to a lack of proper risk management systems. The other issue in business complexity is regional technological imbalances in Algeria, where some parts of the country are not technologically supported, making it hard for telecommunication firms to embrace an enterprise-wide risk system. Thus, these firms may not have sufficient interventions to tackle the issue of business complexity in tackling digital transformation from a systematic and risks point of view. The push to transform customer experience and create new organisational efficiencies makes these organisations launch several digital transformation projects, most of which face some complex barriers. Supply chain risks involve the production and supply of telecommunication products. The firms face challenges in choosing the most appropriate technologies to deliver telecommunication products to consumers. The firms are working towards achieving the digital transformation, which exposes them to supply chain risks. Technological advancement also exposes customer information to privacy and security risks. Most of these risks are emerging threats because they emerge with technical progress. As technology develops, cybercriminals enhance their skills in developing software that attacks these telecommunication systems. The role of ERM frameworks is to identify, assess, evaluate, control, monitor and mitigate these risks. The effectiveness of the ERM frameworks depends on the external and internal risk environments discussed by this study.

6.1.2 Objective 2

The study found that the current telecommunication industry in Algeria has not fully embraced the recommended ERM frameworks due to limitations in technology, top management resistance, lack of expertise, and lack of management information. Some firms have adopted international ERM frameworks, but most rely on traditional risk management methods. Traditional methods are siloed where organisational functions identify and manage risks related to their silos and do not know what happens in other silos. The research found that Algerian firms have embraced ERM frameworks that are comprehensive and allow the integration of organisational operations and human resources into the system. The organisations' risk processes have changed, and the risk managers' work has been made simple by adopting the current ERM frameworks. The firms enjoy a competitive advantage as they offer a holistic risk management framework that saves the organisation's resources. The ERM framework enables the organisation to manage the risks organisation-wide, which means that the risks are managed across departments and branches. ERM frameworks offer a mediating and risk moderating role, thus allowing organisations to maintain competitive advantage; explained that the organisations that adopt ERM frameworks have better risk-focused culture. The research found that the firms that have adopted the ERM frameworks have developed a risk culture where all employees are aware of the type of risks to look out for and report. Employees can now identify the risks that threaten operations, and they are aware of how to report the risks. Another advantage these firms enjoy is making informed risk-adjusted decisions as the frameworks use key risk metrics to update the risk profiles.

The study also found that firms had not fully adopted the ERM frameworks. Therefore, they only adopted the system parts to be integrated with the current risk management systems. Failure to fully embrace the plan was cited as a lack of management information on the value and

potential of the system, management resistance, firm size, the complexity of operations, financial ability, technological advancement, and choice of risk management designs. The partial system adopted by these firms does not fully identify unknown risks. The current ERM frameworks in Algeria have not offered a robust approach to dealing with risk warnings. Most of the ERM frameworks have not keenly focused on risk warning. Some firms have suffered from risks they were aware of as they ignored the risk warnings. The firms have directed much of their resources to identification and risk evaluation, but they have missed reading signs to understand potential risks. The partially adopted ERM frameworks have failed to effectively update the risk profiles, which allow for better risk decisions. According to the research, the organisations do not have comprehensive risk responses because the firms conduct risk identification from individual silos. This makes it hard to combine risks from different silos into one ERM system partially adopted. The risks metric used by separate silos may not be aligned with the adopted partial system, thus the inability to develop the best risk profiles, which help manage potential and unknown risks. The research indicated that ERM adoption in Algeria's telecommunication does not integrate innovative risk management designs and risk representation models due to the limitation of technological advancement. The ERM systems are built on leading-edge technology has self-updating software. However, the firms in Algeria only adopt ERM systems that align with the country's technology level. Some of the ERM technological components are not compatible with the level of technology in the organisations. Limited technology in some areas of the country prevents the firms from adopting and implementing an organisational-wide risk framework, thus forcing the departments and branches to continue using siloed risk management systems. The adopted partial frameworks are not robust in risk management as they have failed to integrate human resources into the ERM strategy. Current ERM strategies advocate for the integration of

human resources into the systems, which means that all employees of the organisation become risk management ambassadors as they are the ones handling daily organisational operations. ERM systems adopted by these telecommunication firms cannot create a robust risk awareness culture because they are partially adopted. Partial adoption forces the organisations to work with traditional risk management frameworks, which are rigid in developing risk awareness programs. The research also found that firms are relying on traditional risk management systems. According to the respondents, the firms have failed to embrace the current ERM systems due to a lack of system information, adequate resources, management resistance, and system knowledge and expertise. The systems do not offer an enterprise-wide risk management process because they are narrow and can only accommodate some bits of the risk process. The inability to adapt comprehensive organisational risks makes them only suitable for use per department. This limitation, therefore, makes it hard for the organisation to make viable risk decisions since each department/silo manages its risks independently. Traditional frameworks treat risks individually, which offers a deeper understanding of the individual risk. These risk processes concentrate on the internal business environment, and those that seek to understand the external risk environment lack comprehensive mechanisms to explore the external environment exhaustively. Lack of capacity to analyse the external environment leaves the organisation vulnerable to new entrants, competitors, and regulators' risks. Siloed methods make the departmental managers only develop mechanisms to deal with risks in their silos and thus become unable to handle any outside risks that can threaten their departments. Traditional risk management methods make alignment with the strategic objectives hard since each department and branch prepares its risks and develops risk response mechanisms that may be hard to align with the strategic goals. Operating siloed risk management

frameworks require the organisation to allocate risk management resources to all its functions which is expensive.

6.1.3 Objective 3

The empirical findings from the semi-structured interviews were used to address this goal. The results listed a number of problems that respondents thought could make it hard to adopt and use ERM effectively. They include but are not limited to lack of senior management support, lack of sufficient resources for ERM adoption, lack of clear guidelines on ERM implementation, lack of ERM culture in the organisation, lack of understanding the benefits of ERM implementation, lack of in-house skills experienced in ERM implementation, lengthy adoption and implementation process and employees' resistant to change.

6.1.4 Objective 4

The research developed a strategic ERM framework that aligns with the organisation's objectives and allows for enterprise-wide risk management. The proposed framework will offer an inclusive risk management mechanism that helps the telecommunication firms in Algeria to manage both existing and emerging risk challenges, especially during the digital transformation. The proposed ERM framework is meant to bridge the risk management gap in Algeria's risk management environment for the telecommunication industry. ERM is a continuous process that holistically addresses an organisation's risks based on a portfolio approach focusing on all organisational risks to formulate and develop effective frameworks to achieve strategic risk mitigation (reference). Algerian telecommunication industry requires ERM frameworks that protect the firms from

challenges emanating from digital transformation. The proposed adoption framework allows the organisation to monitor the internal and external risk environment by identifying risk pillars of the ERM framework, namely; the input factors, which include the key risks that need to be managed through the system, organisational strategies, risk appetite, culture and awareness, and corporate risk governance. The proposed ERM Framework will allow the telecommunication departments and firms to collaborate and share risk information to enable the organisation to manage better existing and emerging risks. The proposed risk management framework requires the telecommunication organisations to build strong ERM internal support and engage the risk resources to ensure the right risk culture requires robust risk governance. The risk governors should be at the forefront to lead the system adoption and implantation. The proposed framework help identify and maintain risk diversification and develop the interrelationships between various risks to inform which risks. ERM framework will support robust risk identification, assessment, and response cultures in the telecommunication industry. The research also confirmed a need for solid risk education and awareness among stakeholders. The proposed ERM framework is user-friendly and integrated with learning programs to help users understand the system.

6.1.5 The proposed framework

The proposed ERM system aims to introduce a paradigm shift in understanding and managing critical factors for system development and implementation within the telecommunication industry. In response to the volatile and unpredictable nature of markets, the framework emphasizes flexibility to accommodate the strategic objectives of organizations across all operational scales. One key input into this Strategic ERM framework is the alignment of organizational strategy with risk appetite and tolerance, allowing telecommunication firms in Algeria to map risks based on exposure levels—whether high, medium, or low. The dynamic risk environment of the telecommunication industry

necessitates advanced risk management systems, and the proposed ERM system provides mechanisms for effectively managing operational, financial, technological, strategic, privacy, and security risks. The framework prioritizes these risks based on their impact as defined by the organization's strategic objectives.

Building on the limitations of existing models, the proposed ERM system seeks to address practical challenges faced by telecommunication organizations in Algeria. While the limitations of current models have been previously discussed, this section delves into the practical applications and implications of the proposed model. By aligning risk management strategies with organizational objectives and providing a flexible framework, the proposed model aims to enhance the adaptability of telecommunication firms to the evolving risk landscape. The discussion underscores the need for a nuanced understanding of the practicalities involved in implementing the proposed ERM system, acknowledging its potential impact on risk mitigation and strategic decision-making within the dynamic context of the telecommunication industry in Algeria.

6.2 Recommendations

6.2.1 Recommendations for Practice

- ✓ **Framework Development:** Future researchers are encouraged to further develop the proposed ERM framework, expanding its applicability beyond the telecommunication industry to cater to diverse sectors and external/internal risk environments.
- ✓ **Implementation Adjustments:** As the current study focuses on the telecommunication industry, it is recommended that the proposed ERM framework undergo adjustments for implementation in sectors beyond telecommunications. This will contribute to a broader understanding of its adaptability and effectiveness.

- ✓ **Technology Alignment:** Given the dynamic nature of technology, it is crucial to continuously align the proposed ERM framework with technological changes. Future research should ensure that the framework remains relevant and effective in addressing contemporary technological risks.

6.2.2 Recommendations for Policy

- ✓ **Mixed Methods Approach:** Future research should employ a mixed methods approach to combine qualitative and quantitative data, providing a more comprehensive understanding of ERM adoption. This approach enables a nuanced analysis, incorporating both qualitative insights and quantitative metrics.
- ✓ **Larger Sample Population:** To enhance generalizability, it is recommended that future research gathers a larger sample population. A more extensive and diverse dataset would contribute to robust findings, offering insights that can be applied across a broader spectrum.
- ✓ **Focus on Intangible Elements:** Future studies should delve into more intangible elements related to ERM adoption, exploring qualities essential to the proposed framework. This includes organizational culture, employee perceptions, and other qualitative aspects influencing ERM effectiveness.

6.2.3 Recommendations for Future Research

- ✓ **Continuous Framework Development:** Researchers are urged to continuously refine and evolve the proposed ERM framework, keeping it in line with technological advancements and emerging risk trends. This iterative approach ensures the framework's resilience and relevance over time.
- ✓ **Quantification of Framework Value:** Future research should quantify the value of the proposed ERM framework by assessing its benefits, shortcomings, and challenges. This

evaluation will provide a clearer understanding of the framework's impact on organizational performance.

- ✓ **Anticipation of Future Factors:** Researchers should proactively identify and examine future factors influencing the proposed ERM framework. Understanding the evolving landscape will aid in preparing organizations for upcoming challenges and facilitating proactive risk management strategies.

6.3 Contribution to the ERM literature

This research significantly contributes to the existing ERM literature in several meaningful ways. Firstly, it stands out as one of the pioneering studies to investigate ERM adoption within Algerian telecom organizations, addressing a notable gap in the literature. While prior research on ERM adoption primarily focused on Western countries, this study sheds light on the current ERM practices in Algerian businesses, providing crucial insights that serve as a foundational reference for future research in the country's ERM landscape. The empirical results of the study offer valuable information on the challenges faced by Algerian telecommunication organizations in effectively implementing ERM. Specifically, the research highlights the pivotal role of management support and the cultivation of an enterprise-wide risk culture as key factors influencing the successful adoption of ERM. Moreover, the study's empirical findings outline challenges and critical success factors essential for ERM adoption, empowering ERM implementers to formulate robust risk strategies. Additionally, the research introduces a tailored framework for ERM adoption specifically designed for telecom companies in Algeria. By adopting a qualitative research method, the study overcomes limitations associated with quantitative approaches, providing a more in-depth understanding of the intricacies involved in ERM adoption within these organizations. This contribution is particularly noteworthy in

bridging theoretical and practical aspects, aligning with identified research gaps and addressing practical challenges in the Algerian telecom sector.

6.3.1 Contribution to the Practice

The results of this study are important for how things work in the real world. I'll explain each contribution below:

1. **ERM implementers and senior managers:** The empirical findings of the study give Top management and the board of directors a better idea of what factors affect the adoption and implementation of ERM. These results could help organisations that are still looking into adopting ERM or that have already set up ERM deployment projects but didn't move forward because they didn't have the key parts of a good risk management framework. Also, the results may help organisations that have already started an ERM program take it to a higher level.
2. **Regulators and government bodies:** The empirical results of the qualitative study will help regulators and policymakers in the Algerian telecommunications sector make changes to the risk management policies that need immediate attention.
3. **Risk Culture:** For policymakers, the results show that an enterprise-wide risk culture has a big effect on the adoption and implementation of ERM and can change how well it works. So, the findings can help policymakers review policies about risk culture.

6.4 Limitation of the study

The study's limitations are notable and warrant consideration. Primarily, the research exclusively concentrates on the Algerian telecommunication industry, restricting the generalizability of its findings solely to this specific sector. To enhance the study's robustness, it would be beneficial to underscore the distinctive features of the Algerian context, providing a more nuanced understanding of the ERM adoption landscape within the country's telecommunications sector. Additionally, the study falls short in comparing its results with applications in other industries, limiting the scope of insights that could be drawn from cross-industry comparisons. Addressing this limitation by incorporating broader industry perspectives could contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of ERM adoption dynamics. Lastly, due to resource constraints, the study was unable to expand the participant pool. Despite this constraint, future research endeavours should aim to overcome such limitations by securing adequate resources to diversify the participant base, ensuring a more representative and comprehensive exploration of ERM adoption in the Algerian context. Furthermore, to mitigate data limitations, it is recommended to draw upon more recent and reliable sources, thereby enhancing the study's credibility and relevance.

6.5 Chapter Summary

The chapter has highlighted the previously discussed factors affecting ERM adoption and developed a framework tailored to the telecommunication industry in Algeria. The country has been lagging technologically, which has slowed down the adoption of technology-intensive applications for many industries. The research found that the telecommunication industry in Algeria is transforming with the digital transformation at a tremendous rate, exposing the industry

to emerging risks. The chapter also highlighted the risk challenges that face the telecommunication industry in Algeria. Slow growth in technology makes the industry lack product diversity. Developing and implementing ineffective strategies leads to business failure, associated with higher exits in many telecom industries. The research indicates that the current challenges in Algerian communications could be reduced if the industry adopts risk management frameworks that can offer enterprise-wide risk management applications. The firms are working towards achieving the digital transformation, which exposes them to supply chain risks that occur during the supply of telecommunication products.

The chapter has also highlighted the complexity surrounding the existing international ERM frameworks. The research indicated that recommended frameworks had not been embraced in Algeria, and most telecommunication firms rely on the traditional silo frameworks. Some respondents indicated that the firms have failed to embrace the current ERM systems due to a lack of top management support, system information, adequate resources, management resistance, and knowledge and expertise. However, some firms have partially adopted the ERM program, and they informed the researcher that the risk management process is not more straightforward. The study has proposed a framework that aligns with the organisation's objectives and allows for enterprise-wide risk management. The proposed framework will offer an inclusive risk management mechanism that helps the telecommunication firms in Algeria to manage both existing and emerging risk challenges, especially during the digital transformation. The proposed risk management framework requires the telecommunication organisations to build strong ERM internal support and ensure the right risk culture requires robust risk governance.

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APPENDICES

Ethical Approval Letter

06/10/2021

Dear Mohamed Amine Bouraba,

Your application 16717: Exploring the critical success factors to Enterprise Risk Management adoption within the Telecom Industry: Case of Algerian Telecom Industry, submission 14104, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study, you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

Descriptive Profile sheet

Participant's educational and professional Background

May I please request you to answer the following questions about your educational background, professional expertise, qualifications, and training?

1.1 What position do you occupy at your respective institution? And could you please provide a short job description?

1.2 Your precedent position:

1.3 Number of years spent within your current company:

1.4 University Education:

1.5 Professional Qualifications, Trainings, Certificates:

ERM Adoption at your institution

1. In your own words, may I ask you to describe your company's risk management system?

2. How would you describe in your own words an enterprise risk management system?

3. Have your company considered or adopted an ERM? If yes, could you please describe the actual adoption stage your company has reached?

. Investigating ERM concept, process, frameworks, but no decision has been made with regards to its adoption

. Considering its adoption, but no formal ERM in place

. Adopted, but partially.

. Fully adopted and implemented.

4. According to you, what drove your company to consider ERM adoption?

5. What is your perception with regards to ERM strategies and how do you think they differ from your institution's current risk management strategies?

6. Do you think that professional experience or educational background can influence ERM adoption?

7. In your opinion, does competitors' satisfaction with ERM adoption drive your institution to consider its adoption?

8. Have you been approached at any point by one of the big four with regards to ERM adoption and implementation?

9. What is your perception of top management support with regards to ERM adoption within your company?

10. Can you please discuss your involvement within ERM adoption process within your company?

11. Could you please state the departments responsible for ERM adoption?

12. In your opinion, what are the challenges facing ERM introduction and adoption within your own institution?

13. In what stage of ERM adoption is your institution at?

14. In your opinion, what are the risks associated with the introduction of enterprise-wide risk management within your company at an organisational level and how and to what extent could they be managed?

15. Do you think that ERM adoption would drive change at a strategic or operational level at your institution? If yes, could you please describe in your own words how?

16. In your opinion, does ERM adoption within your respective institution or in general does add value? if yes, could you please describe how?

17. In your opinion, what are the most critical factors or elements required for a successful ERM adoption?

18. According to you, what lack your current risk management process or system that led your institution or your competitors within the industry to consider and proceed with ERM adoption?

19. How would you describe top management and board of directors' support with regards to ERM adoption?

20. In your opinion, what are the key elements that can make individuals within your company accept and adhere to this change (ERM adoption)?

21. According to you, is ERM adoption widely supported by your top management or are there any other departments that show more support?

22. Do you have an idea about the international ERM frameworks available worldwide? If yes, can you state some?

23. Is your company following any internationally recognised framework or do you have one which is specifically designed to your institution?

24. How would you rate your motivational level and willingness in a scale of 0 to 10 with respect to achieving a successful ERM implementation?

The Interview has come to an end, I would like to thank you for your time to answer my questions.

For the purpose of this research, I may require to talk to you again. Would you agree to that? What would be the most convenient way to get in touch with you?

